

Transmedia History

Circulations, Reconfigurations and New Methodologies

Edited by
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Book of abstracts

About the Book of Abstracts

This book of abstracts is a compilation of texts provided by the authors for the Transmedia History Conference. The conference took place at the University of Lausanne (Switzerland) on January 27-28, 2025 and was organized by the History Department and the Impresso Project.

Abstracts are listed in the order of appearance in the program.

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Illustration:

25 November 1963 - A crowd of television, radio and press journalists attending District Attorney Henry Wade's press conference in Dallas, three days after the assassination of President Kennedy.

Photo Bill Sauro, Library of Congress, Wikimedia Commons.

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Transmedia History: Circulations, Reconfigurations and New Methodologies

Conference call for papers

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How can “transmedia” history be put into practice from both theoretical and empirical perspectives? The international conference “Transmedia History”—organised by the Impresso project¹ and the University of Lausanne’s History Department²—will gather scholars from various backgrounds around this question to exchange views on new prospects opened by digitisation and digital tools to carry out transmedia research.

Media history is composed of a myriad of parallel histories, which makes comparisons difficult (Fickers 2018, 121). Research in the field has indeed long focused on single types of media (newspapers, television, radio, ...) or single institutions within their national contexts. In the mid-2000s however, the transnational turn—which spread across all historical disciplines—allowed for new trends in research objectives to emerge (Bourdon 2008; Vallotton and Nicoli 2021). Research scopes overcame previous temporal and spatial frameworks and thereby became less driven by institutional perspectives than by contents and their circulation. Moreover, this new focus on transnational perspectives enlarged its scope to encompass a wider range of topics within media studies, such as technologies and communication. The development of the history of communication, cultural industries, techniques, and international relations all contributed to a form of *décloisonnement* or decompartmentalisation, that paved the way for a more comprehensive history of media systems (Mattelart 2002). These new approaches were made possible most notably by mass digitisation of media sources and the improvement of their online accessibility to researchers. International research networks gathered around such transnational ambitions. The first engaged with the history of the book (Society for the History of Authorship, Reading and Publishing - SHARP³) and the history of television (European Television History Network - ETHN, (Post)Socialist Television History Network), while, later on, other groups broached the radio (Transnational Radio Encounters - TRE⁴) and the press (Transnational Network for the Study of the Press in Foreign Languages - Transfopress⁵). The transnational turn was a major breakthrough that resulted in important publications (see for example Mollier and Lyon 2012 for the book; Fickers and Johnson 2012 for the television; Badenoch, Fickers and Henrich-Franke 2013 for radio and a global history of French-speaking press which is currently in the making).

It remains, however, that research in media history continues to face borders it has not managed to cross yet: beyond geographical borders, those between media institutions and between different types of media remain mostly uncrossed (Cronqvist and Hilgert 2017, 134). This challenge gave the impulse

¹ <https://impresso-project.ch/>

² <https://www.unil.ch/hist/home.html>

³ <https://sharpweb.org/>

⁴ <http://www.transnationalradio.org/>

⁵ <https://www.chcsc.uvsq.fr/transfopress-transnational-network-for-the-study-of-foreign-language-press>

for the establishment of the Entangled Media Histories (EMHIS)⁶ network in 2013. In a milestone article published in 2017, Marie Cronqvist and Christoph Hilgert—both members of EMHIS—defined the concept of entangled histories “as a means of better understanding the dynamic interconnectedness of media across semiotic, technological, institutional and political boundaries in history” (Cronqvist et Hilgert 2017, 130). Rather than accumulating histories of different media, they advocated for a focus on the elements that bridge them. This idea has a certain genealogy (Müller 2000) and theoretical debates have also broached the matter. This perspective was indeed articulated in different ways depending on the historical subdiscipline (global history, history of communications, history of techniques, history of cultural industries that incorporate sociological methods, etc.) and the national and linguistic areas. Despite this, a lack of empirical studies persists, primarily due to the enduring division of knowledge and the practical challenges associated with navigating separate, multilingual archives. These factors discourage research that moves beyond compartmentalised, sector-specific approaches. With the exception of a handful of significant works (see most notably Daniel, de Lima Grecco, Tamagne and Zierenberg 2023), monomedia perspectives still dominate the field of media history and too little research is being carried out on exchanges and cooperation between media.

This international conference aims to extend those efforts and reflections by inviting papers that prioritise a “transmedia” approach. We seek to present research that explores media history through the simultaneous analysis of different media, thereby emphasising the significance of the media ecosystems in which they co-evolve. A variety of terms have been used in fields like art history, narratology, journalism and communication to explore the interconnectedness of media (cross-media, intermedia, transmedia, etc.). With regards to history, it has occurred to us that “transmedia”—first used in narratology (Jenkins 2006)—was most suited to capture our ambition. We believe that it encompasses the study of various forms of circulation that occur between media (institutional, economic, technological, aesthetic, or content level). In this sense, we argue that “transmedia” refers with greater accuracy to our objective of transcending monomedia units.

“Media” is understood in a broad sense here. It includes traditional media (books, posters, press, cinema, radio and television), but also recent ones such as video games, the Internet (e.g. streaming services, podcasts, online news) and social media. The targeted timeframe is extensive, spanning up to the present day. The conference ultimately seeks to present papers that contribute to a decompartmentalised and interconnected history of media. These papers will not only place media history within a broader social, political, and cultural context but also foster a dialogue among them.

In this regard, we invite papers that fall within **three main research axes**:

1. Transmedia circulations, adaptations and reciprocal influences

Media history, which was also strongly influenced by the cultural turn of the 1970s and 1980s, has gradually expanded the range of media objects studied and the actors involved (Ruppen Coutaz and Vallotton 2019). The concepts of cultural transfer (Spain and Werner 1988) and acculturation (Dulphy, Frank, Matard-Bonucci and Ory 2010) have proved useful in understanding the international circulation of media productions, which is now increasingly being studied (Mattelart 2014). Such approaches highlight the importance of mediators (Cooper-Richet, Mollier and Silem 2005; Sapiro 2012) and the creation of new transnational circulation spaces.

The aim of this initial strand of research is to identify and analyse various factors that facilitate the circulation of content and formats across media and/or that foster interactions between media:

- specific actors or media professions such as news and advertising agencies, foreign correspondents, exiles and diaspora representatives active in various media, translators, arrangers, cross-border media;
- technological innovations like the telegraph, printing technologies, digital platforms or alternate reality games;

⁶ <https://emhis.blogg.lu.se/>

- spaces of circulation and exchanges that transcend traditional political and/or linguistic boundaries, such as fictional serial productions, co-productions, joint-broadcasts, technical cooperation associations in the telecommunications field, foreign-language press;
- socio-economic factors like concentration and financial globalisation, liberalisation and deregulation, convergence and new consumption habits.

It will also involve considering the rhythms and temporality of information, the modes of circulation (e.g. scissors-and-paste journalism), adaptations and reconfigurations (e.g. comics to radio), as well as the transmission of practices and the mobility of people. Finally, it will be important to investigate resistance to these phenomena, in the sense of factors that hinder or trouble transmedia circulation (seasonal and geopolitical conditions, legal matters, censorship, etc.).

2. Intersections, reconfigurations and new media genealogies

Traditionally, media history has viewed the advent of new distribution channels as significant ruptures per se marking the beginning of life cycles, each eventually bound to a certain downfall. Against this backdrop, new perspectives rooted in the *new media history* (Marvin 1990; Gitelman 2006) and *media archaeology* (Parikka 2012) provided counterpoints. Some have emphasised the relevance of synchronic approaches to study global transformations in the media system, as instanced by the “invention” of the telephone and, more broadly, by the evolution of images transmission. Others have put forth diachronic perspectives. In this vein, the notion of “live” transmission—which had been used to draw a line between television and cinema—provided an entry point for the exploration of media history through the lens of interdependence and competition. Likewise, analyses of “media imaginaries” (*imaginaires médiatiques*) acknowledged new periodisations that considered, for example, the presence of prophetic literary representations in communication or the recycling of media devices bound to disappear.

The goal set by this second strand of research is to provide a refined understanding of how media define themselves in relation to each other. Additionally, it seeks to shine light upon their strategies and motives, in order to appreciate better the complex ties that they maintain (Lits 2005; Letourneux 2017). How was the advent of new media perceived, announced and narrated by existing media? How do media publicise, promote and criticise other media’s content? We aim to identify productions and documentary resources that reflect such intertwined relations, such as anticipation tales, criticism in the press, advertising productions, etc. From a broader viewpoint, these considerations also address the evolution of mentalities towards new media, their gradual integration within the media ecosystem, as well as the reconfigurations of the latter.

3. New approaches, resources and methods

In what ways can the mass digitisation of archival collections and the advancement of computational analysis tools foster transmedia research? Computational research methods allow processing large volumes of data and in recent times also increasingly across languages and modalities (e.g. image, text, sound) (Arnold et al. 2021; Smits and Wevers 2023). Techniques such as text reuse detection (Salmi et al. 2020; Düring et al. 2023; Rosson et al. 2023) or the representation of textual elements in multilingual dense vector spaces (embeddings) (Reimers and Gurevych 2019) have been shown to serve large-scale comparisons and content exploration. But how exactly can computational approaches contribute to the advancement of a transmedia media history?

The third axis of this conference aims to identify (new and/or digital approaches that facilitate and bolster comparisons. Besides, it seeks to discuss methods which enable analyses of the circulation of contents and formats at scale, in order to enhance our understanding of information fluxes (Lundell, Hannu et alii 2023). Until recently, most projects that embraced data-driven approaches focused on a single media, mostly the press (see for instance Viral Texts Project⁷, Oceanic Exchanges⁸,

⁷ <https://viraltexts.org/>

⁸ <https://oceanicexchanges.org/>

Computational History and the Transformation of Public Discourse in Finland (COMHIS)⁹ or Information Highways of the 19th Century¹⁰). Research now starts to explore how to set up the processing—and how to conduct the analysis—of transmedia data; projects in the likes of TwiXL: An infrastructure for cross-media research on public debates¹¹, Clariah Media Suite¹² and Impresso - Media Monitoring of the Past II¹³ all welcomed this goal. We therefore look to understand the effects that the use of digital tools and methodologies has on the research practices of media historians (changes in scale, shifts between close and distant reading). More broadly, we want to question how the facilitated exploration of media sources affects the way we carry out historical research, especially in the field of media history (changing relation to sources, cross-fertilisation of research fields, emergence of new objects of study, new ways of presenting results, etc.). In doing so, we seek to assess the added value of digital tools for media history (Weber, Comte and Vallotton 2023).

By embracing a transmedia approach, papers gathered for this conference will:

- showcase shared, entangled histories, as well as differences and lesser-known relations and connections between media;
- discuss the application of novel methods and tools to conduct historical research and ground a theoretical and empirical reflection on complex interactions between media;
- enhance the global understanding of media ecosystem dynamics.

This conference seeks to contribute to the clarification and development of a transmedia approach in the historical sciences. It aims to address transmedia **from a historical, long-term perspective** and, more broadly, to promote a decompartmentalised, entangled history of media. We therefore encourage presentations from junior and senior researchers who wish to share their empirical and methodological approaches in this field.

References

- Arnold, Taylor, Stefania Scagliola, Lauren Tilton, and Jasmijn Van Gorp. 2021. 'Introduction: Special Issue on AudioVisual Data in DH'. *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 15 (1).
- Badenoch, Alexander, Andreas Fickers, and Christian Henrich-Franke, eds. 2013. *Airy Curtains in the European Ether. Broadcasting and the Cold War*. Baden-Baden: Nomos.
- Baetens, Jan. 2004. 'La novellisation, un genre contaminé ?' *Poétique* 138 (2): 235–51.
- Bourdon, Jérôme. 2008. 'Comment écrire une histoire transnationale des médias ? L'exemple de la télévision en Europe'. *Le Temps des médias* 11 (2): 164–81.
- Clavert, Frédéric, Martin Grandjean, and Cécile Méadel. 2018. 'Le temps long des réseaux sociaux numériques, une introduction'. *Le Temps des médias* 31 (2): 5–11.
- Cooper-Richet, Diana, Jean-Yves Mollier, and Ahmed Silem, eds. 2005. *Passeurs culturels dans le monde des médias et de l'édition en Europe (XIXe et XXe Siècles)*. Villeurbanne: Presses de l'Enssib.
- Cronqvist, Marie, and Christoph Hilgert. 2017. 'Entangled Media Histories'. *Media History* 23 (1): 130–41.
- Daniel, Ondrej, Gabriela de Lima Grecco, Florence Tamagne, and Malte Zierenberg. 2023. 'Mass Media and Popular Culture in Contemporary History (ca. 1900–2000)'. In *The European Experience. A Multi-Perspective History of Modern Europe, 1500–2000*, 875–84. Cambridge: Open Book Publishers.
- Dulphy, Anne, Robert Frank, Marie Anne Matard Bonucci, and Pascal Ory, eds. 2012. *Les relations culturelles internationales au XXe siècle : de la diplomatie culturelle à l'acculturation*. Bruxelles: P. Lang.
- Düring, Marten, Matteo Romanello, Maud Ehrmann, Kaspar Beelen, Daniele Guido, Brecht Deseure, Estelle Bunout, Jana Keck, and Petros Apostolopoulos. 2023. 'Impresso Text Reuse at

⁹ <https://www.kansalliskirjasto.fi/en/projects/comhis-computational-history-and-transformation-public-discourse-finland-1640-1910>

¹⁰ <https://www.oru.se/english/research/research-projects/rp/?rdp=p2403>

¹¹ <https://twi-xl.humanities.uva.nl/>

¹² <https://mediasuite.clariah.nl/>

¹³ <https://impresso-project.ch/>

- Scale. An Interface for the Exploration of Text Reuse Data in Semantically Enriched Historical Newspapers'. *Frontiers in Big Data* 6.
- Dyson, Kenneth, and Peter Humphreys, eds. 1988. *Broadcasting and New Media Policies in Western Europe*. London: Routledge.
- Espagne, Michel, and Michael Werner, eds. 1988. *Transferts. Les relations interculturelles dans l'espace franco-allemand (XVIIIe-XIXe siècles)*. Paris: Éditions Recherche sur les Civilisations.
- Fickers, Andreas. 2018. "Hybrid Histories" - Versuch Einer Kritischen Standortbestimmung Der Mediengeschichte'. *Annali Dell'Istituto Storico Italo-Germanico in Trento* 1 (44): 117–31.
- Fickers, Andreas, and Catherine Johnson, eds. 2012. *Transnational Television History: A Comparative Approach*. London: Routledge.
- Gitelman, Lisa. 2006. *Always Already New: Media, History, and the Data of Culture*. Cambridge MA: The MIT Press.
- Jenkins, Henry. 2006. *Convergence Culture. Where Old and New Media Collide*. New York: New York University Press.
- Letourneux, Matthieu. 2017. *Fictions à la chaîne, littératures sérielles et culture médiatique*. Paris: Seuil.
- Lits, Marc. 2005. 'De la culture populaire à la culture Médiatique. Marchandisation et mondialisation'. *Recherches Sociologiques* 2–3: 77–98.
- Lundell, Patrik, Hannu Salmi, Erik Edoff, Jani Marjanen, Petri Paju, and Heli Rantala, eds. 2023. *Information Flows across the Baltic Sea. Towards a Computational Approach to Media History*. Lund: Föreningen Mediehistoriskt arkiv.
- Martel, Frédéric. 2010. *Mainstream. Enquête sur cette culture qui plaît à tout le monde*. Paris: Flammarion.
- Marvin, Carolyn. 1990. *When Old Technologies Were New: Thinking About Electric Communication in the Late Nineteenth Century*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Mattelart, Tristan, ed. 2002. *La mondialisation des médias contre la censure. Tiers Monde et audiovisuel sans frontières*. Bruxelles: De Boeck Supérieur.
- . 2014. 'Les enjeux de la circulation internationale de l'information'. *Revue française des sciences de l'information et de la communication*, no. 5.
- Mollier, Jean-Yves, and Martyn Lyons. 2012. 'L'histoire du livre dans une perspective transnationale'. *Histoire et Civilisation Du Livre* 8: 9–20.
- Müller, Jürgen E. 2000. 'L'intermédialité, une nouvelle approche interdisciplinaire : perspectives théoriques et pratiques à l'exemple de la vision de la télévision'. *Cinéma et Intermédialité* 10 (2–3): 105–34.
- Negrine, Ralph, ed. (1988) 2013. *Satellite Broadcasting: The Politics and Implications of the New Media*. 2nd ed. London: Routledge.
- Parikka, Jussi. 2012. *What Is Media Archaeology?* Cambridge: Polity.
- Reimers, Nils, and Iryna Gurevych. 2019. 'Sentence-BERT: Sentence Embeddings Using Siamese BERT-Networks'. arXiv.
- Rosson, David, Eetu Mäkelä, Ville Vaara, Ananth Mahadevan, Yann Ryan, and Mikko Tolonen. 2023. 'Reception Reader: Exploring Text Reuse in Early Modern British Publications'. *Journal of Open Humanities Data* 9 (April): 5.
- Ruppen Coutaz, Raphaëlle, and François Vallotton. 2019. 'Histoire des médias et histoire des relations internationales: deux champs en dialogue'. In *Penser l'histoire des médias*, 149–56. Paris: CNRS Éditions.
- Salmi, Hannu, Petri Paju, Heli Rantala, Asko Nivala, Alekski Vesanto, and Filip Ginter. 2020. 'The Reuse of Texts in Finnish Newspapers and Journals, 1771–1920: A Digital Humanities Perspective'. *Historical Methods: A Journal of Quantitative and Interdisciplinary History* 54 (1): 14–28.

- Sapiro, Gisèle, ed. 2012. *Traduire la littérature et les sciences humaines. Conditions et obstacles*. Paris: Ministère de la Culture - DEPS.
- Sassoon, Donald. 2006. *The Culture of the Europeans. From 1800 to the Present*. Fulham: Harper.
- Smits, Thomas, and Melvin Wevers. 2023. 'A Multimodal Turn in Digital Humanities. Using Contrastive Machine Learning Models to Explore, Enrich, and Analyze Digital Visual Historical Collections'. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities* 38 (3): 1267–80.
- Sparviero, Sergio, Corinna Peil, and Gabriele Balbi, eds. 2017. *Media Convergence and Deconvergence*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Vallotton, François, and Miriam Nicoli. 2021. 'La collection éditoriale : une perspective transculturelle'. In *Espaces, formes et métissages de la collection éditoriale*, edited by Miriam Nicoli, Christine Rivalan Guego, Patricia Sorel, and François Vallotton, 11–19. Rennes: Presses Universitaires de Rennes.
- Weber, Anne-Katrin, Simone Comte, and François Vallotton. 2023. 'Audiovisual Heritage and its Uses at the Swiss Public Broadcaster: A Dialogue on Opportunities and Constraints for Archives and Academics'. *VIEW Journal of European Television History and Culture* 12 (23): 38–52.

"No Wall is Thick Enough to Stop Them" - Transmediality and Colonial-Critical Resistance in French West Africa 1900 – 1914

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Between 1900 and 1914, brochures, lithographs, and newspapers printed in Bologna, Cairo, New York, and Hamburg circulated freely in French West Africa, largely beyond the control of colonial authorities. This paper examines how these cross-media and cross-border connections significantly influenced the rise of a colonial-critical consciousness in the region through an interplay between local and global forces. The paper advocates for a critical reassessment of the concept of mass media, emphasizing the importance of transmedia competences and the practices they enable. It further argues that individuals occupying cultural intermediary roles within imperial contexts often possessed greater media competence than colonial rulers, a skillset that could be strategically applied in anti-colonial struggle.

1. The Sultan's Portrait

In August 1911, French colonial authorities intercepted a shipment of one hundred postal packages at the port of Dakar, Senegal (ANS 19G4). Each package contained high-quality art prints from a small printing press in Bologna, addressed to a Dakar-based Moroccan merchant. While the images themselves were not explicitly anti-colonial, the French authorities were highly alerted. A significant portion of the cargo consisted of portraits of the Sultan of Egypt (see figure 1), which the French interpreted as part of a pan-Islamic propaganda campaign aimed at undermining their influence in West Africa. This suspicion was seemingly confirmed by the sender of the prints: Abdel Hamed Zaki, an anti-colonial Egyptian activist, living in Bologna, where he published an anti-colonial caricature magazine notorious for its sharp criticism of European imperialism, the *Cairo Punch* (Booth 2013; Byron 2019)

Figure 1: *Sultans et Princes d'Islam, Cairo Punch 1911, Archives Nationales du Benin*

The confiscation of the Cairo Punch in the summer of 1911 is the micro-historical vantage point for this paper. In what follows, I will advance two arguments that bring together global transmedia history (Asseraf 2022; Cronqvist; Hilgert 2017) and new trans-imperial history (Brückenhausen 2017; Goebel 2016; Marsh 2019) First, I argue that global transmedia history provides a lens through which the inherent fragility of imperial rule and the lack of colonial control over information can be observed. The circulation of Cairo Punch prints exemplifies how a West African public sphere was able to form independent connections with other empire-critical publics in the Global South, illustrating an imperial loss of control. As one official remarked on the circulation of empire-critical information: 'No wall is thick enough to stop them' (ANS 21G24 versemment 108).

Secondly, as a media impact study, this paper posits that transregional entanglements significantly influenced cultural and political dynamics at the local level. This influence can be observed in how individuals, drawing on an enhanced transmedia competence due to their social and cultural position, engaged in self-politicization through the interplay of written, oral and visual carriers of information. The incorporation of Cairo Punch prints into local contexts by West-African middle-class actors catalysed the rise of one of Africa's first democratic, anti-colonial movements, the Jeunes Sénégalais (1913 – 1920).

2. Transmedia Densification and Colonial Fragility in French West Africa 1900 – 1914

Founded in 1907, the Cairo Punch was a sophisticated medium. Its editor, Abdel Hamid Zaki printed cartoons and illustrations in Bologna and sent them to Cairo, where they were put together with trilingual texts (Arabic, English and French). After the interception of the cargo in Dakar, the French authorities feared that someone in Senegal might assemble the images with anti-imperial text modules in a similar manner (ANS 19G4). However, it rather appeared that Zaki tailored his prints to local needs and demand. Nevertheless, the import of his prints disrupted an imperial media regime, which relied on a hierarchical diffusion of information from the metropolis to the periphery. Unsurprisingly, the French viewed this loss of control as a threat to their authority.

This colonial fragility is best illustrated through the link between the circulation of the Cairo Punch and the development of a distinct Senegalese technique of reversed glass painting: Suwer (*sous-verre*). While studies have examined Suwers from the 1950s to the 1980s, the origins of this technique remain obscure (Baj-Strobel 2013; Bouttiaux 1994). Recently, art historian Giulia Paoletti has linked Suwers to the global spread of portrait photography and depictions of saints from the Middle East, which reached Senegal in the late 19th century (Paoletti 2018; 2024, 62 – 68). Building on her ideas and my own archival research in Benin and Senegal, I contest earlier research that posits that Suwer originated as a response to colonial censorship by replicating banned art prints to meet local demand (Baj-Strobel 2013, 244). This assumption rests on the notion of effective colonial censorship, which archival evidence contradicts.

Archival records reveal thirty-three confiscations of lithographs, chromolithographs, brochures, and other imported media across West Africa between 1911 and 1916 (ANS 19G1-6; ANB 4E15). These discoveries often happened by chance. In December 1914, for instance, French authorities in Conakry seized a German shipment of over 850 chromolithographs, mainly portraits of Arab royals and leaders of Egyptian and Turkish Young-movements. Apparently, only heightened scrutiny of German cargo during World War I brought the shipment to attention (ANS 19G4).

The various imported media should be regarded as parts of a single, cohesive media flow that countered the European imperial portrayal of Islam. While French propaganda around 1900 depicted Islam as fanatical and resistant to progress (Harrison 1990, 29), publications like Cairo Punch and Egyptian newspapers presented a modern, dignified, and powerful Muslim world, often organised around portraits of Muslim royals. These portraits were integrated into local visual regimes, including Suwers. Findings from private collections suggest that portraits of sultans were a prominent motif in early Suwers. These generic portraits appeared as standalone motifs or as additions to religious images, serving as carriers of political information (Paoletti 2018; Samuel 2014, 2017, 2019; Schulz 2014). Rather than being a reaction to colonial censorship, Suwers supplemented the circulation of

images and texts from Beirut, Cairo, Bologna, and Hamburg, reflecting a cross-media densification of a globally entangled, local public sphere.

This densification can be further understood by considering the oral dimensions of a Senegalese public. Michelle Baj-Stobel has noted that reverse glass painting in Senegal was closely tied to oral knowledge transfer (Baj-Stobel 2013, 245-246). In Senegal, oral traditions were institutionalized by griots, oral historians who chronicled the reigns of Senegalese aristocrats. By the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the role of griots evolved alongside a globally interconnected Senegalese society. They became advertising agents for local traders, political mobilizers, and entertainers for the urban bourgeoisie (Diop 1935). This Senegalese bourgeoisie (Dejung; Motadel; Osterhammel 2019), the primary consumer of Cairo Punch prints, Suwers, and Arabic newspapers, occupied a unique intercultural position. Often trained in Islamic and French-schools, they combined the ability to read texts in both languages, with the financial means to afford luxury items like art prints and Suwers.

For this urban upper strata of Senegalese society, portraits of Muslim royals not only fostered a sense of affiliation with the Muslim world but served as repositories of local oral traditions. Griots, or other institutions engaging in oral knowledge transmission, might incorporate these portraits into their practices, linking visual and oral communication. As one French report suggests, teachers at Islamic schools used images from the Cairo Punch as educational tools (ANS 19G4). In Saint-Louis du Sénégal, the library of a wealthy merchant, serving as a gathering place for the local intelligentsia, featured a family tree of the Egyptian royals, complete with portraits (ANS 10D0069; Diop 2003, 159). In this social context, these images acted as a media bridge between orality and visuality, intertwining global and local references.

3. The Jeunes Sénégalais : Bridging ‘Global Waves’ and Local Contexts

These “cross-border and cross-medial overlappings” (Cronqvist; Hilgert 2017, 131) produced concrete political outcomes. It allowed for a Senegalese urban intelligentsia to situate their local political concerns into a global discourse while simultaneously adapting global political narratives to address local issues.

In 1913, a group of Senegalese intellectuals founded one of the first anti-colonial movements on the African continent in the city of Saint-Louis, the Jeunes Sénégalais (Gueye 1964, 18 – 20; ANS 20G21). Prior to the First World War, the group advocated for substantial reforms within the French Empire, including the extension of citizenship to West African populations. The similarity between their name and those of contemporary movements in Egypt or Turkey was no coincidence but the result of discursive entanglements that enabled the movement to align itself with a “global constitutional wave.” (Sohrabi 2002, 45)

In their efforts to prevent the entanglement of a West African public sphere, the colonial authorities inadvertently contributed to the rise of the Jeunes Sénégalais. As early as 1911, when issues of Cairo Punch were confiscated, the French authorities recognized that their ability to enforce censorship was undermined by a lack of translators (ANS 19G4). Consequently, all intercepted media was sent to Saint-Louis to be translated and checked for content, as the city was home the sole institutions in French West Africa dedicated to training local Arabic translators (ANS J93). With these translators drawn from the politicized West-African urban upper classes, the colonial administration inundated the already most politically subversive point of its system with newspapers, pamphlets, and images discussing Arab reform movements. One of these translators subscribed to a banned Young Egyptian newspaper in 1910 (ANS 19G4), while another translator working there in 1912 was a co-founder of the Jeunes Sénégalais (Gueye 1964, 18 – 20).

In conclusion, the circulation and mutual stimulation of different media with shared Empire-critical themes shows that a West African public successfully connected with other publics in the global South, circumventing colonial control. Shifting from media distribution to an analysis of media impact, it becomes clear that these transregional entanglements had significant cultural and political effects within the “small spaces” (Adelman; Bell; Motadel; Drayton 2018) of Senegalese cities. On the one hand, it influenced the technique of Senegalese reverse glass painting, establishing it as a

distinct media tradition. On the other hand, cross-media densification within the Senegalese bourgeoisie, equipped with the social and cultural capital to integrate diverse media into a unified political outlook, played a key role in the emergence of one of the continent's earliest colonial-critical movements.

References

Archives

Archives Nationales du Benin (ANB)

Affiche : Sultans et Princes d'Islam, 1911, Salle de Cartes, Plans et Affiches, Bureau N°21, Meuble N°05, Tiroir N° 02.

4E15 (02) Cercle de Porto-Novo. Renseignement sur les deux parties musulmanes existant à Porto-Novo ; Indépendance des arabes envers la Turquie ; Correspondance 1916 – 1917.

Archives Nationales du Sénégal (ANS)

10D0069, Correspondance du Gouverneur du Sénégal; surveillance de étrangers et des suspects (1911-1918); demande de cartes d'identité (1918); réunion publiques (1911-1922).

19G4, Surveillance de l'Islam, Propagande Islamique par l'image et la presse, 1906-1907.

20G21, Elections législatives 1914.

21G24 versement 108, Propagandes anti-française 1919 -1926.

J93, Medersa de Saint-Louis 1906 – 1912.

JOM-Collection, Mr. Bassam Tibi, Dakar

Published Sources

Diop, Ousmane Socé. 1935. "Karim."

Gueye, Lamine. 1964. "Itinéraire Africaine."

Bibliography

Asseraf, Arthur. 2022. "Mass Media and the Colonial Informant: Messaoud Djebari and the French Empire, 1880 – 1901." *Past and Present* 254 (1): 161 – 192.

Baj-Strobel, Michele. 2013. Le Suver contemporain – création coloniale, déclinaisons postcoloniales. In *Les arts de la citoyenneté au Sénégal. Espaces contestés et civilités urbaines*, edited by Mamadou Diouf and Rosalind Fredericks. Karthala 237 – 267.

Bouttiaux-Ndiaye, Anne Marie. 1994. "Senegal behind glass: images of religious and daily life." Royal Museum of Central Africa.

Byron, D. Cannon. 2019. "Symbolism and folk imagery in early Egyptian political caricatures : the Wafd election campaign, 1920-1923." The University of Utah Press.

Brückenhaus, Daniel. 2017. "Policing transnational protest : liberal imperialism and the surveillance of anticolonialists in Europe, 1905-1945." Oxford University Press.

Cronqvist, Marie and Hilgert, Christoph. 2017. "Entangled Media Histories. The value of Transnational and Transmedial Approaches in Media Historiography." *Media History* 23 (1): 130-141.

Dejung, Christof; Motadel, David; Osterhammel, Jürgen. 2019. "The Global Bourgeoisie: The Rise of the Middle Classes in the Age of Empire." Princeton University Press.

Diop, Moussa Iba Amett. 2003. "Les Lumières d'une Cité. Ndar", Presses Universitaires de Dakar.

- Drayton, Richard and Motadel, David. 2018. "Discussion: the futures of global History." *Journal of Global History* 13: 1 – 21.
- Goebel, Michael. 2016. "The Capital of the Men without a Country": Migrants and Anticolonialism in Interwar Paris." *The American Historical Review*, 121 (5): 1444-1467.
- Harrison, Christopher. 1990. "French policy towards Islam in West Africa, 1860-1960", Cambridge University Press 1990.
- Marsh, Kate. 2019. "The only safe haven of refuge in all the world': Paris, Indian 'revolutionaries' and imperial rivalry, c. 1905–40." *French Cultural Studies* 30 (3): 196–219.
- Paoletti, Giulia. 2024. "Portrait and place: photography in Senegal, 1840-1960", Princeton University Press.
- Paoletti, Giulia. 2018. "Searching for the Origin(al) On the Photographic Portrait of the Mouride Sufi Saint Amadou Bamba". *Cahiers d'Études Africaines* 58 (230): 323 – 348.
- Samuel, Jérôme. 2019. "Mosquées sous verre à Java : vie et mort d'un thème iconographique." *Archipel. Études interdisciplinaires sur le monde insulindien* 97: 113 – 150.
- Samuel, Jérôme. 2017. "A la recherche des ateliers perdus. Peinture sous verre et production en série à Java." *Archipel. Études interdisciplinaires sur le monde insulindien* 94, 143 – 169.
- Samuel, Jérôme. 2014. "Iconographie de la présence turque dans le monde malais : ce que dit la peinture sous verre javanaise." *Archipel. Études interdisciplinaires sur le monde insulindien* 87 : 103 – 142.
- Schulz, Vera-Simone. 2014. "Portraits, Photographs, and Politics in the Carpet Medium: Iran, the Soviet Union and Beyond." *Konsthistorisk tidskrift/Journal of Art History*, 83 (3): 244 – 265.
- Sohrabi, Nader. 2002. "Global Waves, Local Actors: What the Young Turks Knew about Other Revolutions and Why It Mattered." *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 22 (1): 45-79.

Geneva's Press and Radio Microcosm and the League of Nations in the Interwar Period

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Introduction

How does the establishment of an international organization change the local media landscape of a small Swiss city, turning it into an international capital in a matter of months? In 1920, following skillful negotiations by Swiss diplomats at the 1919 Paris Peace Conference (Fleury 1981) in the wake of the First World War, the city of Geneva became the headquarters of the newly created League of Nations (LoN) (Bourneuf 2022). The first truly global parliament, which, despite its youthful mistakes, was to become the foundation of the multilateral system that still exists a century later through the United Nations agencies, the League was an institution that generated a great deal of media activity. On the one hand, because the press took a keen interest in the debates of its Assembly and Council, and in the worldly activity of its diplomats and heads of state, but also because the organization itself sought to spread its message throughout the world (Biltoft 2021) and set itself a mission of information (Seidenfaden 2024). More than internationalist ideals, what is at stake is the legitimacy of such an enterprise and its bureaucratic machinery (Seidenfaden 2020).

The local Geneva press was well placed to act as a sounding board for this new situation: Switzerland's neutrality during the Great War propelled several of its titles onto the international stage. The *Journal de Genève*, a liberal-conservative newspaper distinguished for decades by its high-quality international column, and the *Tribune de Genève* news daily, saw their circulations increase significantly during the conflict (Clavien 2017), and thus join the microcosm of foreign correspondents covering the activities of the League of Nations for the major Western media. This small cosmopolitan world formed a society where the porosity between journalists and the institutional communicators of the League's Information Section was significant. This gave rise to original media experiments, such as the creation of *Radio-Nations* in 1929, or a few minutes of daily news about the League on *Radio-Genève*. But it also resulted in dissident initiatives, such as the *Journal des Nations*, created in 1931 by anti-fascist journalists eager to defend the institution's ideals in the face of rising dictatorships (Cerutti 2006).

The "world center for information on international political affairs"

A question of infrastructure

The installation of an organization like the League of Nations required major infrastructural adaptations for the small city of Geneva. The development of its airport, of course, but also telephone connections with the major world capitals. At the end of the First World War, Geneva had only one direct telephone line, to Paris. Lines were gradually set up and, by 1925, the States agreed that telegrams to and from the League should have priority. In 1939, direct telephone lines to all European countries and dozens of non-European ones, attest to Geneva's infrastructural development during the interwar (Bourneuf 2022, 82–83). But the lack of means of communication in the early 1920s calls for more substantial investment, and in 1926 the creation of a radio telegraph station specifically dedicated to the League is proposed. It's not a new idea: as far back as 1919, when the founders met in Paris to discuss the location of the headquarters, the communications infrastructure was already an important issue. They probed the Swiss envoy about the possibility of setting up a radio station in Geneva, which posed a problem of sovereignty in neutral Helvetia. The U.S. government, still not out of the League of Nations project, was ready to move forward very quickly:

“In President Wilson's idea, it would be extremely important, for the development of the LoN and for the peaceful future of mankind, that Geneva should become, partly through this radiotelegraph station, the world center of information in international political matters”.¹

While this demonstrates that communication is an intrinsic need of modern diplomacy, this idea only truly took shape in 1930: Switzerland constructed the station, and the League of Nations financed the transmitters. Commissioned in 1932, the station served both radiophony and radiotelegraphy (fig. 1). It was therefore not merely a medium intended for the general public, but primarily a means of communication overseen by two sections of the institution: the Information Section and the Communications and Transit Section. In this perspective of an infrastructure at the service of the international organization, the main activity was therefore to receive and send telegrams to facilitate the work of diplomats and the secretariat. But it was quickly put to use for institutional communication. This technology also made it possible to collect live statistics from offices far from the headquarters: radiotelegraphy was used from the end of the 1920s to coordinate health efforts in Asia by collecting weekly epidemiological information at the Singapore office (*The League of Nations: A Pictorial Survey* 1929, 20). Even though the International Telegraph Union was still headquartered in the federal capital of Bern – it relocated to Geneva after the Second World War (Balbi and Fickers 2020) – Geneva truly became a prominent point on the global telecommunications map.

Figure 1. Undated photographs of the Radio-Nations station in Prangins. League of Nations Archives, UN Geneva, P132-01-007 / P285-01-142 / P285-01-066.

Establishing open diplomacy?

The establishment of such an institution in Geneva not only necessitated the development of infrastructure but also demanded a clear definition of how this new form of political organization interacts with the public and, crucially, with the messengers of information: the journalists. Although the secretariat worked continuously throughout the year, the visible face of the League was the General Assembly, an annual event that saw hundreds of national delegates and journalists crowding onto the shores of Lake Geneva. The meetings of the Council, the executive body bringing together the main powers, were also an important decision-making arena.

This quickly raised the question of public opinion and the openness of official sessions to the press. Two years after the first Assembly, the first point of the memorandum from the president of the

¹ Report by William Rappard to the Head of the Political Department, Felix Calonder, April 29, 1919, Diplomatic Documents of Switzerland 44114, p. 3. Cited by Fleury 1983, 197. Translated from French.

association of journalists accredited to the League of Nations reminded the organization that "it must be regarded as axiomatic that the League of Nations depends, not merely for its success but for its existence, on public opinion."² If, in 1922, it was still necessary to argue against private sessions, it is because the institution's initial good intentions clashed with the gradual return to a deeply rooted tradition of secret diplomacy, despite the negative experience of the Paris Peace Conference, criticized for drafting the Treaty of Versailles behind closed doors. Does the existence of an international organization truly depend on public opinion and journalists? In theory, it was established because the signatory parties believed it was justified. Yet, two years after its creation, it became apparent that the organization already needed to justify itself. Despite the grace period the League of Nations enjoyed in its early years, it found itself confronting the public opinions of the nations it represents. It was therefore crucial for the League to create a favorable environment for effective communication with its audiences. However, while the Assembly was regarded as a public meeting, the Council strongly opposed opening its sessions to external observers, as this naturally created pressure on negotiators. Instead, the League established a system of press releases, carefully reviewed and approved by the Council members, which were distributed to the media. And if, under pressure from journalists, some sessions became public, they were only accessible to a select group of privileged reporters. This forced the profession to adopt a form of collaboration, often among correspondents of the same country (Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 78). This selection clearly demonstrated that journalists were viewed as allies in the institution's communication strategy, rather than as independent actors free to cover all its activities. However, it was not for lack of communication: during the 1920s, the League of Nations published between 300 and 600 press releases per year! (*The League of Nations: A Pictorial Survey* 1929, 28).

Throughout its existence, the League of Nations continually debated the role of the press. It even convened conferences specifically dedicated to this issue (the first one in 1927). The topic repeatedly resurfaced –sometimes because journalists demanded broader access to deliberations, and at other times because the institution sought to combat "false and biased information" as part of its efforts toward "moral disarmament." This debate extended a few years later to radio broadcasting and culminated in 1936 with the signing of the *International Convention Concerning the Use of Broadcasting in the Cause of Peace* by 28 states (Tworek 2010, E. Seidenfaden 2019).

The transmedia microcosm

The ecosystem bringing together diplomats, international civil servants, and the media in Geneva during the interwar period constituted a highly distinctive microcosm (fig. 2). And it's not just about infrastructure, but about people and sociability. While the spatial dimensions of Geneva's internationalism have already been studied (Herren 2017), its specifically transmedia nature is what interests us here: the corridors of the Assembly where journalists waited for officials to exit, discussions at the press café, the telephone office where correspondents dictated their articles to their editorial teams, the bicycle couriers racing between the headquarters and journalists' residences, the members of the Information Section recording the speech of a statesman to broadcast it on the airwaves, the informal meetings with a national delegation in a hotel lounge or the formal press dinner that brought together the elite of the profession.

The evolution of a profession

First, it is interesting to note that all journalists accredited to the League of Nations were mentioned in the Official Journal when they attended an Assembly. They were listed there by nationality and with their address, which allows for a very interesting prosopography (Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 133). There were always around 200 to 350 journalists per Assembly between 1920 and 1938 (*The League of Nations: A Pictorial Survey* 1929, 28). A figure which, if we consider that they mostly wrote for several media, gives an idea of the extent of the media coverage of these events. The profiles are diverse, from official correspondents to independent journalists, including press agency employees, some of whom had permanent positions in Geneva, independently of the League of Nations

² Memorandum by Wilson Harris, January 8, 1922. League of Nations Archives, UN Geneva, Council Documents C.19.M.4.1922. Cited by Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 59.

Assemblies. Women were few in number, 5-10% in general, sometimes up to 25% in the British media (Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 138). With the development of radio, some naturally had a transmedia profile, either because they wrote indifferently for the press and the airwaves, or because they were, like Arthur Richard Burrows, recognized "voices" (first newscaster of the *BBC* in 1922 and from time to time registered as a journalist of the *Times* at the League of Nations, see Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 147). Moreover, other media professions also formed this community, in particular photographers – mostly local but also sometimes international – or press cartoonists (Reef 2019).

Figure 2. Schematic representation of Geneva's transmedia microcosm in the interwar period.

It is, however, unclear whether the local and international press collaborated beyond occasionally hiring a local journalist temporarily when a foreign publication lacked on-site staff. What is evident is that the cosmopolitan nature of this microcosm gave rise to local yet international initiatives, such as the *Journal des Nations* (1931), whose editor-in-chief, Carlo Emanuele A. Prato, was an Italian refugee and former correspondent for *The New York Times* (Cerutti 2002). This daily publication, which offered highly detailed coverage of international news and the League of Nations' diplomatic activities, represents a truly unique media phenomenon.

This environment also proved fertile for the institutionalization of the journalism profession. It is during this period that the *Fédération Internationale des Journalistes* was established in Paris in 1926, owing much of its legitimacy to the League, as it immediately became its principal interlocutor during the 1927 Press Experts Conference (Beyersdorf 2016). Also noteworthy are the Association of Journalists Accredited to the League and the work of the International Labour Organization, which began investigating the status and working conditions of journalists as early as 1925. All these initiatives highlight the "co-evolution" of journalism and the public relations strategies of international organizations (Koenen, Averbek-Lietz, and Gellrich 2024, 9).

The symbiosis of this ecosystem of journalism and public relations is also evident in the Information Section's intense activity in keeping abreast of what's being published about the institution. Before it outsourced this work, it employed professional readers who read 200 press titles every day and distributed the thousands of clippings to the relevant sections (Gellrich 2023). It then employed the Geneva-based company *Argus Suisse*, which specialized in this work, delivering tens, if not hundreds, of thousands of press clippings a year (Averbek-Lietz 2024, 109), a mandate that represented a very substantial budget for the section.

Mobility and blurred lines

It goes without saying that the majority of the staff in the League of Nations' Information Section previously worked as journalists, highlighting a structural mobility between these two worlds. For example, this was the case for the section's director, Pierre Comert, a former French journalist and German literature professor in Göttingen, who, from 1916, served as press attaché at the French Embassy in London (the backbone of the Secretariat was assembled while the League was being prepared in London in 1919–1920). This was also true for dozens of others, such as Max Beer, a journalist for the *Kölnische Zeitung* accredited to the League between 1920 and 1927. On the recommendation of Gustav Stresemann himself, Beer joined the Information Section when Germany was moving closer to the organization. There, he organized the 1927 Press Experts Conference. He left the League in 1930 to return to journalism, first in Germany and later in exile in France and Switzerland. After World War II, he was hired by the Public Information Department of the United Nations (Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 82).

It was not uncommon for precarious working conditions, the habit of acting as correspondents for multiple media outlets, and the lack of clear rules to create situations that blurred the line between communication and journalism. For instance, this was the case with Vernon Bartlett, head of the London Branch Office of the Information Section, who later moved on to the *BBC* but reportedly wrote articles for *The Times* during his tenure. The most emblematic case is that of Arthur Sweetser, whose actions prompted the Secretariat to clarify that its members were not permitted to publish articles in a personal capacity (Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 85). Often, this was because the novelty of the institution meant that the distinction between journalism and institutional communication was still being defined, partly due to the back-and-forth nature of these actors' careers and their highly personal assessment of the situation (in several instances, their writing for the press and radio was done in good faith to compensate for the lack of media coverage of certain League of Nations activities!). Moreover, this politico-media microcosm was, unsurprisingly, not immune to intertwined personal situations, such as that of Antonina Vallentin. A journalist of Polish origin initially working for Stresemann's German Foreign Ministry, she covered the League of Nations between 1926 and 1928 before marrying Julien Luchaire, the director of the newly created International Institute of Intellectual Cooperation of the League of Nations. Luchaire's son Jean was also a journalist at this time and occasionally covered the League while his father was still working there, in a way taking over his father's new wife (Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 159). But while his father, Julien, fully embraced the internationalist vision by seeking to strengthen France's position in cultural diplomacy (Grandjean 2022), Jean Luchaire pursued a career increasingly at odds with the values of the League of Nations. He later became involved in nationalist press and, from 1940, openly collaborationist, ultimately serving as the chief censor of the French press and a propagandist for Vichy, while his father joined the Resistance. This personal episode highlights that the transmedia microcosm of "International Geneva" was nevertheless composed of actors from across the political spectrum, including Italian fascists and German journalists controlled by the regime from 1933 onward.

Taking advantage of new media: radio and film & the League of Nations

While this paper cannot focus on all the communication activities of the Information Section, which is an object of renewed interest in recent years (see Löhr and Herren 2014, Seidenfaden 2022 or Van Dijk 2022), it is interesting to see how it attempted to take advantage of the telecommunication infrastructure described above and how it intersected with the traditional media of the time, the press.

When the local and international press were invited to visit *Radio-Nations'* brand-new facilities in early March 1932, the *Journal de Genève* concluded that it was “an admirable and useful work”³, because it also served the press. In fact, *Radio-Nations* was in no way in competition with the print media, since it limited itself to a weekly broadcast, late on Sunday evenings, in French, English and Spanish. From 1937 onwards, it also transmitted reports on the work of the Assembly. It was also used to broadcast concerts by the Orchestre de la Suisse Romande around the world. And, in the reverse scenario, was

³ "Les stations émettrice et réceptrice de Radio-Nations", *Journal de Genève*, 2 March 1932, p. 4. Available on the Impresso app: <https://impresso-project.ch/app/issue/JDG-1932-03-02-a/page/JDG-1932-03-02-a-p0004>

paid for by major American radio stations to broadcast some of their content to Europe. But basically, technological change has had little effect on the type of communication practiced by the League, which has always relied, as in its more traditional communiqués, on a precise and elitist expert discourse that “overestimated the public's powers of rationality” in the era of the emergence of mass-based politics based on new media (Akami 2019, 167).

Although the audio recordings have not been preserved, the annual reports list the topics of these approximately 45-minute broadcasts: speeches by Secretary-General Eric Drummond, discussions with the President of the Assembly, interviews of the Secretariat conducted by local or international journalists, responses to listener letters, lectures by experts on technical achievements of the League, reports from the Secretariat on specific actions, and more.⁴ Despite its remarkable regularity – broadcasting weekly in its early years and increasing its pace to 748 official programs between 1936 and 1938 (Bourneuf 2022) – the overall volume of broadcasts was not very significant compared to radio stations that aired programs throughout the day. What truly sets *Radio-Nations* apart is its global ambition. At the time, it was the only station broadcasting simultaneously worldwide (the Vatican station had a similar ambition but lacked sufficiently powerful transmitters). In its first year, while only 49 programs were broadcast, the audience was estimated at 100,000 listeners, from whom they received 8,797 letters in Geneva. Additionally, 150 press articles reproduced the content of their broadcasts, and 8 other radio stations relayed their programs.⁵

Figure 3. Left: *Le Radio* 11 March 1932, A full-page spread detailing the first live broadcast of an entire League of Nations assembly, the extraordinary session devoted to the Sino-Japanese War (p.348). Right: *Le Radio* 23 September 1932, A half-page of press cartoons allowing readers/listeners to put a face to the voices they hear on the radio (top, p.1231) and an extract from the week's program, where we see the space reserved for Suès' chronicle (bottom, p.1224).

On a much more local scale, Radio-Genève also showed significant interest in the work of the League of Nations. Here too, very few archives of their broadcasts on the League remain – at most, a few dozen recordings, primarily major speeches by heads of state preserved for their potential future

⁴ "Premier rapport annuel sur le service de la section d'information", 1933, League of Nations Archives, UN Geneva, R4325-9G-14701-742, p. 1-3.

⁵ Idem, p. 4 and 12.

reuse, along with more comprehensive coverage of the League's final session in 1946. However, the weekly magazine of the Société romande de radiodiffusion, *Le Radio*, helps partially fill this gap (fig. 3): during League sessions, the Geneva station dedicated 10 to 15 minutes daily to the "Travaux de la Société des Nations" at 8:00 p.m., hosted by Marcel-William Suès, a pioneer of news broadcasting in French-speaking Switzerland (Musy 1984).

Regarding cinema – the other future mass-media of the interwar period – the League of Nations was a latecomer (Dijk 2023). Prompted by Mussolini's Italy, which sought to counterbalance French initiatives related to intellectual cooperation (Grandjean 2018, 371–78) and aimed to assert its influence in the cultural diplomacy of the late 1920s, the League founded the *International Educational Cinematographic Institute* in Rome in 1928 (Faillibert 2020, Wilke 2024). However, this institute functioned more as a center for reflection on the use of film rather than a site of production. The League of Nations nevertheless ventured into "film-splaining" its activities (Jensen, Schulz, and Seidenfaden 2019) in 1935 through an "infomercial" titled *The League of Nations at Work* (fig. 4). While this document is highly valuable for understanding the organization's communication strategy, its distribution remains more challenging to trace.

Figure 4. Screenshot from a scene in the film "League of Nations at Work" showing the telegraph office at the League of Nations headquarters, accompanied by a description of the scenes.⁶

Making the world smaller

The infrastructure established in Geneva helped reduce the reaction time of the political world. The Sino-Japanese conflict, often regarded as the final nail in the coffin of the League of Nations' ability to resolve international disputes, paradoxically serves as the perfect example of its effectiveness in circulating information. In March 1932, during the very early days of *Radio-Nations*, the live broadcast of an entire extraordinary assembly – rather than simply the delayed dissemination of a few key speeches – was widely praised (fig. 3). However, the most striking demonstration came a year later, in February 1933, when the League finally released its report accusing Japan of invading Manchuria. This marked a major achievement for the organization: Thanks to its transmission network, the 15,000-word report was sent to all corners of the globe and reproduced in full in media worldwide (fig. 5), including Chinese newspapers, just 24 hours later (Bourneuf 2022, 85). In addition to this telegram – which, in total, required several kilometers of tape – *Radio-Nations* also used its regular broadcast to explain the report.

⁶ Part 1 can be seen here: <https://media.un.org/avlibrary/en/asset/d211/d2113114> (UN Audiovisual Library).

COUZENS BANK BILL SWIFTLY MADE LAW; NEW RELIEF LOANS

Carry to Settle Republican Leaders' Row; Macy and Knevez at Odds on Tax Post

STATE LIQUOR BOARD NORRIS LEADS MOVE DISAGREES ON PLANS FOR BIPARTY UNION FOR VOTE ON REPEAL OF 'PROGRESSIVES'

CHAOYANG FALLS AS JAPANESE ADVANCE; FOUR ARMIES AND AIR FLEET IN DRIVE; WASHINGTON APPROVES LEAGUE'S ACTION

Broadcast of Manchurian Report Proved Value of "Radio-Nations" at Geneva

THE earliest plans for the League of Nations in the burst of enthusiasm for the League immediately after the World War included a radio station with power sufficient to stridle the earth.

The efficiency of the station and the value for quick and complete dissemination of information were strikingly illustrated recently when the League's 15,000-word report on the China-Japanese dispute in Manchuria was broadcast to the entire world. The New York Times wireless station copied the dots and dashes of the report in ten hours direct from Geneva and it was printed in full in *The Times* on the following morning.

Though the subject was under discussion for many years, it was only in September, 1929, that the Assembly of the League of Nations resolved to erect a wireless station which would issue independent and direct communications between the League and the greatest possible number of its member States.

"We can hardly estimate the change that may be made in international relations," remarked Sir Eric Drummond, Secretary General of the League, "if people in various parts of the world become accustomed not only to the thought but even to the actual voices of the League of Nations in the form of a broadcast."

The aerial system consists of three groups of beam aeriels. The first group (Marconi system) comprises two parts, one of which is directed toward South America, the other toward the Far East, each side being composed of two complete sets of aeriels one for day and one for night working.

The second aerial group (Telefunken system) is directed toward Central America and can be shifted in the direction of Australia and the West Indies. This group is also divided into a night and day array.

The third aerial is directed toward South America and can be shifted toward British India. This aerial has been designed for one wavelength only.

Apart from these three groups of beam aeriels the station possesses three semi-directional aeriels. The two short-wave transmitters have an aerial power of twenty kilowatts, sufficient for reaching the most distant parts of the globe.

The medium wave transmitter of fifty-kilowatt aerial power can work on waves between 2,000 and 4,000 meters, and it is possible to establish by means of it communications with any point in Europe.

New York hears the 20.64-meter wavelength twice there is a band of daylight between Switzerland and the United States. Soon after 2 P. M. in New York, a stronger sig-

League's Note and Reply

LEAGUE OF NATIONS NOTE.

The last paragraph of the report which the Assembly of the League of Nations has adopted today is an instruction "to commission a study of the League's radio system."

The Commission of the League of Nations, which was appointed by the Assembly in 1929, has the honor to inform you that it has completed its report and that it is now in a position to submit it to the Assembly on the 26th of February, 1933.

The Commission's report is a study of the League's radio system, which was established in 1929, and it is a study of the League's radio system, which was established in 1929, and it is a study of the League's radio system, which was established in 1929.

90,000 MEN IN OFFENSIVE

Bombs Do Much Damage to the Chinese Defense at Lingyuan Pass.

TWO MORE ARMIES START

Japan Hurts Big New Forces into China's Defense as Preparations for Fight.

PHIRING AT SHANHAICHAO

Advance Proceeding Through Bizzard from Gobi in 12 Baby Zoo Temperature.

BY HALEY'S ARMY

News from the New York Times, SHANHAICHAO, Feb. 26.—Chongqing, the second largest city of China, has been shelled by Japanese planes today. The report of this city, about 1,000 miles from the Manchurian border, where a huge Chinese force has been ordered to meet the Japanese advance, is the first of a series of reports from the Chinese front which indicate that the Japanese are making rapid progress. The Japanese have been shelling the city for several days, and the Chinese are reported to be suffering from a shortage of food and ammunition. The Japanese are reported to be advancing on the city from the north and east, and the Chinese are reported to be fighting a desperate battle to hold the city.

Figure 5. "Broadcast of Manchurian Report Proved Value of "Radio-Nations" at Geneva", New York Times, 26 February 1933, p.X10. The technical feat is celebrated with a photograph of the Prangins station.

Next steps

While the inventory of communication tools is now well-established in recent scholarship, one question remains unresolved: what is the real impact of public relations strategies on the transmedia microcosm and its outputs, and subsequently on international public opinion (assuming the notion of public opinion even holds meaningful weight in a world still heavily compartmentalized along national lines)? Conversely, what is the effect of these processes of mediatization on the political institution itself?

For instance, did media innovations lead to changes in how delegates addressed the plenary sessions of the Assembly? The near-total absence of radio archives from this period makes an exhaustive analysis of the media productions challenging. However, the goal of this research is to lay the groundwork for a study of the content of the Geneva press, in an effort to measure the precise media coverage of this international organization in this very specific local context.

References

Akami, Tomoko. 2019. 'Beyond the Formula of the Age of Reason: Experts, Social Sciences, and the Phonic Public in International Politics'. In *The League of Nations, Perspectives from the Present*, edited by Haakon A. Ikononou and Karen Gram-Skjoldager, 161–72. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press.

Averbeck-Lietz, Stefanie. 2024. 'Discovering Open Diplomacy. The League of Nations' Information Section 1920-1932 and Its External and Internal Communication'. In *Communicating the League of Nations: Contributions to a Transnational Communication History of the League of Nations in the Inter-War Period (1920-1938)*, edited by Erik Koenen, 59–122. Geneva: United Nations.

Balbi, Gabriele, and Andreas Fickers, eds. 2020. *History of the International Telecommunication Union (ITU): Transnational Techno-Diplomacy from the Telegraph to the Internet*. Berlin: De Gruyter.

Beyersdorf, Frank. 2016. 'First Professional International: FIJ (1926–40)'. In *A History of the International Movement of Journalists: Professionalism Versus Politics*, edited by Kaarle Nordenstreng, Ulf Jonas Björk, Frank Beyersdorf, Svernik Høyer, and Epp Lauk, 80–124. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK.

- Biltoft, Carolyn N. 2021. *A Violent Peace: Media, Truth, and Power at the League of Nations*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Bourneuf, Pierre-Etienne. 2022. *Genève, berceau de la Société des Nations*. Collection histoire 3. Genève: Nations Unies
- Cerutti, Mauro. 2002. 'A Prato, Carlo Emanuele'. In *Dictionnaire Historique de la Suisse*. <https://hls-dhs-dss.ch/articles/027932/2002-08-21/>.
- Cerutti, Mauro. 2006. 'Carlo Emanuele a Prato et le "Journal des Nations": un intellectuel antifasciste dans la Genève de la Société des Nations'. In *Les intellectuels antifascistes dans la Suisse de l'entre-deux-guerres*, edited by Alain Clavien and Nelly Valsangiacomo, 97–110. Lausanne: Antipodes.
- Clavien, Alain. 2017. *La presse romande*. Lausanne: Antipodes.
- Dijk, Pelle van. 2023. 'Internationalism on the Big Screen: Films on the League of Nations'. *Studies in Communication Sciences* 23 (1): 51–66.
- Fleury, Antoine. 1981. 'L'enjeu du choix de Genève comme siège de la Société des Nations'. In *L'historien et les relations internationales. Recueil d'études En hommage à Jacques Freymond*, edited by Saul Friedländer, H. Harish, and André Reszler, 251–78. Genève: Institut universitaire de hautes études internationales et du développement.
- Fleury, Antoine. 1983. 'La Suisse et Radio Nations'. In *The League of Nations in Retrospect / La Société des Nations: Rétrospective, 196–220*. De Gruyter.
- Gellrich, Arne Lorenz. 2023. 'A "Careful Study" on Public Opinion. An Exemplary Investigation of Media Monitoring through Press Clippings Collections in the League of Nations' Information and Mandates Sections'. *Studies in Communication Sciences* 23 (1): 67–84.
- Gellrich, Arne Lorenz, and Erik Koenen. 2024. 'In Search of the Geneva Journalist. A Biographical Kaleidoscope of the Journalistic Sphere around the Assemblies of the League of Nations from 1920 to 1938'. In *Communicating the League of Nations: Contributions to a Transnational Communication History of the League of Nations in the Inter-War Period (1920-1938)*, edited by Erik Koenen, 133–85. Geneva: United Nations.
- Grandjean, Martin. 2018. 'Les réseaux de la coopération intellectuelle. La Société des Nations comme actrice des échanges scientifiques et culturels dans l'entre-deux-guerres'. Lausanne: Université de Lausanne. <https://halshs.archives-ouvertes.fr/tel-01853903>.
- Grandjean, Martin. 2022. 'The Paris/Geneva Divide. A Network Analysis of the Archives of the International Committee on Intellectual Cooperation of the League of Nations'. In *Culture as Soft Power. Bridging Cultural Relations, Intellectual Cooperation, and Cultural Diplomacy*, edited by Elisabet Carbó-Catalan and Diana Roig-Sanz, 65–98. Berlin: De Gruyter.
- Herren, Madeleine. 2017. 'Geneva, 1919–1945: The Spatialities of Public Internationalism and Global Networks'. In *Mobilities of Knowledge*, edited by Heike Jöns, Peter Meusbürger, and Michael Heffernan, 211–26. Knowledge and Space. Heidelberg: Springer
- Jensen, Helle Strandgaard, Nicolai Schulz, and Emil Seidenfaden. 2019. 'Film-Splaining the League of Nations'. In *The League of Nations, Perspectives from the Present*, edited by Haakon A. Ikononou and Karen Gram-Skjoldager, 201–10. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press.
- Koenen, Erik, Stefanie Averbeck-Lietz, and Arne L. Gellrich. 2024. 'Communicating the League of Nations - an Introduction'. In *Communicating the League of Nations: Contributions to a Transnational Communication History of the League of Nations in the Inter-War Period (1920-1938)*, edited by Erik Koenen, 5–17. Geneva: United Nations.
- Löhr, Isabella, and Madeleine Herren. 2014. 'Gipfeltreffen Im Schatten Der Weltpolitik: Arthur Sweetser Und Die Mediendiplomatie Des Völkerbunds'. *Zeitschrift Für Geschichtswissenschaft* Jg. 62, H. 5:411–24.
- Musy, Frank. 1984. 'Marcel-William Suès'. *Archives RTS*, 3 October 1984, sec. Journal de midi. <https://www.rts.ch/archives/1984/audio/marcel-william-sues-25230826.html>.

- Reef, Paul. 2019. 'Imaging the League of Nations. Cartoons as a Prism for Perceptions of International Politics and Organisations?'. In *The League of Nations, Perspectives from the Present*, edited by Haakon A. Ikononou and Karen Gram-Skjoldager, 223–34. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press.
- Seidenfaden, Emil Eiby. 2019. 'From the Gallery to the Floor. The League of Nations and the Combating of "False Information"'. In *The League of Nations, Perspectives from the Present*, edited by Haakon A. Ikononou and Karen Gram-Skjoldager, 188–200. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press.
- Seidenfaden, Emil Eiby. 2020. 'Legitimizing International Bureaucracy: Press and Information Work from the League of Nations to the UN'. In *Organizing the 20th-Century World: International Organizations and the Emergence of International Public Administration, 1920-1960s*, by Karen Gram-Skjoldager, Haakon Andreas Ikononou, and Torsten Kahlert, 129–43. London: Bloomsbury Publishing
- Seidenfaden, Emil Eiby. 2022. 'The League of Nations' Collaboration with an "International Public", 1919–1939'. *Contemporary European History* 31 (3): 368–80.
- Seidenfaden, Emil Eiby. 2024. *Informing Interwar Internationalism. The Information Strategies of the League of Nations*. London: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Taillibert, Christel. 2020. 'Le cinéma d'éducation et le projet internationaliste de la SDN : la brève histoire de l'Institut international du cinéma éducatif'. *Relations internationales* n° 183 (3): 95–112.
- The League of Nations: A Pictorial Survey*. 1929. Genève: Société des Nations.
- Tworek, Heidi. 2010. 'Peace through Truth? The Press and Moral Disarmament through the League of Nations'. *Medien & Zeit* 25 (4): 16–28.
- Van Dijk, Pelle. 2022. '“We Must Work with a Missionary Spirit” : The League of Nations Information Section and Public Diplomacy'. Thesis, European University Institute.
- Wilke, Jürgen. 2024. 'Cinematography as a Medium of Communication. The Promotion of Research by the League of Nations and Rudolf Arnheim's Role in This Context'. In *Communicating the League of Nations : Contributions to a Transnational Communication History of the League of Nations in the Inter-War Period (1920-1938)*, edited by Erik Koenen, 187–210. Geneva: United Nations.

Cross Media History in the mid-20th Century: The American Foreign Correspondents, the Rise of National Socialism, and the Convergence of Print and Radio Reporting

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Introduction

The mid-20th century marked a pivotal period in the evolution of media history. During this time, global political developments and technological advancements combined to create a unique cross-media landscape. In particular, American foreign correspondents played a crucial role in shaping public understanding of international events, such as the rise of National Socialism. The convergence of print journalism and radio broadcasting further amplified the reach and influence of foreign correspondents, facilitating real-time reporting that transcended geographical borders. This paper will explore the interconnectedness of American foreign correspondents, the rise of fascist movements, and the historical significance of cross-media reporting during the mid-20th century.

The discussion will focus on three key arguments. First, the rise of (foreign) political journalism in the United States and the emergence of fascism in Europe were deeply interlinked, benefiting and influencing one another. Second, American radio correspondents established themselves as leading voices in international political reporting, particularly during critical moments such as the Munich Agreement of 1938. Third, cross-mediality became a defining characteristic of journalism during this period, as foreign correspondents navigated the boundaries of print and radio to report on global crises. During the war, new and improved technologies like sending news photos via radio-transmitter around the world in just some minutes (radio photos) complemented blurred the boundaries between print and radio journalism further.

The Interconnection of American Journalism and National Socialism

The rise of National Socialism in Germany and its global ramifications brought European affairs to the forefront of American media coverage. The early 1930s were marked by rapid political changes in Germany, particularly Adolf Hitler's rise to power in 1933. Contrary to popular misconceptions, many American foreign correspondents did not flee Germany after Hitler's ascension. Instead, major American media companies strengthened their presence in Berlin after 1933, recognizing the city's importance as a global news center.

For American journalists, Nazi Germany presented a paradoxical environment. On one hand, Germany became a hub of international interest, generating newsworthy events that demanded coverage. On the other hand, the suppression or rather manipulation of press freedom under the Nazi regime posed significant challenges. Journalists had to navigate censorship, propaganda, and the regime's attempts to control the narratives. Despite these obstacles, American correspondents remained committed to reporting on the realities of life under National Socialism, shedding light on the regime's totalitarian nature and aggressive foreign policies.

The relationship between American journalism and National Socialism was complex and mutually influential. While the fascist movements in Europe provided journalists with compelling material, American media played a critical role in shaping public perception of Nazi Germany on a global scale. This interconnection highlights 1) the role of the media as both an observer and a participant in historical events and 2) the role of foreign correspondents as political actors who often shaped political events in performative ways.

The Role of American Radio Correspondents in Political Reporting

The late 1930s witnessed a significant shift in international political journalism with the rise of radio as a dominant medium, also in foreign politics and international relations. American radio correspondents emerged as key players in reporting on European crises, particularly those that brought the continent to the brink of war. Unlike print journalism, which required time for distribution, radio allowed for near-instantaneous reporting, offering listeners in the United States real-time access to events unfolding thousands of miles away.

One of the most notable examples of radio's influence was its coverage of the Munich Agreement in 1938. As Hitler's expansionist policies threatened the stability of Europe, American correspondents in Berlin, Bad Godesbergs, and Munich provided live updates on the diplomatic negotiations and the political tensions surrounding the agreement. This marked a turning point in the history of journalism, as radio broadcasting became the leading medium for international political reporting. Listeners could hear the voices of both politicians and correspondents directly from the scene, fostering a sense of immediacy and emotional connection to global events.

The success of radio journalism can be attributed to the skill and adaptability of American foreign correspondents. Many radio correspondents had backgrounds in print journalism, bringing with them a strong foundation in storytelling, news analysis, and investigative research. Their ability to combine the strengths of print and radio journalism allowed them to deliver accurate, engaging, and timely reports that resonated with audiences. By leveraging the capabilities of radio technology, correspondents were able to overcome geographical barriers and connect American listeners to the realities of war-torn Europe.

Cross-Mediality and the Convergence of Print and Radio

The convergence of print and radio reporting during the mid-20th century reflects the adaptability and resourcefulness of American foreign correspondents. As radio emerged as a powerful medium, journalists began to work cross-media, bridging the gap between traditional print journalism and the new possibilities offered by radio broadcasting.

Cross-mediality became a practical necessity during this period. Advances in transportation technology, such as airplanes, allowed journalists to travel more quickly between locations, enabling faster and more dynamic reporting. At the same time, improvements in radio technology, including wireless transmission, made real-time reporting possible. This convergence of transportation and communication technologies allowed foreign correspondents to transcend geographical and temporal boundaries, providing audiences with up-to-the-minute coverage of global events. As well, new formats like the *European News Roundups* helped the leading American radio companies NBC and CBS to improve their real-time reporting during political crises and make it more independent from dictatorial and authoritarian regimes.

Many prominent radio correspondents of the time were originally print journalists who transitioned to the new medium, like William Shirer (CBS) or Max Jordan (NBC). This overlap between print and radio was particularly evident during the 1930s and early 1940s. Print journalists, accustomed to crafting detailed and analytical reports, brought a level of professionalism and depth to radio broadcasting. They became versatile media professionals, capable of adapting their storytelling techniques to suit the strengths of each medium.

The economic incentives of cross-media reporting also played a role in this convergence. Radio offered lucrative opportunities for journalists, many of whom were "stars" of the print sector. As

radio audiences grew, media companies recognized the value of employing experienced print journalists to deliver high-quality broadcasts. This professional overlap blurred the lines between newspaper and radio reporting, creating a hybrid form of journalism that defined the media landscape of the mid-20th century.

However, it is important to note that this period of cross-mediality was not without its challenges. The demands of war reporting during the Second World War brought about a gradual separation between print and radio journalism again. The specific requirements of wartime communication necessitated a more specialized approach, leading to the professional differentiation of the two media. Nonetheless, the legacy of cross-media reporting remained a defining feature of journalism in the mid-20th century, leading directly towards the emergence of Television and political news on TV after 1945.

The Impact and Legacy of Cross-Media Reporting

The convergence of print and radio reporting during the mid-20th century had a profound impact on the development of modern journalism. By combining the strengths of both media, American foreign correspondents were able to deliver comprehensive, timely, and engaging coverage of global events. This cross-media approach not only expanded the reach of journalism but also enhanced its ability to influence public opinion and political discourse.

The work of American correspondents in Nazi Germany serves as a testament to the importance of journalism in times of crisis. Despite the challenges posed by censorship and propaganda, journalists remained committed to their role as witnesses to history. Their reporting provided valuable insights into the rise of fascism, the realities of life under totalitarian regimes, and the geopolitical tensions that led to the Second World War.

Furthermore, the integration of print and radio paved the way for the multimedia journalism of today. The principles of cross-mediality—adaptability, immediacy, and technological innovation—continue to shape the practice of journalism in the digital age. Modern journalists, much like their mid-20th-century predecessors, must navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by multiple media platforms to effectively report on global events.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the mid-20th century was a transformative period in the history of (political) journalism and foreign correspondence. The rise of National Socialism in Europe and the technological advancements in radio broadcasting created a unique environment in which American foreign correspondents played a central role. Their work exemplified the convergence of print and radio reporting, as they navigated the challenges of censorship, propaganda, and war to deliver timely and impactful news coverage.

The interconnectedness of American journalism and the rise of fascism, the prominence of radio correspondents in international reporting, and the emergence of cross-media practices all highlight the significance of this period. The legacy of cross-media reporting during the mid-20th century continues to resonate in the field of journalism, reminding us of the vital role that journalists play in documenting history and shaping public understanding of global events.

By examining the experiences of American correspondents in Nazi Germany, we gain valuable insights into the evolution of media, the power of storytelling, and the enduring importance of journalistic integrity in times of political and social upheaval. Their work remains a powerful example of how journalism can bridge borders, transcend media, and bear witness to the defining moments of history.

A direct consequence of the convergence of print and radio reporting during the “Munich crisis” 1938: William Shirer’s scoop of broadcasting the Armistice of Compiègne to the United States on CBS on 22 June 1940 before it was officially announced in Germany and France. Source: Life, February 3, 1941, p. 67.

Selected Bibliography

Norman Domeier, Weltöffentlichkeit und Diktatur. Die amerikanischen Auslandskorrespondenten im »Dritten Reich«, Göttingen: Wallstein, 2021. Available in English from January 2025 as: Norman Domeier, American Journalists in Hitler’s Germany, New York 2025. [Camden House ; in print]

Available from January 2025 : Norman Domeier/Benno Nietzel (eds.), Nationalsozialismus und internationale Öffentlichkeit im 20. Jahrhundert, Frankfurt/New York 2024 [Campus; in print]

Norman Domeier, World Domination and Genocide: The ‘Lochner Version’ of Hitler’s Speech from 22 August 1939, a Key Document of National Socialist Ideology, in: The Journal of Holocaust Research, 38:1 (2024), pp. 35-54.

Norman Domeier, Ein „totaler Krieg“? Die Verflechtungen zwischen NS-Regime und internationalen Medien im Zweiten Weltkrieg und die Kontinuitäten nach 1945, in: Themenportal Europäische Geschichte, 2022, <www.europa.clio-online.de/essay/id/fdae-112440>.

Norman Domeier, NS-Pressefotos und ihre transatlantische und globale Verbreitung 1942-45. Ein Plädoyer für die Digitalisierung der NS-Presse, in: Markus Stumpf/Hans Petschar/Oliver Rathkolb (Hg.), Nationalsozialismus digital. Die Verantwortung von Bibliotheken, Archiven und Museen sowie Forschungseinrichtungen und Medien im Umgang mit der NS-Zeit im Netz, Göttingen 2021, pp. 343-351.

Norman Domeier, A Scream, then Silence. Kristallnacht and the American Journalists in Nazi Germany, in: New Perspectives on Kristallnacht. After 80 Years, the Nazi Pogrom in Global Comparison, ed. by Wolf Gruner and Steven J. Ross, Casden Annual Review 17 (2019), pp. 91-113.

Norman Domeier, Schreibmaschinentäter im »Dritten Reich« und danach, in: Dirk Rose/Dirk van Laak (Hg.), Schreibtischtäter: Begriff-Geschichte-Typologie, Göttingen 2018, pp. 179-190.

Norman Domeier, Geheime Fotos. Die Kooperation von Associated Press und NS-Regime 1942-1945, in: Zeithistorische Forschungen/Studies in Contemporary History 2/2017, pp. 199-230. <http://www.zeithistorische-forschungen.de/2-2017/id=5484> (English version available under “Translation”)

La diffusion du rock en France : approche transmédiatique (années 1960 - années 1970)

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L'histoire est bien connue. Au milieu des années 1950, de l'autre côté de l'Atlantique, naît une nouvelle musique ; le rythme est chaloupé, on commence par taper du pied et c'est bientôt le corps tout entier qui se trouve pris d'une étrange frénésie. Les paroles cinglent les oreilles des jeunes Américains qui n'ont désormais plus qu'un nom à la bouche : Elvis Presley. D'autres suivent : Little Richard, Chuck Berry, Jerry Lee Lewis... Vu d'Europe, ce spectacle paraît d'abord curieux. Mais voilà que les Anglais s'y mettent avec les Beatles et les Rolling Stones ; des cheveux longs et des guitares électriques qui conquièrent bien vite la jeunesse du Vieux Continent. La France fait cependant exception : lorsque les Beatles atterrissent à l'aéroport du Bourget en 1964, seule une dizaine de fans les attend, bien loin de la liesse déchaînée partout ailleurs. Pour leur concert à l'Olympia, ils partagent l'affiche avec Sylvie Vartan, idole des yéyés. Avec leurs versions édulcorées du rock'n'roll anglo-américain (Birgy, 2012), les yéyés séduisent les jeunes Français (Glenn, 2023) qui ne s'intéressent guère aux groupes anglais. Leur succès est savamment orchestré par une stratégie médiatique qui joue sur tous les tableaux.

En 1959, Frank Ténor et Daniel Filippachi lancent d'abord l'émission radiophonique *Salut les Copains*, sur Europe n°1. Devant l'évidente réussite du programme, le tandem décline la marque en magazine papier à la parution mensuelle dès 1962. Le système est alors parfaitement rôdé et satisfait tous les acteurs mis en jeu d'un bout à l'autre de la chaîne : à la radio, Frank Ténor et Daniel Filippachi diffusent les artistes de Vogue – la maison de disques qui héberge entre autres Johnny Hallyday – et annoncent leurs prochaines dates de concert, faisant les beaux jours de Bruno Coquatrix, directeur de l'Olympia (Tournès, 2011). La télévision suit la tendance et lance sa propre émission consacrée en grande partie aux yéyés : *Âge tendre et Tête de bois*, présentée par Albert Raisner entre 1961 et 1968. Dans les cafés enfin, les scopitones mettent en images – et en couleurs – les chansons de ces jeunes idoles (Orillard, 2014). À lire, à voir, à entendre : les yéyés sont partout.

Mais avec leur venue en France en 1964, les Beatles ont mis un pied dans la porte. Les yéyés commencent doucement à marquer le pas et les oreilles des jeunes Français se familiarisent avec les sonorités anglo-américaines. Là encore, les médias suivent et accélèrent le mouvement. En 1965, France Inter lance *Le Pop-Club*, émission animée par José Artur et dédiée entièrement à la « pop music » – le mot « rock » ne s'impose en France qu'au milieu des années 1970. L'année suivante, en 1966, le magazine *Rock & Folk* s'émancipe du mensuel *Jazz Hot*, sous la direction de Philippe Koechlin ; un tournant s'opère alors dans le traitement médiatique de la pop music, qui s'intellectualise sous les plumes de « rock critiques » (Vieau, 2021). La seconde moitié des années 1960 voit ainsi se structurer un réseau médiatique du rock en France : plusieurs voix du *Pop-Club* écrivent également dans *Rock & Folk*, à l'image de Pierre Lattès, un jeune ingénieur du son passionné de jazz. Emblématique du vivier qui est en train de se constituer, le même Pierre Lattès est logiquement choisi par l'Office de radiodiffusion-télévision française (ORTF) pour présenter la toute première émission de télévision consacrée à la pop music : *Bouton rouge*, lancée en 1967 sur la Deuxième chaîne. Le basculement est clair : au duo yéyé *Salut les Copains-Âge tendre et Tête de bois* succède le tandem pop *Rock & Folk-Bouton rouge* (Guibert, 2006 et Savev, 2004).

Comme souvent, la télévision a réagi avec un léger temps de retard et vient parachever un mouvement initié par la presse écrite et la radio. Le petit écran occupe alors une place à part dans le paysage médiatique français. Régie par un monopole d'État incarné par l'hyper-structure de l'ORTF, la télévision est considérée par les Français comme « la voix de la France » ; le général de Gaulle y

apparaît en majesté pour s'adresser directement au peuple dans des allocutions solennelles. On n'y tolère pas tous les spectacles (Poels, 2015) et les téléspectateurs ont l'indignation facile. Le rock ne peut y entrer qu'à pas feutrés et s'appuie d'abord sur la presse écrite pour tenter de se bâtir une légitimité télévisuelle.

À la rentrée 1968 – après l'échec de *Bouton rouge* emportée par la vague de Mai 68 – l'ORTF lance une nouvelle émission de pop music : *Forum musiques*. La direction choisit de confier le programme à un groupe de spécialistes, à savoir la rédaction de *Rock & Folk*. Pour le premier numéro diffusé le 23 octobre 1968, l'équipe présente les Mothers of Invention de Frank Zappa. Scandalisés, de nombreux téléspectateurs envoient des courriers incendiaires à l'ORTF, obligé de rattraper le coup lors du numéro suivant en recevant Guy Béart. *Forum musiques* végète ensuite pendant quelques mois avant de sortir de l'antenne à l'été 1969.

Ce n'est que l'année suivante qu'un pacte de non-agression est signé entre le rock et la télévision, quand est lancé sur la Deuxième chaîne *Pop 2*, premier programme de pop music à s'installer dans la durée. L'émission est parrainée par *Le Pop-Club*, puisque José Artur introduit le premier numéro aux côtés de l'animateur, Patrice Blanc-Francard – lui-même ancien chroniqueur du *Pop-Club* et contributeur occasionnel de *Rock & Folk*. L'influence du mensuel reste d'ailleurs profonde dans *Pop 2* : Patrice Blanc-Francard et son équipe entendent parler sérieusement de rock, musique en cours de légitimation. Le ton se veut un mélange d'ironie contre-culturelle et de critique musicale ; en somme, on parle dans *Pop 2* comme on écrit dans *Rock & Folk*. Les chroniques de disques du magazine servent de modèle à Patrice Blanc-Francard pour donner son avis éclairé sur les nouvelles sorties musicales qu'il évoque lors de revues de presse rituelles. L'animateur y présente également les derniers numéros des magazines spécialisés, français comme étrangers : *Rock & Folk* bien sûr, mais aussi *Best*, *Actuel*, *Rolling Stone*, le *Melody Maker* ou encore le *New Musical Express*. Face caméra, Patrice Blanc-Francard lit de longs extraits d'articles et invite parfois à ses côtés quelques journalistes rock de la place de Paris qui se posent en experts, voire en esthètes de la pop music.

Dans ce maillage médiatique, *Rock & Folk* donne le ton, tandis que le *Pop-Club* sert de laboratoire, voire d'antichambre avant l'entrée en télévision. Le rock est encore jeune, on le découvre en même temps qu'on l'écoute, et ceux – très peu celles – qui en parlent dans les différents médias ne sont guère nombreux. D'un support à un autre, rien n'est donc cloisonné (Blandin et Servat, 2024) : le rock se diffuse à travers un ensemble de circulations transmédiatiques qui fonctionne grâce à un étroit réseau d'acteurs polyvalents. À partir de la seconde moitié des années 1970, ce réseau se dilue et perd lentement de sa force, dans un contexte de profonde reconfiguration des médias français. La télévision se déleste de la béquille de la presse écrite au moment où le vidéoclip permet au rock de définitivement apprivoiser ce média, voire de le conquérir alors que l'arrivée de la gauche au pouvoir fait souffler un vent de liberté inédit sur l'audiovisuel français.

Pour l'historien qui étudie la diffusion du rock en France, l'approche transmédiatique se révèle ainsi indispensable, voire s'impose à lui. Sa boîte à outils s'en trouve enrichie de nouvelles clefs lui permettant de dépasser – dans la mesure du possible – les contraintes archivistiques auxquelles il se trouve immanquablement confronté. L'historien de la radio ou de la télévision doit en effet composer avec de nombreuses lacunes dans ses sources primaires, certaines émissions des années 1960 et 1970 n'ayant été que partiellement conservées. Un détour par la presse écrite, dans une démarche d'archéologie médiatique, lui permet d'exhumer ces programmes que le temps a parfois effacés des rayons des archives audiovisuelles. Les animateurs se confient volontiers sur les coulisses de leurs émissions dans la presse musicale spécialisée, tandis que les périodiques de radio et de télévision annoncent souvent en détail leur programmation ; c'est ensuite à l'historien de reconstituer le puzzle.

Bibliographie

Birgy, Philippe. « “Si cette histoire vous amuse, on peut la recommencer”. Le yéyé et l’importation de la contre-culture américaine ». *Volume !. La revue des musiques populaires*, n° 9 : 1 (15 septembre 2012) : 151-67. <https://doi.org/10.4000/volume.3004>.

Blandin, Claire et Servat, Véronique (dir.). « We will rock you ». *Le Temps des médias* 42 (1). <https://shs.cairn.info/revue-le-temps-des-medias-2024-1>.

Glenn, Matthias. *La fabrique du rock français (1955-1982) : sociologie historique d’une nationalisation culturelle*. Thèse de doctorat, Paris 10, 2023.

Guibert, Grme. *La production de la culture : le cas des musiques amplifies en France : gense, structurations, industries, alternatives*. Paris, France, IRMA, 2006.

Orillard, Audrey. *Scopitone : histoire culturelle du tl-box et de la chanson filme yy (1959-2010)*. Thse de doctorat, Paris 1, 2014.

Poels, Graldine. *Les trente glorieuses du tlspectateur : une histoire de la rception tlvisuelle des annes 1950 aux annes 1980*. Bry-sur-Marne, France, INA, 2015.

Savev, Marc. « Deux exemples de presse musicale jeune en France, de 1966  1969 : *Salut Les Copains* et *Rock  Folk* ». *Volume !. La revue des musiques populaires*, n° 3 : 1 (mai 2004), 5-28. <https://doi.org/10.4000/volume.2039>.

Tourns, Ludovic. *Du phonographe au MP3*, Paris, France, Autrement, 2011.

Vieau, Grgory. *Une histoire de la presse rock en France*. Marseille, France, Le mot et le reste, 2021.

Animation as a Transmedia Catalyst

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This paper examines the place and the role of animation - understood as the art of artificially creating the illusion of movement frame by frame - in the history of media. I would like to argue that animation plays an active role in the deployment of transmedia and the advent of new media, such as video games.

The question here is: how does animation act as a catalyst for transmedia, precipitating the interactive future of the media?

This question raises the underlying issue of the appropriate methodologies to capture such a protean object. To understand the development of animation and its interactions with other media (cinema, television, video games, Internet, etc.), we need to adopt a perspective transmedia and transdisciplinary perspective.

Animation is a sector apart from the film industry. It has been a long time considered as “children's animated cartoon”, and so it has been marginalized within the *Film Studies*. Animation constitutes consequently an art world (the art of creating movement frame by frame) within a larger art world (cinema). Yet this small art world provides fertile ground for thinking about a transnational history of the media: human and aesthetic circulations, unfolding within a relatively small field of actors, are easier to trace.

Long marginalized by film studies, animation is now theorized as a "cultural meta-series" integrating cinema, and seems to be an omnipresent medium embedded at the heart of all other visual media: in web interfaces and network communications (via gifs) as in video games.

In this paper, I'm going to restrict myself to examining three aspects of the interaction between animation and other media, corresponding to three distinct methodologies : a case study of Walt Disney's career, and his implementation of a transmedia economy ; a media archaeology of visual forms and the circulation of aesthetic paradigms of animated cinema, illustrated by an analysis of the video game *Donkey Kong* ; and, to conclude, a theoretical reflection on the relationship between animation and interactivity, questioning the way in which animation seems to have spread to other media.

1. Animation: an art form developed at the crossroads of media, contributing to the emergence of transmedia

The transmedia development of animation can first be considered by studying the social trajectories of its actors. The interactions between animation and other media unfold through the careers of specific individuals, who have circulated between media since the beginnings of the history of animation.

First of all, I would like to briefly mention the transmedia careers of animation pioneers such as Émile Cohl and Winsor McCay, who brought the press cartoon to the cinema screen: the institution of the cartoon as an aesthetic form and economic sector is based on a media transfusion. Émile Cohl was a cartoonist, photographer and game designer. He was long considered the father of French cartooning, and helped found the cartoon industry in the USA. Winsor McCay worked as a fairground cartoonist before becoming a press cartoonist, animating his drawings, and then working in live entertainment. The cartoon industry itself developed as a media transfusion from the press cartoon to the cinema screen.

I will then focus on a case study: Walt Disney's impact on the entertainment industry, to show how, in return, animation contributes to the emergence of transmedia industries. In the 1930s, Disney initiated the logic of derivative products through merchandising and the creation of comic strips based on cartoons. In the 1950s, the Disney empire branched out into television and the Disneyland theme park, basing its business model on transmedia synergies. Animation, which had its origins in press cartoons, comic strips and the fairground world, returned to this medium, modifying its form.

2. The aesthetic influence of animation across media borders

The history of the transmedia circulation of animation can then be written at the aesthetic level of the life of forms. It's no longer a question of studying the career of a creator navigating from one medium to another, but of looking at the works produced, to show how they reify the technical and aesthetic exchanges between different media.

The first cartoon creators came from the amusement park and the press. These social trajectories determine the aesthetics of the cartoon. The characters of the first cartoons came from comic strips (*Little Nemo*, *The Pieds Nickelés*, *The Katzenjammer Kids...*), and spoke in phylacteries, while the cartoon was presented as a cinema of attractions, inspired in its movements and its relationship to the audience by the physical sensations produced in the amusement park universe.

If a transmedia logic presides over the emergence of theatrical animation, the principles and aesthetic forms produced by animated cinema, in return, program the emergence of new interactive media. In this part, I will be focusing on how animated films, and cartoons in particular, are proving decisive for video games - visually, technically, narratively and kinesthetically, in the way they determine certain game mechanics. A study of *Donkey Kong* (Nintendo, 1980) illustrates this web of influence.

On a visual level, I will be looking at how the game's limited animations extend the limited animations of UPA (United Production of America). This studio, founded in 1945 by Disney dissidents following the strikes of 1941, made a radical break with Disney's aesthetic, proposing a new aesthetic that was decisive in the transition from theatrical cartoon to television cartoon. The development of limited animation thus seems to have been determined by the development of the cold medium of television and video.

Technically, the game's display is based on the sprite principle, which in turn incorporates principles developed by the cartoon industry, in particular the use of transparency and multiplane.

In narrative terms, *Donkey Kong* was initially conceived as an adaptation of *Popeye*, whose structure it adopts: Popeye must rescue Olive from the hands of Bluto, while Jumpman (the protagonist of *Donkey Kong*) must rescue a princess from Donkey Kong. The very setting of the diegesis, with its scaffolding, is explicitly inspired by certain episodes in the *Popeye* series.

In addition to this spatial layout, cartoons also influence game mechanics, determining the rhythms and movements used in video games. The principle of die & retry, for example, and the staged repetition of death, seem to come straight out of cartoon logic, just as the principle of power up, which reverses the balance of power between protagonist and antagonists, is inspired by Popeye's spinach.

3. Animation, between hand and machine: an interactive catalyst

Animation has accompanied the emergence of new media not only in terms of aesthetics, but also in terms of structure. Fundamentally, animation is a reappropriation by the hand of the work of image production that cinema usually delegates to the machine. It reintroduces the hand into an automated process, and this "return of the hand" produces a certain relationship to the spectacle. In this way, animated cinema tends to produce a spectator who actively participates in the spectacle. Animation has never ceased to encourage the spectacle to become a space for play, a relationship to the image that ultimately seems to contaminate all media.

Cartoons, in fact, with their many ways of addressing the audience, and their aesthetic of shock, invite the public to enter the image. Winsor McCay's shows, for example, made this penetration into the

image a reality, with the artist literally entering the screen. In the 1920s, Fleischer Studio's *Screen-Songs* created a form of cinematic karaoke, inviting the audience to sing along to the lyrics on the screen.

In the second half of the 20th century, television animation extended this participatory relationship with the image: Marsha Kinder's work has shown how television cartoons foster a playful, interactive relationship with the image among children, preparing them « for full participation in this new age of interactive multimedia— specifically, by linking interactivity with consumerism¹. »

Finally, the development of digital animation accompanies the emergence of research into 3D images: they feature common actors (Ed Catmull, for example, who was behind numerous advances in 3D imagery and was one of the founding members of the Pixar studio); they also share principles and tools (3DS Max, Photoshop...).

In this way, animation, born of a media transfusion from press cartoons to cinema, is in turn accompanying the deployment of transmedia logics, favouring an interactive and kinaesthetic relationship with the image. As such, it operates on multiplanar levels: technical, aesthetic, economic, cultural and social.

¹ KINDER Marsha, *Playing with power in Movies, Television and Video Games, From Muppet Babies to Teenage Mutant Ninja Turtles*, University of California Press, 1991, p. 6. cf. also HATCHUEL Sarah & PRUVOST-DELASPRE Marie, *Goldorak, L'aventure continue*, Tours, Presses Universitaires François Rabelais, 2018.

“CD-ROMs in Print”: Transmediality in Early Digital Culture

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In the late 1980s and early 1990s an era of “new media” opened, full of the promises of multimedia. This was a time when databases emerged as the new “symbolic form” (Manovich, 2002), museums turned “virtual,” and interactivity became a buzzword. Our paper revisits this history¹ through one “transmedia” and “boundary” object: *CD-ROMs in Print* books.

While CD-ROM culture is traditionally framed—and often self-described—in terms of *multimedia*, defined by the integration of diverse media forms within a single digital framework (Schafer, 2022), *CD-ROMs in Print* catalogs complicate this narrative. These catalogs, which provide extensive listings of published CD-ROM titles, offer a distinctive lens through which we can explore the shifting boundaries between and across different media forms.

We first position the catalogs as products of media circulation, emphasizing their role as transmedia objects. Situated at the crossroads of print and emerging digital cultures (Rassuli, Tippins, 1997), these “transmedia remnants” offer an opportunity to explore the transition from analog to digital media, their intertwinement and complementarity. Our analysis then focuses on the production of CD-ROMs, the wide range of actors involved, and the reconfiguration of media players, as captured in the catalogs. Finally, we examine the CD-ROM titles and their content descriptions, that reveal the many ways in which transmediality manifests within the medium.

1. CD-ROMs in Print as a transmedia object

CD-ROMs in Print were extensive catalogs designed to list, classify, and describe all available CD-ROM titles of the time. These catalogs or “directories” began to be published almost immediately after the emergence of CD-ROM technology and saw multiple editions from the late 1980s to the early 2000s².

The 1998 edition, which forms the basis of this study, describes itself as offering “unparalleled access to CD-ROMs produced, distributed, and sold internationally, as well as within the United States” (Suchowski, 1998, vi). This gateway to the “new digital world” took the form of a traditional printed book. In both its name and purpose, *CD-ROMs in Print* mirrored *Books in Print*, printed catalogs that had long served for tracking published books. Before the rise of digital databases, *Books in Print* was an essential tool for librarians, researchers, booksellers, and publishers, helping them to locate book titles and compile bibliographies. *CD-ROMs in Print* can be viewed as a continuation and adaptation of these established practices to a new technological medium. Ironically, while *CD-ROMs in Print* was published predominantly as traditional printed catalog³, *Books in Print* was among the first resources

¹ Within the framework of the conference and its core theme, we chose to focus on these printed books. However, this study is part of a larger project, CD-Hist, which uses a variety of historical sources—including company archives, specialized and general press, CD-ROMs, web archives, advertising, and oral histories. The project aims to revisit the history of CD-ROMs while also engaging with its extensive born-digital heritage.

² *CD-ROMs in Print* was one of several printed CD-ROM catalogs. Other examples include the CD-ROM Directory (1987–1996), the Optical Publishing Directory (1987–1991), and the CD-ROM Librarian Index. *CD-ROMs in Print* was published from 1987 to 2004, with earlier editions produced by Meckler (1987–1998) and later by Gale (1998–2004).

³ *CD-ROMs in Print* was also published in CD-ROM format, but significantly later than *Books in Print*—beginning in 1992. The print edition, however, was never discontinued.

to transition to the CD-ROM format (p. 100). The CD-ROM editions of *Books in Print*, launched in 1987, demonstrated the medium's potential to store data and function as a searchable database and was positioned as a revolutionary alternative to traditional paper catalogs (Clarck, Bingham, 1987).

CD-ROMs were praised as a “transient technology” (McSean, Law, 1990), predicted to replace print by consolidating multiple volumes into a single compact disc. Yet, paradoxically, CD-ROM culture also contributed to the proliferation of paper: the 1998 edition of *CD-ROMs in Print* alone spanned nearly 1,500 pages. This paradox captured by Dominique Boullier and Catherine Charlier in their observations about the Internet (“While the Internet may not yet drive sales online, it certainly sells a lot of paper!”), 1997, 167) may also apply to CD-ROMs.

While rooted in paper and book culture, *CD-ROMs in Print* also reflects the emerging digital database culture of its time, as well as the development of a broader digital culture. This is evident both in the catalog's discourse, which frequently references “data”, invites suggestions and comments (p. vii), starts with a User's Guide, accounts for the ephemerality of production and in its structure, which features far more indices and classifications than its predecessor, *Books in Print*.

2. Transmediality of production and reconfiguration of media ecosystem

The 1998 edition lists more than 4,000 actors—companies, organizations, and institutions—that were involved in the production of CD-ROMs. This list is strikingly diverse, ranging from universities (or conference organizers) and libraries to small firms specializing in adult content CD-ROMs, from government agencies and international scientific organizations to niche distributors, associations, and retail agencies, and from major tech giants to art galleries and media startups. For some of these entities, CD-ROM production represented only a small and temporary aspect of their broader activities. Others were established specifically for producing CD-ROMs, while yet another group transitioned into CD-ROM production from traditional publishing (Hachette, publishers in the field of law, specialized press in the economic sector, to name but a few), the audiovisual sector (Wizard, 20th Century Fox) or video disc media.

Moreover, this heterogeneous assembly of actors contributed at various stages of CD-ROM production, taking on roles such as content developers, data preparators, hardware manufacturers, mastering experts, search software creators. The guide thus provides an overview of the flow of CD-ROM production. It captures a moment when highly diverse players came together to shape the CD-ROM ecosystem. It also provides a snapshot of two parallel dynamics: the emergence of new actors shaped by CD-ROM technology (e.g., Eureka Electronic, a company born in 1991 and engaged in several activities such as distribution, content development, data preparation, mastering, consultancy, publication) and the adaptation of long-established institutions in publishing (e.g., Grolier, which then became part of the Lagardère Group, published the first encyclopedia on CD-ROM in 1985).

Other important elements are to be noted, particularly in the technical specifications of CD-ROMs: their use of Quick Time or other software, sound and memory specifications, compatibility with the PC or Macintosh systems, and the various formats parallel to the CD-ROM itself. For example, the CD-I or the FM-TOWNS system (p. 1275), focused on graphics and compatible with audio CDs, demonstrates other paths to transmediality and the challenges of standards and interoperability.

3. Transmediality of content

As both a product and a mirror of genre hybridity, *CD-ROMs in Print* showcases through the titles listed the intersections, overlaps, and hybridizations of media and genres that defined this period. The 1998 edition lists approximately 13,000 CD-ROM titles, presenting an impressive panorama of “re”- and “trans”-mediations. By navigating this landscape, we may retrace how content circulates across media forms, the functions that CD-ROMs fulfill in these processes, and the broader implications for late 1990s digital culture.

There are diverse manifestations and *uses* of transmediality within the CD-ROM medium. In some cases, CD-ROMs remediate content **to complement or extend** the original media source. For example, the CD-ROM *Conduct Unbecoming* (p.189) supplements Randy Shilts' eponymous book, providing not only full text but also interviews, over 2,000 photographs and documents, and profiles of hundreds of gay U.S. Military servicemembers. On contrary some cases demonstrate the complete **detachment of the content from its original form** (e.g., the CD-Rom *Adventure Bible*, p.12, where the players need to save Froggo, while relying on their knowledge of Bible facts and history).

Some CD-ROMs afford the **distribution and reuse** of materials, acting as intermediaries that allow text, photographs, and video to be repurposed across various media platforms (this is the case for many business CD-ROMs, which remediated and distributed reference lists, clip-art, photographs, such as *Business Metaphors and Details* (p.111)). In contrast, some CD-ROMs function as **archives** for otherwise “ephemeral” media, preserving content that might not survive in other formats (one fascinating example is the *AB20 Amiga*, which would deserve its own story, as a mirror of the vivid demoscene surrounding Amiga - the Amiga archive shutting down in April 1992 and being first preserved at the university of Berkeley⁴).

We may also mention cases of **radical genre and media hybridization**—such as the diverse forms of virtual museums on CD-ROMs, where the museum medium is remediated into various formats, from a static image collection to video games. Examples include *Ancient Egyptian-Art-The Brooklyn Museum* (1994) featuring 100 items with “multiple views and details of selected hieroglyphs and objects that are difficult to see during a museum visit” (p. 38) and *Versailles: A Game of Intrigue at the Court of Louis XIV* (1997) by the Réunion Des Musées Nationaux, a French cultural institution experimenting with what can be described as a “*serious game*”.

Finally, transmediality appears in its most reflective form when one medium is used to **mediate access to another medium**, as exemplified by CD-ROMs serving as gateways to the burgeoning world of the Internet (e.g., *Complete Internet Collection*, p.182, which includes Netscape Navigator, 15 Internet access hours, an interactive online shopping CD, and 10,000 BBS listings).

Through an exploration of this extensive catalog, we piece together an *entangled media story*, where different media, both analog and digital, not only coexist but reinforce and adapt, influence, and shape one another. While our focus is limited, the catalog opens many other avenues for further exploration, such as market segmentation or geographical distribution of production, which are of interest for the industrial and economic history of CD-ROMs. A distant reading of the catalog could also provide valuable insights, with, for instance, hundreds of occurrences of terms *multimedia* and *interactive*.

References

- Boullier, Dominique, and Catherine Charlier. “À Chacun Son Internet: Enquête sur des Usages Ordinaires.” *Réseaux* 15, no. 86 (1997): 159-181.
- Clark, Barton M., and Karen Havill Bingham. “The New CD-ROM Technology: Shaping the Future of Reference and Information Research.” *Clinic on Library Applications of Data Processing (24th : 1987)*, 1987.
- Manovich, Lev. *The Language of New Media*. Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press, 2002.
- McSean, Tony, and Derek Law. “Is CD-ROM a Transient Technology?” *Library Association Record* 92, no. 11 (1990): 837–41.
- Rassuli, K., M., and M. J. Tippins. “History and Cyberspace: A Marketing History of the CD-ROM Book Industry.” *Journal of Macromarketing* 17, no. 1 (1997): 89–106.
- Schafer, Valérie. “Le CD-Rom, Une Histoire à Graver.” *Le Temps des Médias* 39 (2022): 173–187.

⁴ https://wiki.preterhuman.net/AB20_Amiga_Archive_on_CDROM

Suchowski, Amy R. (ed). *CD-Roms in Print 1998: An International Guide to CD-ROM, CD-I, MMCD, CD32, Multimedia and Electronic Products*. Detroit, MI: Gale Research, 1998.
<https://archive.org/details/cdromsinprint1990000unse/mode/2up>

The Fax and Teletext. Imagining the Future in the 1980s and 1990s

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The fax and Teletext were essential features of what in the 1980s and 1990s was referred to as the Information Age. Though technically different, they share important similarities. Engineers and managers in telecommunications often worked on both Teletext and the fax (Coopersmith, 2015, p. 5). Both took off in the early 1980s and quickly became era-defining. Both have been described as precursors to the Internet. Perhaps most importantly, both at the same time helped introduce and popularize the idea that information was and should be available almost instantly. In short, these “formidable” technologies (Moe & Bulck, 2016, p. 9) “changed the world” (Coopersmith, 2015, p. 1).

Despite their sociocultural importance, they have largely been neglected in media-historical scholarship (Coopersmith, 2015; Moe & Bulck, 2016). Moreover, existing literature focuses on *either* of these technologies in isolation, even though they were entangled (Verhoef, 2023a, p. 17).

This paper aims to fill this gap. It will answer the question: How were the fax and Teletext discussed *in relation to each other* in Dutch public discourse (1980-2000)? The Netherlands, known as “the ‘cockpit of Europe’ regarding media innovations” (Olderaan & Jankowski, 1989), provides a relevant case study as both technologies gained rapid and widespread popularity during the decades at hand.

Discourses about new media provide insights into the “multiple anxieties about the changing nature of everyday life” (Spigel, 1992, p. 3; Verhoef, 2022, 2023b, 2024) – in this case predominantly imaginaries about the (alleged) future. Dutch newspapers and magazines – i.e. existing media – frequently wrote about the fax and Teletext, for they deemed them defining features of the so-called Media Revolution and Information Revolution. By conducting a grounded-theory inspired discourse analysis of 30,000 digitized articles, this study will explore how these technologies were discussed *together* as part of a new media mix poised to change work, leisure, and communication (Verhoef, 2023a).

This research contributes to a better understanding of the interconnectedness of technologies during the often-neglected 1980s and 1990s, offering insights into the evolution of public perceptions and the impact of media innovations.

References

- Coopersmith, J. (2015). *Faxed: The Rise and Fall of the Fax Machine*. Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Moe, H., & Bulck, H. V. D. (Eds.). (2016). *Teletext in Europe: From the Analog to the Digital Era*. Nordicom.
- Olderaan, F., & Jankowski, N. (1989). The Netherlands: The Cable Replaces the Antenna. In L. B. Becker & K. Schoenbach (Eds.), *Audience Responses To Media Diversification* (pp. 29–50). Routledge.
- Spigel, L. (1992). *Make Room for TV: Television and the Family Ideal in Postwar America*. University of Chicago Press.
- Verhoef, J. (2022). The epitome of reprehensible individualism: The Dutch response to the Walkman, 1980–1995. *Convergence*, 28(5), 1303–1319. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565211060297>

Verhoef, J. (2023a). A 1980s and 1990s media history manifesto. *TMG Journal for Media History*, 26(2), 1–34. <https://doi.org/10.18146/tmg.878>

Verhoef, J. (2023b). Let's not be cultural pessimists: The social construction of Nintendo's Game Boy and the need for console-specific game studies. *Game Studies*, 23(2).

Verhoef, J. (2024). The rise of chronic reachability and the accelerated, flexible society. The social construction of the pager, 1987-1999. *Mobile Media & Communication*, 12(3), 617–636.

Digital Throws of the Dice: A Genealogy of Rhetoric in *Fallout*

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In 1994, a developer at Interplay Entertainment began staying after hours working on their private pet project. Over the following three years, that project would become *Fallout: A Post Nuclear Role Playing Game* (Interplay Inc. 1997). *Fallout* would go on to spawn many more iterations, culminating in 2024 in a widely popular television series.

However, *Fallout's* humble origins can be traced back to an altogether different medium: tabletop role playing games (TTRPGs) (Tresca 2016). *Fallout's* developers played TTRPGs religiously and were determined to model their games after them. Out of the many contemporary TTRPG systems, *Fallout* drew most from the *Generic Universal RolePlaying System 3rd Edition (GURPS)* (Jackson, Koke, and Smith 2018; Campbell 2012; Cain 2023). For most of its development, *Fallout* was titled *Fallout: A GURPS Post-Nuclear Adventure* (Interplay Inc. 1996). However, Interplay would eventually drop the *GURPS* license during development, leading *Fallout's* developers to revise their role-playing system (Campbell 2012; Dransfield 2019; Cain 2012). This re-coded system would be the foundation of the modern screen-based role-playing game (RPG) as *Fallout* would go on to inspire and define entire genres. In tracing this history of table-top to computer screen, I offer a genealogy of play. My methodology intersects computational humanities, data-driven analysis, retrocomputing, and interface theory.

World Maps in *GURPS* and *Fallout*

"Caravan to Ein Arris"

Fallout

Figure 1: The maps of the worlds in the two mediums. On the left is a world map of a sample *GURPS* adventure "Caravan to Ein Arris". On the right is the interface of the world map of *Fallout* at an early stage of the game.

Role-playing systems consist of hundreds of pages of rules, but I want to focus on the specific game mechanics which regulate *rhetoric*: those interactions which entail persuasion, discourse, and lies. In order to theorize these mechanics and to trace specific genealogies from *GURPS* to *Fallout*, I employ the concept of "operationalization," borrowing Franco Moretti's definition of the practice as "building a bridge from concepts to measurement, and then to the world" (Moretti 2013). This theoretical framework can be employed at different contextual strata. First, I tie the concepts of implementations of rhetoric, progression through dialogue, and archetype to *Fallout* through

quantitative methods. Second, I interact with operationalization not as a methodology, but instead by conceptualizing game mechanics as diegetic operationalizations of fictive concepts.

I first engage with operationalization by applying computational methods to a dataset of *Fallout's* dialogue. In doing so, I seek to add to my theoretical conclusions by operationalizing concepts of dialogue structure, character interaction, and rhetoric to make “the leap from measurement to reconceptualization” (Moretti 2013). My dataset consists of directed graphs, with nodes representing possible actions or dialogue choices the player can make with a given non-player character (NPC) [Figure 2]. All NPCs, from the primary antagonist to a generic merchant, are included. I begin by identifying instances of reaction rolls and skill checks.

“Aradesh’s” Dialogue Tree

Figure 2: A Sample Dialogue Tree. Dialogue trees are used to represent conversations between the player and a non-playable character (NPC). In this case, a “player dialogue” node refers to a combination of player-chosen lines and the response of the NPC. Players navigate through the tree by choosing different dialogue options, which in turn open up new ones. In the case of *Fallout*, some dialogue options will only reveal themselves based on the current knowledge (or rhetorical skill) of the player-character.

Figure 3: Clustering on Dialogue Graph Embeddings

My operationalizing methods range from statistical analysis on the constructed graph attributes to unsupervised clustering of graph and node embeddings (Rozemberczki, Kiss, and Sarkar 2020; Narayanan et al. 2017) [Figure 3, Figure 4] and the application of LLMs for dialogue behavior detection (Finch, Paek, and Choi 2023). I use topic-extraction techniques to identify the contexts in which rhetoric is employed (Grootendorst 2022). While performing these methods, I reflexively

conceptualize the contact between modern computational practices and legacy software as a form of *retrocomputing* (Kirschenbaum 2015; Takhteyev and DuPont 2024).

Figure 4: Results of KMeans Clustering on Graph Embeddings. The number of KMeans clusters is set to 2; number of neighbors for UMAP projection is set to 7; graph embeddings have a dimensionality of 32.

Next, I step into the fiction of games and conceptualize “game mechanics” as *diegetic* operationalizations. There are two main mechanics of rhetoric which I can string between the mediums: the “reaction roll” and the “skill check.” Both mechanics convert concepts into quantified discretizations, and then extend the results of that measurement onto the narrative fiction of a game. A reaction roll operationalizes “first impressions:” what kind of opinion would a NPC have of a player given the player character’s past associations, physical appearance, and overall demeanor? A skill check operationalizes the application of a player character’s abilities to a specific task: e.g. lockpicking a door, finding their way after getting lost, or lying to a guard. Instead of relating concepts to theory *around* a text, diegetic operationalization acts *within* the text.

Given the lack of a dataset of rhetoric in *GURPS* games, a deconstructionist approach forms the foundation of my analysis of the two operationalizations of rhetoric. As discussed by Olivier Caïra, the rules defined in TTRPG handbooks “participant également de la construction du monde fictionnel” (Caïra 2019). Given the metaphysical importance of these rules, an approach characterized by tugging at loose threads, odd turns of phrase, and uncomfortable framings in the *GURPS* rulebook in turn deconstructs the fiction of RPGs. In order to ground my broader analysis, I choose a case-study: the pre-written adventure “Caravan to Ein-Arris,” which is still included in every purchase of the *GURPS* rulebook to this day (Lambert and Lambert 2004). I use this adventure to extract examples of applications of reaction rolls and skill checks.

When comparing forms of play, we inevitably intersect with questions of *interface*. *GURPS* and *Fallout* both try to emulate the same set of actions on two different mediums. This leads to – materially – wildly different implementations. The hitch is that these implementations share enough vocabulary and grammar for us to string threads from one medium to another. Johanna Drucker’s work on Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) offers me a methodology to *read interface* and knot these thematic threads (Drucker 2013b). Drucker argues a form of critique whose “task is to understand how [GUIs] organize our relation to complex systems (rather than how they represent them) and ... to understand how an interface works as a boundary space” (Drucker 2013b; 2013a). For my case, this means critically comparing a roleplayed conversation to a dialogue screen [Figure 5] or a GM’s character

management screen to global variables. Thus, at the boundary space between tabletop and computer screen, we are met with even more boundary spaces; when we genuinely place ourselves in relation to the text we are analyzing, fissures are bound to exist everywhere.

Figure 5: A Typical Dialogue Screen in Fallout.

As is typical with computer interfaces, I am dealing with an object whose representational and organizational strategies originate in the analogue. As identified by Marie-Laure Ryan, both computer games and table-top roleplaying games share a *mimetic* dimension which “produces a new set of fictional truths” (Ryan 2023). When Ryan writes about “fictional truths,” she is describing the diegetic enactment of roles: mage, knight, vault dweller. However, I am interested in adapting Ryan’s terminology to Drucker’s discussion of interface. In addition to assigning oneself a new name and personality, players engage in mimetic acts of interface.

The dice roll is a canonical example of a mimetic act of interface. Dice rolling has a long history which stretches beyond its usage in role-playing games as a determinate for narrative success or failure. Its origin as a physical act of interface created new fictional truths. The clack of dice against wood is a sound which has been a part of human play for centuries. The most important consequence of this physical materiality is that a player can tell when their game master is rolling dice. This leads to scenarios where the game master is told to lie about what they are rolling for (Lambert and Lambert 2004) or what the result of the roll is – “When all else fails, roll the dice where the players can’t see – and then lie about your roll” (Jackson, Koke, and Smith 2018). The justification for this is always fictional. This kind of *disloyal* relationship to the dice roll is significant because it is *unable to be encoded*. I am primarily interested in these types of unencodable practices.

In *Fallout*, the dice roll is replaced by a silent random number generator. The silence of random number generation intervenes at the Drucker’s “boundary space” of interface. A throw of the dice is replaced by buttons, automatic skill usages, and dialogue [

Figure 6, Figure 7] (Taylor 1997). More complicated and mimetic forms of interface in screen-based RPGs would eventually emerge, but these contemporary interfaces still draw heavily from the practices that *Fallout* canonized. Thus, my attempts at Drucker’s practice of reading interface can be understood as an anthropological exercise: when and how did these structures crystallize into the forms we know today?

Figure 6: The Skill Selection Screen in Fallout

Figure 7: The "Interface Bar" in Fallout

As my presentation traces a genealogy of mimetic and fictional uses of chance, I am curious which aspects of my findings digital humanities as a field can reflect upon. Notions of the unencodable, of the tactile and the silent, and of mimetic interface echo some of the “PROVOCATIONS” posed by *Digital Humanities*: “Is computational work fated to remain in the realm of quantifiable and repeatable phenomena?” (Burdick et al. 2012). These provocations orbit around the notions of *tool* and *implement*. While I traverse the boundary spaces laid out above, I want to keep a kind of ingredient book for a new kind of implementation which turns away from the deterministic and re-enacts role-players’ ludic and disloyal relationship to metrics and repeatability.

Bibliography

- Burdick, Anne, Johanna Drucker, Peter Lunenfeld, Todd Presner, and Jeffrey Schnapp. 2012. *Digital Humanities*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Cain, Timothy. 2012. “Classic Game Postmortem: Fallout.” Presentation presented at the Game Development Conference. <https://gdcvault.com/play/1015843/Classic-Game-Postmortem>.
- , dir. 2023. *History of Fallout: The GURPS Apps*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=efCn85TvrF8>.
- Caïra, Olivier. 2019. “Jeux de rôle sur table : une création de monde à trois niveaux.” *Revue de la BNF* 59 (2): 89–95. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rbnf.059.0089>.
- Campbell, R. Scott. 2012. “The Origins of Fallout.” *No Mutants Allowed*. <https://archive.is/m6lYI>.

- Dransfield, Ian. 2019. "The Complete History of Fallout." *PC Gamer*, April 4, 2019. <https://www.pcgamer.com/the-complete-history-of-fallout/>.
- Drucker, Johanna. 2013a. "Performative Materiality and Theoretical Approaches to Interface." *Digital Humanities Quarterly* 7 (1). <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2555208733/abstract/E896908AD1504F36PQ/1>.
- . 2013b. "Reading Interface." *PMLA/Publications of the Modern Language Association of America* 128 (1): 213–20. <https://doi.org/10.1632/pmla.2013.128.1.213>.
- Finch, Sarah E., Ellie S. Paek, and Jinho D. Choi. 2023. "Leveraging Large Language Models for Automated Dialogue Analysis." In *Proceedings of the 24th Annual Meeting of the Special Interest Group on Discourse and Dialogue*, edited by Svetlana Stoyanchev, Shafiq Joty, David Schlangen, Ondrej Dusek, Casey Kennington, and Malihe Alikhani, 202–15. Prague, Czechia: Association for Computational Linguistics. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.sigdial-1.20>.
- Grootendorst, Maarten. 2022. "BERTopic: Neural Topic Modeling with a Class-Based TF-IDF Procedure." arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.05794>.
- Interplay Inc. 1996. "The Vault." *The First GURPS Computer Role-Playing Game*. 1996. <https://duckandcover.cx/official/gurps/about.html>.
- . 1997. "Fallout: A Post-Nuclear Roleplaying Game." *Fallout*. Bethesda Softworks.
- Jackson, Steve, Jeff Koke, and Dan Smith. 2018. *GURPS Basic Set*. 3rd edition, Revised. Austin, Texas: Steve Jackson Games.
- Kirschenbaum, Matthew. 2015. "Ancient Evenings: Retrocomputing in the Digital Humanities." In *A New Companion to Digital Humanities*, edited by Susan Schreibman, Ray Siemens, and Unsworth, 185–98. 9781118680599. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd.
- Lambert, Creede, and Sharleen Lambert. 2004. "Caravan to Ein Arris." Steve Jackson Games Incorporated.
- Moretti, Franco. 2013. "Operationalizing." *New Left Review*, no. 84 (December), 103–19.
- Narayanan, Annamalai, Mahinthan Chandramohan, Rajasekar Venkatesan, Lihui Chen, Yang Liu, and Shantanu Jaiswal. 2017. "Graph2vec: Learning Distributed Representations of Graphs." arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1707.05005>.
- Rozemberczki, Benedek, Oliver Kiss, and Rik Sarkar. 2020. "Karate Club: An API Oriented Open-Source Python Framework for Unsupervised Learning on Graphs." arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2003.04819>.
- Ryan, Marie-Laure. 2023. "The Fictionality of Games and the Ludic Nature of Fiction: Make-Believe, Immersion, Play." In *The Routledge Handbook of Fiction and Belief*. Routledge.
- Takhteyev, Yuri, and Quinn DuPont. 2024. "Retrocomputing as Preservation and Remix." *ResearchGate*, October. <https://doi.org/10.1108/07378831311329103>.
- Taylor, Chris. 1997. "Vault Dweller's Survival Guide." Bethesda Softworks.
- Tresca, Micheal. 2016. "The RPG Origins of Fallout." *EN World D&D & Tabletop RPG News & Reviews*. October 10, 2016. <https://www.enworld.org/threads/the-rpg-origins-of-fallout-part-2-gurps.663838/>.

Résistance des écosystèmes médiatiques et obsolescence programmée : le cas Dragon Ball (Japon, France, États-Unis)

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Dans les études médiatiques, une tendance consiste à étudier l'histoire d'un média de manière isolée, souvent en le considérant comme un objet autonome et indépendant. Or, cette approche ne permet pas de saisir pleinement les dynamiques complexes qui caractérisent l'évolution des médias dans un écosystème global. Un média ne fonctionne jamais seul : il interagit avec d'autres formes médiatiques, répond à des attentes sociales et économiques, et évolue au sein de configurations économiques, culturelles et juridiques divers. Il devient alors pertinent de dépasser l'approche mono-médiatique pour explorer les relations croisées entre médias au sein d'un même univers fictionnel.

Cette étude de cas sur une œuvre transmédiatique cherche à démontrer la richesse analytique et la pertinence des dynamiques souvent sous-estimées dans les travaux sur la circulation des œuvres culturelles : d'une part, l'évolution historique des écosystèmes médiatiques propres à chaque contexte national, avec leurs spécificités structurelles et culturelles, et d'autre part, l'impact des cycles d'innovation technologique et de l'obsolescence programmée. En examinant comment ces deux facteurs interagissent pour façonner la réception, l'adaptation et la réinvention des contenus, cette analyse met en lumière les mécanismes de transformation médiatique et culturelle qui accompagnent la diffusion transnationale d'une œuvre comme *Dragon Ball*.

Dans un premier temps, il s'agira de décrire et de caractériser les divers écosystèmes choisis, en mettant en lumière leurs spécificités respectives en termes de pratiques médiatiques, de cadres réglementaires et de sensibilités culturelles. Ensuite, une attention particulière sera portée aux processus d'introduction du média initial dans chacun de ces contextes. Ce volet inclura une réflexion sur les facteurs de succès ou d'échec, qu'ils soient liés à des questions d'adaptation linguistique, d'appropriation culturelle ou de résistance locale. Enfin, l'étude s'intéressera à la manière dont l'écosystème cible, une fois exposé à l'œuvre, peut générer de nouvelles dynamiques de production, susceptibles d'enrichir ou de transformer l'écosystème source.

Rappelons que dans cette analyse le Japon constitue l'écosystème source, caractérisé par une stratégie bien établie de *media mix* qui repose sur une habitude d'adaptation multisupports organisée autour d'un cycle de production centré sur le manga. ce système favorise une exploitation extensive et cohérente des droits dérivés, chaque adaptation contribuant à enrichir la notoriété et la rentabilité de l'ensemble. Cette synergie entre supports est renforcée par une industrie culturelle très intégrée, qui permet une circulation fluide des œuvres entre médias.

Le deuxième écosystème étudié est celui de la France, en tant que représentant de l'Europe du Sud (avec l'Italie et l'Espagne). Ce pays se distingue par des caractéristiques économiques, culturelles et législatives différentes, ce qui a influencé la manière dont les œuvres transmédia japonaises y ont été introduites. Contrairement au Japon, où le marché est structuré autour d'un modèle "push" coordonné par les ayants-droits, l'introduction de ces œuvres en France s'est appuyée sur un mécanisme de "pull", qui découle principalement de la dérégulation des réseaux télévisés français dans les années 1980. Cela a favorisé l'importation massive de séries télévisées animées japonaises, souvent diffusées avant même que le manga original ne soit publié ou traduit en français. Ce renversement de l'ordre de production – avec l'animation comme premier produit médiatique – a limité l'intégration entre les différents supports. Contrairement au Japon, où une œuvre transmédia

bénéficie d'un fort niveau de coordination entre les secteurs de l'industrie culturelle, ces différents acteurs fonctionnent de manière plus indépendante.

Les États-Unis, deuxième écosystème cible, se distingue par son ampleur et sa complexité. Avec une population et un pouvoir d'achat significativement supérieurs à ceux de la France, le marché américain représente un territoire stratégique pour les œuvres transmédia japonaises. Toutefois, cet attrait est contrebalancé par plusieurs obstacles structurels. Premièrement, le système de diffusion télévisée en syndication entraîne une grande variabilité des horaires et des régions où une série animée peut être diffusée. Deuxièmement, bien que les États-Unis possèdent des industries puissantes dans les secteurs du dessin animé et du jeu vidéo, la barrière linguistique et culturelle joue un rôle dissuasif pour les ayants-droits japonais. La localisation des œuvres représente un coût important, et le marché américain est déjà saturé de productions locales. En conséquence, bien que les œuvres transmédia japonaises aient parfois réussi à s'imposer sur le marché américain, leur succès repose souvent sur des initiatives locales d'adaptation, plutôt que sur une stratégie intégrée depuis l'écosystème source.

Dans les années 1990, la série animée fait son apparition en France, où elle connaît un succès immédiat, grâce à un processus de reconfiguration qui impliquait non seulement une traduction linguistique, mais aussi une transformation des références culturelles et un réaménagement du montage. La diffusion de *Dragon Ball* à la télévision témoigne de l'importance des médiateurs locaux (les chaînes de télévision, les traducteurs, les producteurs) dans la construction de nouveaux espaces de circulation transnationaux. L'arrivée de l'anime a généré une forte demande pour d'autres versions de la série, dont le manga et les jeux vidéo qui sont diffusés ultérieurement. Ce phénomène montre un rapport inverse à celui du Japon : l'anime, en tant que média d'adaptation secondaire, devient le moteur de la demande, et non le manga qui précède toutes les autres formes médiatiques.

Parmi ces produits, les *anime comics* produits localement se sont imposés comme une forme intermédiaire entre l'animation et la bande dessinée traditionnelle. Ces ouvrages, constitués de captures d'écran issues de la série animée, étaient réorganisés en cases et accompagnés de bulles de dialogue, reproduisant ainsi l'expérience visuelle et narrative de l'anime dans un format imprimé. Cette forme de bande dessinée dérivée a précédé l'introduction officielle du manga au format *tankōbon* en France, qui n'est apparu qu'au milieu des années 1990. Les *anime comics* témoignent ainsi d'une adaptation précoce aux pratiques éditoriales et aux attentes du public français, marquant une étape clé dans la réception et la transformation de *Dragon Ball* au sein de l'écosystème médiatique hexagonal.

Aux États-Unis, *Dragon Ball* a d'abord été introduit par le biais du jeu vidéo, sans référence directe au manga ou à l'anime car la série n'était pas encore largement connue sous ses autres formes. L'obsolescence programmée des consoles de jeu vidéo a également joué un rôle important dans l'évolution de cet écosystème, favorisant une succession de nouvelles adaptations et de réinventions de la franchise pour s'adapter aux technologies en constante évolution. Dans chaque territoire, cette obsolescence a favorisé des dynamiques de diffusion différentes.

Contrairement au Japon, où les jeux vidéo étaient étroitement liés à l'univers narratif du manga et de l'anime, les États-Unis n'ont vraiment bénéficié d'adaptations spécifiques qu'au début des années 2000. Ces nouvelles productions, conçues par des studios occidentaux pour répondre aux attentes du public nord-américain, ont été développées pour des consoles de dernière génération, en réponse à l'obsolescence des plateformes précédentes qui rendaient les anciens titres inaccessibles. Ces jeux, initialement destinés au marché américain, ont par la suite été distribués en Europe avant d'être traduits en japonais et commercialisés au Japon, illustrant un processus de circulation transnationale inversée.

La longévité de la franchise *Dragon Ball* s'explique en partie par ce décalage temporel dans la diffusion internationale des mangas et des animes. Après l'achèvement du manga et la fin de la diffusion de *Dragon Ball Z* à la télévision, la franchise semblait progressivement éclipser, laissant la place à de nouveaux succès éditoriaux de Shueisha tels que *One Piece* ou *Naruto*. L'échec commercial de la série animée *Dragon Ball GT* a renforcé cette tendance, marquant une période de mise en sommeil de la licence sur le plan vidéoludique jusqu'en 2002, date de sortie des jeux développés spécifiquement pour les marchés occidentaux.

Le succès inattendu de ces jeux vidéo a incité les ayants droit japonais à relancer l'exploitation de la licence, malgré l'absence de nouveaux épisodes animés. Ce phénomène souligne l'importance des

adaptations vidéoludiques comme levier de revitalisation pour une œuvre médiatique. En retour, ces créations ont renforcé la visibilité médiatique de *Dragon Ball* et généré de nouvelles déclinaisons multisectorielles. La circulation transnationale s'accompagne d'une boucle de rétroaction sur son territoire d'origine. Ce processus souligne l'interdépendance entre les marchés et les médias dans un contexte globalisé, tout en mettant en lumière la capacité des œuvres à évoluer et à s'adapter aux contraintes qui structurent leur diffusion.

Ainsi, les adaptations transmédiatiques ne circulent pas à une vitesse uniforme, en raison des résistances imposées par les supports physiques et les contextes de production propres à chaque territoire. Il est particulièrement pertinent d'analyser ceux-ci comme des écosystèmes médiatiques, qui fonctionnent comme des environnements dynamiques capables d'intégrer, de transformer et de réinterpréter les éléments hétérogènes qui y sont introduits. Chaque configuration locale agit comme un filtre et un cadre d'adaptation, modifiant les œuvres pour les rendre compatibles avec ses propres normes et pratiques. En retour, ces transformations locales peuvent influencer d'autres écosystèmes par des phénomènes de rétroaction, favorisant l'émergence de nouvelles pratiques médiatiques, formats ou contenus. Ce processus d'adaptation et d'interconnexion souligne la complexité des circulations culturelles et la manière dont les œuvres médiatiques évoluent en réponse aux résistances et aux opportunités propres à chaque contexte territorial.

Des serveurs BBS à la TSR *StarStormer* (1991-1995): trajectoire d'un enchevêtrement transmédiateur

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Introduction

StarStormer est un jeu vidéo suisse, développé en 1991 sur MacIntosh, créé dans le contexte de la démocratisation de la micro-informatique. Il est modifié quelques années plus tard de manière à être joué en direct par un téléspectateur de l'émission de la Télévision Suisse Romande *TV à la carte* avec les touches du combiné de téléphone.

En documentant la trajectoire de *StarStormer*, cette communication cherche à comprendre dans quelle mesure le jeu vidéo s'est frayé une place à la télévision romande des années 90. Quelles ambitions animaient le développeur du jeu ? Par quels réseaux, pour quelles raisons et sous quelle forme le jeu a-t-il pu intégrer une émission de la télévision publique ? En quoi est-ce que les caractéristiques formelles de *StarStormer* répondaient aux volontés éditoriales de la TSR de cette période ? En identifiant les infrastructures, réseaux et acteurs clés de sa carrière, nous souhaitons saisir en quoi ce cas témoigne d'une histoire médiatique enchevêtrée ("entangled media history", Cronqvist & Hilgert 2017), qui invite à désenclaver l'histoire du jeu vidéo d'une histoire plus générale des médias.

Méthodologie

Pour mener cette recherche, nous avons comparé la version initiale de *StarStormer*, sauvegardée sur le site MacIntosh Repository où elle peut être émulée sur navigateur (Macintosh Repository.org), et sa version diffusée dans l'émission *TV à la carte diffusée* en 1993, accessible grâce aux Archives de la RTS au site *notrehistoire.ch*. Cette comparaison permet d'abord de saisir les héritages visuels et ludiques charriés par le titre et les circuits de distribution que l'auteur espérait intégrer, ainsi que les ajustements qui ont été faits pour l'adapter au petit écran. Cette analyse est complétée par des sources secondaires mentionnant le jeu : en général des entrefilets évoquant *TV à la carte*, mais aussi une interview d'Antoine Rosset, le programmeur du jeu. Ensuite, nous avons compulsé les émissions de *TV à la carte* disponibles sur le site des archives de la RTS, afin de de comprendre l'émission dans une perspective diachronique et de contextualiser la diffusion TV de *StarStormer*. Enfin, des entretiens d'Histoire orale nous ont permis de documenter différentes perspectives sur la production de production de *StarStormer* et sur les communautés actives autour des serveurs BBS et sur *TV à la carte*.

Production et diffusion de *StarStormer*

L'étude de la genèse de *StarStormer* témoigne de la volonté d'Antoine Rosset d'intégrer les réseaux internationaux de la distribution de jeux, hors d'une Suisse perçue comme un terrain défavorable à l'édition. Aussi, elle montre en quoi les "Bulletin Board System" (BBS) - des serveurs mis en place par les entreprises et les particuliers pour discuter ou échanger des fichiers grâce au réseau de téléphonie fixe - ont servi à la fois de lieux de socialisation, d'infrastructure de diffusion transnationale et de surface de contact avec la TSR.

En effet, après s'être initié à la programmation durant les années 80, Antoine Rosset accède à un MacIntosh avec lequel il va produire des démos¹ et se connecter à des serveurs BBS. Dans ce cadre, il rencontre Mike Venturi. Ensemble, ils produisent *StarStormer*. Ce jeu de tir à défilement horizontal de science fiction typique des jeux d'arcade se joue en déplaçant la souris ou en appuyant les touches du pavé numérique du clavier.

Fig. 1. Capture d'écran d'une version émulée de *StarStormer* (1991). Le vaisseau doit détruire les obstacles avant qu'ils n'atteignent le bord gauche de l'écran.

Il est accompagné d'éléments paratextuels qui nous renseignent sur les intentions d'Antoine Rosset. Outre des adresses postales et de BBS qui affirment la co-paternité du jeu et une volonté d'être contacté, un fichier texte accompagne l'exécutable du jeu et expose clairement les ambitions commerciales internationales de son auteur :

*This game took many hours of work, it seems normal to us authors that this hard labor should be rewarded by a salary (again and always...): This is why we are putting on the market this freeware, **demonstration of the game** which has 1/10 Tb. of the final product, in hoping to find an editor who would like to distribute it on this planet. **We have strong doubts that an informatic editor in Switzerland would do it...** (Is there a Swiss Micro-Informatic??), **we are open to all propositions** of French editors, americans, etc.. (fichier "about StarStormer.txt")*

Actif dans la communauté romande des serveurs BBS, Antoine Rosset y dépose une démo de *StarStormer* en espérant une diffusion internationale. Pourtant, c'est bien au niveau local que le jeu va faire carrière. En effet, le jeu est repéré par Patrick Allenbach², membre structurant de la communauté BBS mais aussi producteur et animateur de la TSR, dont il profite des serveurs. Ce dernier propose à Antoine Rosset de réaliser une adaptation qui soit activée à la télévision par les téléspectateurs utilisant leur téléphone dans une des émissions qu'il coproduit : *TV à la carte*.

¹ La demoscene, ou "scène démo", désigne la pratique de création de de "demos", des productions graphiques et sonores qui cherchent à exploiter la limite des micro-ordinateurs.

² Patrick Allenbach a par ailleurs été condamné à 3 ans de prison avec sursis en 2012, pour des faits d'agression sexuelle sur mineurs (*Le Matin*, 2012). Il est décédé le 5 février 2020.

StarStormer à TV à la carte : trajectoires croisées de formats “interactifs”

La récupération de *StarStormer* par un producteur issu du média local dominant souligne le rôle de circuit informel de diffusion que pouvait revêtir le réseau des serveurs BBS. De plus, l'analyse de la version activée à la télévision permet d'une part de comprendre en quoi est-ce qu'il correspondait à des impératifs éditoriaux auxquelles l'émission obéissait dans le contexte médiatique européen des années 1990, mais aussi en quelle mesure il a dû être ajusté au dispositif à la fois télévisuel et téléphonique.

En effet, malgré différents changements de format et de ton, le principe de l'émission *TV à la carte* est, dès le début des années 1980, de proposer d'une part des séquences où les téléspectateurs votent, d'abord par cartes postales, puis par téléphone, pour déterminer le programme à venir et de l'autre une animation en direct avec des jeux d'adresse et des quizz. D'abord diffusée les soirs d'été, *TV à la carte* suit dans les années 1990 un format hebdomadaire occupant la case d'été du samedi après-midi, ciblant les adolescents et jeunes adultes.

Fig. 2. Capture d'écran de la version télévisée de *StarStormer*.

Dans ce cadre, la version télédiffusée de *StarStormer* se révèle simplifiée de manière à être accessible aux candidats et compréhensible par les téléspectateurs, tout en gardant les principales mécaniques de tir et de déplacement. Ces mécaniques correspondent bien aux usages ludiques et hybrides de la télévision et du téléphone déjà éprouvés dans l'émission. Par exemple, en 1986, *TV à la carte* proposait le jeu du *Cache-Cam* où un candidat téléphonique commande vocalement l'orientation de la caméra pour retrouver quelqu'un dans le public et gagner un prix. La singularité de notre objet est cependant qu'il est bien un *jeu vidéo* adapté pour la télévision et non pas un format issu de la seule production télévisuelle.

Cet intérêt éditorial pour une télévision interactive, personnalisée, perçue comme moderne et innovante, s'inscrit dans les stratégies de la TSR des années 1980 et 1990 qui, comme le reste de l'offre publique en Suisse, doit s'ajuster aux mouvements de libéralisation et d'ouverture à la concurrence des nombreux diffuseurs privés notamment des pays limitrophes (Mäusli, Steigmeier & Vallotton, 2012:221). Cette pression a comme effet de favoriser l'émergence de ce que William Uricchio résume comme la “télévision télécommandée”, soit l'ère “du contrôle exercé par le spectateur” (Uricchio in Berton, Weber 2009:175). Aussi, nous analysons la diffusion de *StarStormer* dans le contexte de circulation transnationale des programmes (Bourdon, 2008) “interactifs” sur les

chaînes européennes, notamment des formats à succès comme la production danoise *Skarmtrolden Hugo* (1990) (Tuomi, 2009) connue en France sous le nom de *Hugo Délire* (1992-1994).

Conclusion

L'étude de *StarStormer* représente un cas d'enchevêtrement médiatique qui met à jour des spécificités locales - notamment la trajectoire du titre au sein de la TSR - et des processus de transfert (Cronqvist & Hilgert: 134) d'un média à l'autre. De la diffusion de la micro-informatique individuelle à l'usage téléphonique de la télévision, il faut un circuit informel de distribution constitué par les serveurs BBS, animé par des communautés restreintes mais actives, qui fait office de surface de contact. Il faut aussi une appétence pour les programmes ludiques et interactifs, considérés à même de produire un engagement prononcé dans un contexte de concurrence accrue.

Ce cas nous permet de participer à une "histoire intégrée des médias de masse" (Nicholas, 2012) qui s'étend aux jeux vidéo, qui n'ont reçu que peu d'attention dans une perspective d'enchevêtrement médiatique. D'un autre côté, le courant récent d'histoires régionales du jeu vidéo (Wade 2016, Blanchet et Montagnon, 2020, Swalwell, 2021, Svelch, 2018) tend à s'isoler des autres médias tout en restant parfois centré sur des échelles nationales. Notre cas illustre ainsi comment une surface de contact existe entre le jeu vidéo et la télévision par l'intermédiaire du téléphone, qui fonctionne à la fois comme une infrastructure locale et transnationale de diffusion via les serveurs BBS et comme un instrument d'interaction avec l'image télévisuelle, au service de formats ludiques circulant au niveau européen.

Bibliographie

Sources primaires

Hurel, Pierre-Yves. 2024. Interview d'Antoine Rosset.

Hurel, Pierre-Yves. 2024. Interview de Gaël Hurlimann.

Hurel, Pierre-Yves et Guillaume Guenat. 2024. Interview d'Olivier Delaloye.

Le Nouveau Quotidien. 1995. "Un genevois séduit les japonais avec son logiciel de musique" N° 961, 22 février 1995.

Le Matin. 2012. "J'étais un ado parmi les ados", N°327, 25 janvier 2012, page 6. URL : <https://scriptorium.bcu-lausanne.ch/zoom/697966/view?page=5>.

Neue Zürcher Zeitung. 1995. "Zunehmend interaktive Angebote". N°98, 28 avril 1995

Rosset, Antoine et Mike Venturi. 1991. "StarStormer". Consulté via *Macintosh Repository*. <https://macintoshrepository.org> le 17.12.2024.

Radio Télévision Suisse. 1986-1997. "TV à la carte". Émissions du 21.07.1986, 22.07.1986, 23.07.1986, 24.07.1986, 25.07.1986, 11.08.1986, 12.08.1986, 13.08.1986, 14.08.1986, 15.08.1986, 18.06.1994, 20.02.1995, 19.09.1995, 16.12.1995, 24.02.1996, 30.03.1996, 04.05.1996, 01.06.1996, 09.11.1996, 30.11.1996, 21.12.1996, 15.03.1997. Consulté via les Archives de la RTS.

Radio Télévision Suisse. 1993. "StarStormer, Un jeu vidéo spatial" extrait diffusé dans *TV à la carte*. Archives de la RTS. Consulté via *Notre Histoire*, <https://notrehistoire.ch>. En ligne : <https://notrehistoire.ch/entries/vo8vQ9ZJBdZ>

TV-8. 1994. "TV à la carte, l'émission mille-feuille", No 43, 27 octobre 1994, p.7

24Heures. 1995. "Jouez avec la TSR", 3 mars 1995, p.71

Littérature scientifique

Blanchet, Alexis et Guillaume Montagnon. *Une histoire du jeu vidéo en France: 1960-1991 : des labos aux chambres d'ados*. Houdan: Les Éditions Pix'n Love, 2020.

- Cronqvist, Marie, et Christoph Hilgert. “Entangled Media Histories: The Value of Transnational and Transmedial Approaches in Media Historiography.” *Media History* 23, no. 1 (2017): 130–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688804.2016.1270745>.
- Mausli, Theo, Andreas Steigmeier, et François Vallotton. *Histoire de la Société suisse de radiodiffusion et télévision SSR de 1983 à 2011*. Hier+jetzt, Verlag für Kultur und Geschichte GmbH, 2012.
- Nicholas, Siân. “Media History or Media Histories? Re-addressing the History of the Mass Media in Inter-war Britain.” *Media History* 18, nos. 3–4 (2012): 379–394. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688804.2012.727289>.
- Švelch, Jan. *Gaming the Iron Curtain: How Teenagers and Amateurs in Communist Czechoslovakia Claimed the Medium of Computer Games*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The MIT Press, 2018.
- Swalwell, Melanie, ed. *Game History and the Local*. Palgrave Macmillan, 2021.
- Tuomi, Pauliina. “A Brief History of Social iTV Entertainment.” In *Proceedings of the 13th International MindTrek Conference: Everyday Life in the Ubiquitous Era (MindTrek '09)*, 15–18. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, 2009. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1621841.1621846>.
- Uricchio, William. “Télévision : l’institutionnalisation de l’intermédialité.” In *La télévision. Du téléphonoscope à YouTube*, edited by Mireille Berton and Anne-Katrin Weber. Antipodes, 2009. 161–178.
- Wade, Alex. *Playback: A Genealogy of 1980s British Videogames*. Bloomsbury Academic, 2016.

Les nouveaux modes de production et de circulation de l'« actualité littéraire ». La presse littéraire européenne francophone à l'épreuve du numérique

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Cette communication présente les premiers résultats d'un travail de doctorat en cours sur la production et la circulation de l'information littéraire en Europe francophone. À partir d'une enquête sociologique sur le traitement de la littérature dans la presse papier, audiovisuelle et en ligne, nous avons pu observer que si le passage au numérique représente aujourd'hui un enjeu majeur dans l'ensemble du champ journalistique, cet enjeu se dessine d'une manière spécifique pour le journalisme culturel et ici en particulier littéraire, qu'il s'inscrive dans une des presses spécialisées ou au sein de la presse généraliste. Cette démarche internationale comparative et relationnelle donne à voir comment les nouveaux formats numériques reconfigurent ce que nous appellerons la « presse littéraire », à la fois en restreignant le travail journalistique et en l'amenant à se redéfinir et à se réaffirmer, ainsi qu'en modifiant les relations avec les agents intermédiaires de cet espace social, en particulier face à la figure émergente de « l'influenceur livre ».

Cette enquête inductive, qui emprunte à l'approche ethnographique, s'inscrit dans une sociologie des espaces de production culturelle qui se fonde sur la théorie des champs de Pierre Bourdieu. Un ensemble d'entretiens exploratoires a d'abord permis de ne pas construire une grille de lecture *a priori* mais de s'appuyer sur la spécificité du terrain pour s'y orienter - approche d'autant plus nécessaire en raison du manque de travaux scientifiques sur ce terrain. Ensuite, 34 entretiens semi-directifs ont été réalisés en France, en Belgique, en Suisse et au Luxembourg avec : 26 journalistes de radio et de journaux généralistes quotidiens et hebdomadaires ainsi que de magazines, de revues spécialisées et d'agences de presse ; 1 un attaché de presse éditorial, 1 influenceur-livres, 1 illustrateur de la presse culturelle et 5 responsables de politiques publiques pour le journalisme culturel et/ou la littérature. Ces entretiens ont été complétés par des observations ethnographiques au sein des rédactions et des recensements statistiques. C'est cette méthode inductive qui nous a permis - en travaillant à partir des relations objectives des journalistes et des intermédiaires de la profession (particulièrement les attachées de presse) - d'observer que les délimitations de cet espace professionnel ne se font pas en fonction des supports médiatiques mais qu'elles se fondent sur la priorité donnée à la production du discours sur celle de l'image ou vice-versa. En effet, il apparaît que ce ne sont pas les oppositions médiatiques traditionnelles (papier/numérique, écrit/audiovisuel, etc.) qui délimitent en premier lieu cet univers, ce qui semble corrélé à la spécificité du secteur culturel couvert par ces journalistes : les livres. Il s'agit, d'une part, de restituer comment s'organise cet espace médiatique spécifique qui fait de l'écriture à la fois son objet et son instrument de travail à travers divers enjeux et positionnements et, d'autre part, d'analyser les transformations et les résistances qui le traversent au regard du renouvellement des agents intermédiaires (ici les bloggeurs et influenceurs).

Les relations professionnelles entre les journalistes, leur mobilité d'une rédaction à l'autre ainsi que les usages qu'ils font de la presse donnent à voir que « l'information littéraire » (descriptive) dans ses rapports plus ou moins étroits avec la critique (prescriptive) se jouent essentiellement dans la presse écrite papier et en ligne, ainsi qu'à la radio. L'enquête de terrain a alors conduit à écarter le domaine de la télévision. Mais cette opposition entre la production de l'image et de l'écrit caractérise également le domaine des médias d'information littéraire numériques. La distinction entre l'image et le discours se fait ainsi au nom de la profession, de son ethos et de son éthique, dans laquelle l'écriture est à la fois l'objet et l'instrument du travail journalistique littéraire. Nombreux sont les journalistes littéraires qui considèrent que leur rapport à l'écriture journalistique est particulier en comparaison avec ceux

d'autres rubriques. Ce serait en raison de l'objet littéraire sur lequel ils écrivent, indépendamment du fait que ces journalistes se positionnent davantage du côté de la critique, de l'information dite objective ou factuelle, de la prescription ou encore indépendamment du fait qu'ils soient ou non écrivains à côté. Spécialité dominée dans le champ journalistique, l'espace professionnel de la presse littéraire s'organise autour d'un discours de distinction qui vise à renforcer la légitimité des journalistes, cette distinction s'énonçant en particulier à l'égard du *discours universitaire* d'un côté (ce qui n'empêche pas leur recours à un savoir et à un discours analytique qui emprunte à celui-ci) et du *discours publicitaire* de l'autre côté (ce qui n'exclut pas non plus leur assomption d'un discours prescriptif et/ou commercial). Si la légitimité de ces journalistes tend à diminuer au profit de la production d'images et d'un discours publicitaire par les influenceurs, les journalistes témoignent généralement d'un intérêt à ce qu'ils n'aient plus le monopole du discours sur la littérature, légitimité qui est revendiquée par les blogueurs et les influenceurs qui se positionnent comme des amateurs de littérature. Toutefois, c'est en interrogeant les représentations et liens objectifs des journalistes avec les blogueurs et les influenceurs que l'on comprend que la différenciation se fonde davantage sur une priorité donnée à la production d'image par rapport au discours (et vice-versa) que dans le caractère « professionnel » ou « amateur » de leur activité. Ainsi, la distance structurale entre blogueurs et journalistes semble bien moindre que celle qui existe entre blogueurs et influenceurs, ces derniers apparaissant d'ailleurs plus proches du monde de la télévision.

Si les journalistes distinguent catégoriquement leur profession de celle des influenceurs, l'émergence de cette profession transforme tout de même leurs pratiques de travail. Ces nouveaux modes de production de l'actualité littéraire peuvent se comprendre en lien avec les transformations du champ éditorial et de ses relations avec les champs littéraire et publicitaire. Comme la multiplication des publications et la diminution des tirages entraînent un plus fort travail de « visibilité » des livres notamment via les réseaux sociaux, les journalistes qui défendent leur ethos professionnel et le travail d'écriture en opposition au travail des influenceurs sont tout de même disposés, par ces logiques éditoriales notamment, à faire évoluer leur média vers l'image, entrant ainsi davantage dans une logique de prescription qui répondrait aux attentes supposées du public. Mais si les éditeurs eux-mêmes ont effectivement toujours plus recours aux agences de communication et aux réseaux sociaux, ce qui affecte le plus fortement le travail journalistique réside dans le fait que les éditeurs font appel aux influenceurs comme nouveaux *intermédiaires* de médiatisation. Pour comprendre la complexité des institutions et structures de production et de circulation des œuvres dans l'espace public, la sociologie de l'art et de la littérature en effet fait appel à cette notion d'intermédiaire en s'attachant à observer leurs rapports de concurrence. Alors que la « presse littéraire » est décrite par les journalistes comme le secteur de la presse le plus durement touché par les difficultés économiques des rédactions, les éditeurs ont ainsi tendance à rediriger les budgets des relations presse vers leurs services marketing, sous l'effet de la captation des audiences par les influenceurs et les réseaux sociaux. Là où les attachées de presse des maisons d'édition sont généralement à l'initiative de l'envoi des services de presse, la tendance tend ainsi à s'inverser, les journalistes devant de plus en plus solliciter eux-mêmes les éditeurs, même les plus prestigieux. Enfin, la littérature traitée par les influenceurs étant essentiellement anglo-saxonne et les logiques algorithmiques profitant généralement aux centres mondiaux, on peut se demander dans quelle mesure les transformations des relations avec les intermédiaires affectent les rapports internationaux du champ littéraire dans l'espace francophone européen.

Bibliographie

- BOURDIEU, Pierre, *La Distinction* Critique sociale du jugement Paris, Éditions de Minuit, coll. « Le sens commun », 1979.
- CASANOVA, Pascale, *La République mondiale des Lettres*, Paris, Éditions du Seuil, 1999.
- CHALABY, Jean, « From Internationalization to Transnationalization », *Global Media and Communication*, n° 1, vol. 1, 2005, p. 38-42.
- COMBY, Jean-Baptiste, *Enquêter sur l'internationalisation des biens médiatiques et culturels*, Rennes, Presses universitaires de Rennes, 2017.
- DIRKX, Paul, *Les "amis belges". Presse littéraire et franco-universalisme*, Rennes, Presses universitaires de Rennes, 2006.
- DUVAL, Julien et COULANGEON, Philippe, *Trente ans après « La Distinction » de Pierre Bourdieu*, colloque organisé par l'Observatoire sociologique du changement ; le Centre européen de sociologie et de science politique ; le Centre d'études européennes... [et al.], Paris, Éditions La Découverte, 2013.
- MARCHETTI, Dominique « Les sous-champs spécialisés du journalisme », *Réseaux*, n° 111, 2002, p. 22-55.
- MATTELART, Tristan, « Les enjeux de la circulation internationale de l'information », *Revue française des sciences de l'information et de la communication*, n° 5, 2014.
- MEIZOZ, Jérôme, *Faire l'auteur en régime néo-libéral : rudiments de marketing littéraire*. Genève, Éditions Slatkine, 2020.
- REIMER Julius, „Neue Amateure‘ oder ‚traditionelle Rezipienten‘? Empirische Befunde zur Beziehung zwischen Journalismus und seinem Publikum unter sozialmedialen Bedingungen“
- SAPIRO, Gisèle, *Qu'est-ce qu'un auteur mondial ? : le champ littéraire transnational*, Paris, Éditions EHESS Gallimard Seuil, 2024.

Transmediality and Colonial Diplomacy: The Berlin Conference (1884-1885) Through Diplomatic Correspondence, “Livre Jaunes” and the French Press

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Introduction

The 1880s marked a major turning point in the history of the French press and diplomacy. As the 1881 law enshrined freedom of the press and the industrialization of printing techniques led to the emergence of a new era of “newspaper civilization” (Kalifa et al. 2011), colonial tensions between European powers intensified, culminating in the Berlin Conference. Held from November 1884 to February 1885, the Conference brought together 14 major European powers, as well as the United States, with the aim of settling these disputes and establishing a legal framework for the effective occupation of African territory (De Courcel 1988).

While the economic and legal aspects of the Berlin Conference have been the subject of various studies (Förster et al. 1988; Craven 2015; Kumar 2016), its media dimension remains little explored, with the exception of Bendikat's work (1988). Similarly, the “Livres jaunes”, though crucial in mediating diplomatic information, have been neglected by academic research especially in terms of their interaction with the press. These series of publications of French diplomatic documents introduced in 1856, served as an official account of “France's foreign policy, as part of a controlled information effort aimed more particularly at French parliamentarians and opinion leaders, and at foreign cabinets”(Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires étrangères n.d.).

To fill these gaps in existing literature, our study draws on a corpus of primary sources covering three distinct stages in the circulation of colonial diplomatic information: diplomatic correspondence from the reference work “Documents on the Berlin West African Conference and Related Subjects, 1884-1885” (Gavin and Betley 1973), the *Livre Jaune* published by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs in October 1884 (France Ministère des affaires étrangères 1884), and a selection of articles from 13 French newspapers of the period. Mobilizing the concepts of transmediality and entangled media history developed by Cronqvist and Hilgert (2017), we examine how diplomatic correspondence, initially confidential, were transformed into public documents through the *Livre Jaune*, and then reinterpreted by the French press. This approach, highlighting the dynamic interdependence of media across institutional and political boundaries, helps shed light on the mediatization mechanisms of colonial diplomacy and the construction of public opinion in late 19th-century France.

The Construction of the Diplomatic Narrative: From Correspondence to the *Livre Jaune*

The analysis of our corpus reveals a complex system of reciprocal influences between different media, showing how colonial diplomatic information circulates according to a dynamic of appropriation and transformation that highlights the constant interactions between the political sphere, the press and public opinion (Marc 1997).

The private correspondence between Jules Ferry and his ambassador in Berlin, Baron de Courcel, testifies to the constant attention paid to the reactions of French public opinion. In a letter dated 12 December 1884 to Courcel, Ferry is very aware of the risks of any concessions that might undermine France's colonial interests and provoke a justified outcry from public opinion (Gavin and Betley

1973). Courcel voices these same concerns with, Hatzfeldt, German State Secretary for Foreign Affairs, in a letter dated 5 December 1884, pointing to the challenges of convincing French public opinion on the practical results of the Franco-German entente. He cites in particular a “bitterly” critical article published in the *Journal des Débats*, pointing out that: “The government can only be embarrassed by attacks thus sustained.” (Gavin and Betley 1973)

The constant concern for public opinion had also a direct influence on the conduct of negotiations at the Conference, as illustrated by a telegram sent by Courcel to Ferry on November 22, 1884. In this message, the ambassador reports on his exchanges with Dr. Busch, a German Diplomat. Courcel describes drawing his interlocutor's attention to the resistance Ferry might encounter from French public opinion if he pushed concessions too far, pointing to the risk of a “movement of ideas contrary to our arrangements” likely to “occur in Parliament” and “prevent the ratification of the Conference” (Gavin and Betley 1973). This example illustrates how the media dimension and its echoes in public debate can constitute a significant constraint on diplomatic action.

The transition from these confidential correspondences to the *Livre Jaune* is therefore a delicate exercise in colonial narrative construction. A detailed analysis of the *Livre Jaune* “Affaires du Congo et de l’Afrique occidentale” published before the Berlin Conference, reveals an editorial strategy based on several mechanisms. The first level of construction takes place in the selection of documents: over the period 1882-1884, only 28 documents are retained for publication. Beyond this selective process, the organization of the *Livre Jaune* itself contributes to the construction of a coherent narrative. The chronological presentation of documents is designed to demonstrate the logical progression of French colonial enterprises, from the De Brazza mission to the Berlin Conference. The documents are carefully chosen to highlight certain narrative axes: the legitimacy of French action, its continuity, its “civilizing mission”, its moderation in the face of Portuguese pretensions, and the agreement with Germany for a conference presented as the natural outcome of this policy.

The “silences”, however, in this official narrative are significant: internal tensions, doubts about German strategy, and domestic political considerations are systematically erased from this public record. This process of erasure reflects a deliberate desire to shape a smooth, coherent image of French diplomatic action, while concealing the hesitations, disagreements and pressures that may have permeated it behind the scenes.

The Press vs the *Livre Jaune*: Colonial Diplomacy Under Scrutiny

This desire to control the diplomatic image was met with a complex and diverse media reception, as shown by the analysis of French press reactions to the publication of the *Livre Jaune* in 14 October 1884. The study of this reception highlights not only the diversity of editorial positions, but above all what Cronqvist and Hilgert (2017) describe as the “dynamic interconnectedness of media across [...] institutional and political boundaries.”

The flow of diplomatic information follows a pattern in which the official document becomes the starting point for a multi-level media conversation. The first level corresponds to the announcement and factual presentation of the *Livre Jaune*. *Le Monde* opened this media cycle on October 13, preparing its readers for the publication. *Le Petit Journal*, *La Justice* and *Le Matin* followed a similar approach on October 14 and 15, favoring a descriptive presentation that emphasized the technical nature of the document (28 items) and its period of coverage (1882-1884), as well as a selective reproduction of its content. This introductory function is soon supplemented by a second, more in-depth level of analysis. *Le Temps* and *Le Figaro* stand out for their methodical, exhaustive reading of the document over several issues. *La Croix* (October 16) adds to this reading, placing particular emphasis on the issues surrounding Savorgnan de Brazza's expedition.

A third level of media interaction takes the form of direct criticism of the diplomatic document. Over three issues (October 16-19), *La Gazette du Centre* launches an acerbic critique describing the publication as “un truc” of Jules Ferry “to explain his good relations with Germany.” *Le Combat* (October 16-18) took the critical analysis a step further, denouncing “cuts” and “disguise of truth”. The *Journal Des Débats* (October 15 and 20) adds a more technical dimension to this criticism, identifying precisely the gaps in coverage of certain important negotiations. The question

of the Franco-German alliance in particular gives rise to divergent interpretations. L'Anjou was particularly virulent in its criticism, devoting three articles (October 17, 22 and 27) to denouncing what it perceived as a surrender to Germany. Le Radical (October 16) follows this critical line, questioning diplomatic leaks, particularly a letter from the Livre Jaune prematurely published in Le Figaro, suggesting possible orchestration by either Ferry or Bismarck. In contrast, Le Patriote Albigeois (October 19) defends the agreements as balanced and profitable for France.

The publication of the Livre Jaune was part of a sophisticated media ecosystem in which different types of publication interacted. La Croix (October 16) and Le Figaro illustrate this flow of information particularly well, crossing official sources with commentaries from the French and foreign press. A true media conversation developed: Le Radical (October 16) echoed the analyses of Le Journal des Débats, while Le Combat took up and criticized the positions of Le Temps.

Conclusion

This study reveals the complexity of interactions between diplomacy and the media in the age of imperialism. A cross-analysis of diplomatic correspondence, the Livre Jaune and its reception in the French press reveals the emergence of a dynamic public space, where different narratives are developed and confronted on the basis of a common documentary matrix. The case of the Berlin Conference illustrates how the state attempted to shape and control diplomatic colonial discourse while simultaneously coping with press criticism that often challenged its official narrative. Far from being mere relays of official information, newspapers appear to be players in their own right in the colonial debate, capable of influencing representations and decisions of those in power. This transmedia approach opens up new perspectives for rethinking relations between diplomacy, colonial propaganda and public opinion in the late 19th-century.

References

- Bendikat, Elfi. 1988. "The Berlin Conference in the German, French, and British Press." In *Bismarck, Europe, and Africa: The Berlin Africa Conference 1884-1885 and the Onset of Partition*.
- Craven, Matthew. 2015. "Between Law and History: The Berlin Conference of 1884-1885 and the Logic of Free Trade." *London Review of International Law* 3 (1): 31–59. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lril/lrv002>.
- Cronqvist, Marie, and Christoph Hilgert. 2017. "Entangled Media Histories." *Media History* 23 (1): 130–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688804.2016.1270745>.
- De Courcel, Geoffrey. 1988. "The Berlin Act of 26 February 1885." In *Bismarck, Europe and Africa: The Berlin Africa Conference 1884–1885 and the Onset of Partition*, 252–60.
- "Figaro : Journal Non Politique." 1884a. Gallica. October 15, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k279088b>.
- "———." 1884b. Gallica. October 10, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k279083f>.
- "———." 1884c. Gallica. October 13, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k279086k>.
- "———." 1884d. Gallica. October 14, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k279087z>.
- "———." 1884e. Gallica. October 15, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k279088b>.
- Förster, Stig, Wolfgang J. Mommsen, Ronald Robinson, and German Historical Institute in London. 1988. *Bismarck, Europe and Africa: The Berlin Africa Conference 1884-1885 and the Onset of Partition / Edited by Stig Förster, Wolfgang J. Mommsen and Ronald Robinson*. Oxford: University Press for German Historical Institute.
- Gavin, R. J., and J. A. Betley. 1973. *The Scramble for Africa: Documents on the Berlin West African Conference and Related Subjects, 1884/1885*. Ibadan University Press.

- “Journal Des Débats Politiques et Littéraires.” 1884a. Gallica. October 20, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k462997b>.
- “———.” 1884b. Gallica. October 15, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k462992f>.
- Kalifa, Dominique, Philippe Régnier, Marie-Ève Thérenty, and Alain Vaillant. 2011. *La Civilisation Du Journal: Histoire Culturelle et Littéraire de La Presse Française Au XIXe Siècle*. Edited by Kalifa, Dominique, Régnier, Philippe, Therenty, and Marie-Ève. Nouveau monde éd. <https://hal.parisnanterre.fr/hal-01409940>.
- Kumar, Yash. 2016. “Can a Principled Negotiations Framework Explain the Participants’ Strategies and Outcomes in the 1884-1885 Berlin Conference?” SSRN Scholarly Paper. Rochester, NY. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=2720092>.
- “La Croix.” 1884. Gallica. October 16, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k210656g>.
- “La Gazette Du Centre : Journal Quotidien [Du Soir] : Organe de La Défense Sociale et Des Libertés Publiques.” 1884a. Gallica. October 17, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t54427286>.
- “———.” 1884b. Gallica. October 13, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t5442724p>.
- “———.” 1884c. Gallica. October 16, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t5442727t>.
- “———.” 1884d. Gallica. October 19, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t5442730h>.
- “La Justice / Dir. G. Clemenceau ; Réd. Camille Pelletan.” 1884. Gallica. October 15, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k7709811>.
- “L’Anjou : Journal de l’Ouest.” 1884a. Gallica. October 27, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t57263977>.
- “———.” 1884b. Gallica. October 17, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t57263888>.
- “———.” 1884c. Gallica. October 22, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t5726392b>.
- “Le Combat : Journal Quotidien / Rédacteur En Chef Ch. de Massas.” 1884a. Gallica. October 17, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6788529s>.
- “———.” 1884b. Gallica. October 16, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6788528c>.
- “———.” 1884c. Gallica. October 18, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6788530f>.
- “Le Matin : Derniers Télégrammes de La Nuit.” 1884. Gallica. October 15, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k552055c>.
- “Le Monde.” 1884. Gallica. October 13, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6784409f>.
- “Le Patriote Albigeois : Journal de La Démocratie Du Tarn.” 1884. Gallica. October 19, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bd6t53855676n>.
- “Le Petit Journal.” 1884. Gallica. October 14, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k6084571>.
- “Le Radical.” 1884a. Gallica. October 16, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k7602723w>.
- “———.” 1884b. Gallica. October 16, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k7602723w>.
- “Le Temps.” 1884a. Gallica. October 15, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k230451f>.
- “———.” 1884b. Gallica. October 19, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k230456b>.
- “———.” 1884c. Gallica. November 25, 1884. <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/bpt6k230494z>.
- “Livres jaunes | BDN.” n.d. Accessed January 10, 2025. <https://bibliotheque-numerique.diplomatie.gouv.fr/meae/fr/content/livres-jaunes>.
- Marc, Martin. 1997. *Médias et journalistes de la République / Marc Martin*. Histoire, hommes, entreprises. Paris: Odile Jacob.

Faire une histoire visuelle et médiatique du tourisme, un enjeu transmédiatique : l'exemple de la Tchécoslovaquie en contexte de guerre froide

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Revue touristique, guides de voyage, livres photo-illustrés ou encore cartes postales, brochures et supports publicitaires sont autant de publications, supports, médias qui constituent et définissent le corpus médiatique du tourisme. Au-delà de cette définition extensive, et sans effacer les singularités de chaque média qui le composent, nous pouvons nous interroger : le tourisme et ses objets médiatiques peuvent-ils constituer une catégorie transmédiatique singulière ? En premier lieu, le tourisme met en circulation des personnes, mais également un très vaste ensemble d'images, d'objets et de productions médiatiques, faisant écho à la question posée par Jérôme Bourdon : « Qu'est-ce qui passe d'une nation à l'autre, et comment ? » (Bourdon, 2008). Le tourisme représente ainsi un lieu d'observation intéressant des circulations et transferts à la fois de motifs, de stratégies et de normes médiatiques entre plusieurs espaces géographiques. Les corpus produits dès le XIX^{ème} siècle pour documenter des destinations marquent la proximité entre industries touristiques et photographiques (Bouillon, 2017) et se définissent très rapidement par leur caractère exponentiel. Cette tendance s'accroît tout au long du XX^{ème} siècle, suivant les avancées techniques des procédés mécaniques de reproduction de l'image puis le déploiement de matériel photographique et audiovisuel amateur. Au-delà de ce constat de massification de la mise en circulation des images du tourisme, plusieurs interrogations transmédiatiques émergent, tant du point de vue méthodologique que thématique. Quelles sont les images, thématiques et manières de donner à voir qui circulent d'un espace à un autre ? Comment s'articulent et se répondent les différentes existences médiatiques d'un territoire ? Comment le tourisme, en tant que phénomène transmédiatique, est-il investi par des dessins politiques ? A partir de l'exemple tchécoslovaque, la communication propose d'observer les apports d'une approche transmédiatique appliquée au tourisme, à la fois du point de vue de l'étude des stratégies de communication politique que de celui de la circulation de motifs et de normes éditoriales à l'échelle européenne.

La première question que la communication entend étudier est donc celle de l'existence et de la définition d'un corpus touristique médiatique, plus particulièrement ici de l'existence médiatique de la Tchécoslovaquie. Si l'étude de nombreux objets du corpus touristique a désormais été légitimée par l'historiographie (guides de voyage, cartes postales, portraits de ville et de pays¹, affiches et publicité), il n'existe pas encore d'étude transmédiatique à large échelle spécifiquement dédiée au tourisme. Comment définir un paysage touristique transmédiatique ? L'histoire visuelle et médiatique du tourisme a jusqu'à présent été largement dominée par des études mono-médiatiques, qui connaissent aujourd'hui encore une grande actualité de la recherche et des expositions, les liens entre presse et voyage ont également déjà pu être mis en évidence² et mon travail s'inscrit dans cette continuité historiographique tout en s'efforçant de resituer les médias étudiés les uns par rapport aux autres. Dans ma thèse, et dans cette communication, le choix d'une focale géographique précise, la Tchécoslovaquie, permet de circonscrire la vaste question du tourisme à une étude de cas, d'identifier à partir de là certaines circulations transmédiatiques et d'observer un paysage éditorial et médiatique produit depuis la France et la Tchécoslovaquie. Enfin, un des apports de l'approche transmédiatique

¹ Pour reprendre la terminologie mise en place par David Martens.

² Voir la bibliographie finale et notamment le numéro du Temps des Médias n°8 « Le Tour du monde. Médias et voyages », coordonné par Hélène Eck et Laurent Martin en 2007.

se trouve également du côté de l'étude de la réception, en proposant de restituer une expérience plurielle de lecture et de documentation.

Pour réfléchir au tourisme dans une perspective transmédiatique, un des premiers enjeux réside dans la constitution d'un corpus cohérent (et raisonnable, à l'échelle d'une étude individuelle). Ici seront rapidement présentés les enjeux d'accès et les problématiques de conservation de ces publications, qui ne permettent pas toujours d'envisager une étude exhaustive mais qui permettent de souligner la diversité et la quantité des productions éditées pour la période. La communication souhaite surtout se pencher sur les manières de faire dialoguer des objets médiatiques jusqu'ici majoritairement étudiés isolément. Il s'agit par exemple d'observer comment des images, des auteurs ou des photographes se retrouvent d'un média à un autre, et, dans leurs répétitions, participent aussi à la production d'un discours normé et encadré. L'objectif est aussi de comprendre comment, dans ce dialogue, se construisent des définitions visuelles, politiques et commerciales de soi et de l'ailleurs, spécifiquement liées à leur nature transmédiatique. A partir du corpus établi, il est possible de constater que ces définitions trouvent d'abord leur origine dans un vaste programme mis en place par l'Etat tchécoslovaque, qui centralise la production et l'exportation de ces médias, à destination d'un lectorat étranger³. Ici le transmédiatique se donne d'abord à voir comme stratégie de communication politique. Pour retracer ce programme, les archives des maisons d'éditions, agences de presse et agences photographiques tchécoslovaques concernant ces productions touristiques sont malheureusement largement parcellaires. Les archives consultables à l'heure actuelle sont majoritairement constituées d'échanges avec des ministères, qui permettent néanmoins de renseigner certains aspects (par exemple les besoins croissants en termes de rédacteurs et de traducteurs en langues étrangères⁴) ou de rendre compte d'une grande proximité géographique, parfois au sein de mêmes immeubles, entre les acteurs de ces chaînes de production, appartenant pourtant sur le papier à différentes instances médiatiques. Cet aspect sera exemplifié lors de la communication. Il s'agit ici d'observer comment le transmédiatique s'inscrit dans une stratégie plus large de communication politique, produit d'une proximité entre tourisme et propagande (Neves, 2022).

Grand producteur et exportateur de contenus touristiques, l'Etat tchécoslovaque a notamment publié deux revues touristiques trimestrielles à destination de l'étranger – *Pour vous de Tchécoslovaquie* (1961 – 1992) et *Soyez les bienvenus en Tchécoslovaquie* (1965 – 1990). Après avoir esquissé le portrait d'un paysage médiatique touristique, et afin de circonscrire le propos, la deuxième partie de la communication se concentre sur ces deux revues et sur la manière dont peuvent s'y lire les stratégies transmédiatiques de communication mises en place par l'Etat tchécoslovaque dans le contexte de la guerre froide.

Le présent colloque souligne l'intérêt d'ajouter aux analyses des productions imprimées, celles du corpus audiovisuel. Celui-ci n'est pas directement traité dans ma thèse, mais sa présence est néanmoins très souvent repérable au sein des deux revues étudiées : publicité, interviews ou reportages liés à des contenus audiovisuels sont réguliers. Sans aborder le corpus audiovisuel pour lui-même, mon travail est donc sensible à sa présence par le biais de ses citations et de textes dédiés notamment aux programmes radiophoniques, aux disques, aux livres, ou encore à d'autres revues publiées. Sans se substituer à une véritable analyse transmédiatique entre médias imprimés et audiovisuels, cette première approche permet déjà de souligner leurs intrications et d'observer comment ces espaces médiatiques se définissent eux-mêmes par leur caractère transmédiatique. L'étude de la réception des revues permet aussi de mettre en avant ces relations. A titre d'exemple consulté dans un fonds privé, une auditrice s'adressant à un programme radiophonique francophone, diffusé par la Tchécoslovaquie, reçoit en réponse de sa lettre plusieurs numéros de revues ainsi que des objets promotionnels (l'exemple sera détaillé lors de la communication⁵). La question de la réception et des usages de ces médias est aussi posée puisqu'avant, pendant ou après le voyage, les productions étudiées encadrent autant qu'elles informent le touriste, faisant de son voyage une

³ Orbis et Artia, deux entreprises de commerce extérieur et d'édition de produits éditoriaux en langue étrangère, incarnent ce programme en produisant à large échelle des livres, périodiques, disques ou encore des timbres-poste. Voir Blanc Marie, « *Soyez les bienvenus en Tchécoslovaquie*. Le bonheur touristique en contexte de guerre froide : usages, circulations et fonctions du stéréotype visuel », *Déméter*, 11 | Hiver, 28 mai 2024 (DOI : [10.54563/demeter.1539](https://doi.org/10.54563/demeter.1539)).

⁴ Voir par exemple, aux Archives nationales de Prague [Narodni Archiv], les archives du Ministère de l'Education et de la Culture [Ministerstvo školství a kultury], cote 28, carton 1763 (ensemble non classé d'échanges avec la maison d'édition Orbis).

expérience intrinsèquement transmédiatique. La communication reviendra sur des exemples de mises en scène du rôle des récepteurs et des lecteurs des revues étudiées, notamment via leurs rubriques de courrier des lecteurs ou l'organisation de concours de photographies. Les revues s'affichent comme des protagonistes centraux de la bonne tenue du voyage, depuis sa préparation jusqu'à la médiatisation de son souvenir, notamment en se faisant vitrines des autres productions médiatiques disponibles pour le voyageur.

Une autre manière possible d'approcher ce corpus réside dans l'étude des processus de collaborations éditoriales transnationales, et avec eux les circulations de normes, stratégies et savoirs faire médiatiques, autour du tourisme. Le choix d'étudier l'existence médiatique d'un territoire précis permet d'observer des transferts et emprunts d'origines mixtes, notamment en ce qui concerne les productions photo-illustrées, depuis le photojournalisme, la publicité ou encore l'histoire documentaire et humaniste de la photographie.

Au-delà de la question de la propagande, définir ce paysage médiatique et éditorial permet d'interroger les circulations existantes entre objets produits de part et d'autre du rideau de fer. Le tourisme apparaît alors comme un espace privilégié d'observation de phénomènes de circulations transmédiateurs et transnationales (motifs, mais aussi pratiques, savoirs faire), de collaborations et de transferts éditoriaux. Ces collaborations transnationales sont parfois subies, dans le sens où les rédactions ou maisons d'édition francophones qui s'intéressent à la Tchécoslovaquie n'ont pas d'autres choix que d'obtenir leurs images et informations par les canaux tchécoslovaques officiels. Sont alors produits des objets en apparence coconstruits ou co-écrits, dont les archives ne permettent malheureusement pas de retranscrire avec finesse les processus de collaboration, mais qui interrogent un certain pan de la production médiatique dédiée au tourisme. Il s'agit de comprendre si, et comment, ces médias fonctionnent ensemble, se citent et se répondent d'un espace à l'autre, depuis leurs thématiques, leurs agencements internes jusqu'à leurs modes d'élaboration (appel aux mêmes agences photographiques, autonomie des auteurs, reprise de motifs phototextuels, ...). Les observations faites jusqu'ici montrent que les collaborations effectives sont plutôt rares, à quelques exceptions près sur lesquelles la communication se penchera⁶. Mais au-delà de collaborations effectives, les problématiques posées par le colloque permettent de questionner l'existence de modèles et de normes médiatiques en partage au sein du domaine touristique.

S'intéresser au tourisme par le prisme de ses productions médiatiques offre donc une opportunité de dépasser les cadres nationaux. Au-delà de collaborations effectives, plutôt rares, l'approche transmédiateur permet plutôt de souligner un partage de normes médiatiques, codes éditoriaux, manières de montrer le territoire. Cet aspect permet de s'inscrire dans l'histoire de la guerre froide culturelle en mettant en évidence de nombreuses porosités, entre Europe de « l'Est » et de « l'Ouest », et de participer à la remise en question de ces catégories, suivant le sillage de nombreux travaux contemporains (Kott, 2021). Le tourisme produit-il des formes médiatiques réellement globales, où les particularités nationales s'effacent ? Existe-t-il une manière européenne de donner à voir l'ailleurs, de vendre une destination, de produire un récit médiatique du tourisme ? Parmi les approches possibles, l'étude de ces revues permet de souligner un apparent paradoxe : l'utilisation de codes communs à la presse magazine capitaliste, pour vendre une destination et un modèle socialiste. Ici une éventuelle « esthétique socialiste » passe par la présence de certains motifs, sujets, vocabulaire, mais ne semble pas relever d'une forme médiatique spécifique. Au-delà de l'aspect national, c'est plutôt le caractère commercial de ces publications qui semble devoir prévaloir et à partir duquel émerge une définition commune du voyage réussi, sur laquelle la communication reviendra.

La communication propose ainsi de mettre en évidence l'intérêt de produire une analyse transmédiateur du tourisme, en se basant sur une riche historiographie mono-médiatique, notamment dans la perspective de se placer au plus proche de l'expérience du lecteur voyageur. Espace de circulation par définition, le tourisme est ainsi un observatoire privilégié de phénomènes de transferts et partages, à la fois de motifs et savoirs faire. Au fil des analyses émerge l'idée du tourisme comme expérience visuelle et transmédiateur, dont les publications, au caractère souvent prescriptif, ont des effets sur la définition et l'expérience même du voyage.

⁶ Pour citer un exemple le numéro de *La revue française de l'élite européenne* consacré à la Tchécoslovaquie en 1970.

Bibliographie indicative

Antoine, Philippe, Danièle Méaux, Jean-Pierre Montier, et Centre culturel international. *La France en albums: XIXe-XXIe siècles*. Paris, France: Hermann, 2017.

Aslangul, Claire, Bérénice Zunino-Lecoq (dir). *La presse et ses images : sources, réseaux, imaginaires, méthodes*. Berlin: Peter Lang, 2022.

Bertho-Lavenir, Catherine. *La roue et le stylo: comment nous sommes devenus touristes*. Le Champ médiologique. Paris: Éditions Odile Jacob, 1999.

Bouillon, Marie-Ève. « Le marché de l'image touristique ». *Études photographiques*, n° 30 (20 décembre 2012). <https://journals.openedition.org/etudesphotographiques/3334>.

———. « Naissance de l'industrie photographique. Les Neurdein, éditeurs d'imaginaires (1863-1918) ». Thèse de doctorat, Paris, EHESS, 2017. <https://www.theses.fr/2017EHES0102>.

Bouillon, Marie-Ève et Valérie Perlès. *Nouvelles du paradis: la carte postale de vacances*. Paris, France: Loco, 2023.

Bourdon, Jérôme. « Comment écrire une histoire transnationale des médias ? L'exemple de la télévision en Europe ». *Le Temps des médias* 11, n° 2 (2008): 164-81. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tm.011.0164>.

Chabaud, Gilles, et Évelyne Cohen (dir.). *Les guides imprimés du XVIe au XXe siècle: villes, paysages, voyages*. Paris, France: Belin, 2000.

Cohen, Évelyne, et Bernard Toulhier. « Les guides de tourisme, un patrimoine et un objet d'étude ». *In Situ. Revue des patrimoines*, n° 15 (13 avril 2011). <https://doi.org/10.4000/insitu.723>.

Devanthéry, Ariane. « Les guides de voyage, des portraits de pays ? » *Mémoires du livre / Studies in Book Culture* 14, n° 2 (2023): 1-22. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1109172ar>.

Gervais, Thierry. « L'invention du magazine ». *Études photographiques*, n° 20 (1 juin 2007): 50-67. <https://journals.openedition.org/etudesphotographiques/997>.

Gervais, Thierry, et Gaëlle Morel. *La fabrique de l'information visuelle : photographies et magazines d'actualité*. Paris, France: Textuel, 2015.

Kalantzis, Alexia, Hélène Védrine, et Norbert Verdier, éd. *Les périodiques comme médiateurs culturels : autour de la diffusion des savoirs*. Gif-sur-Yvette, France: MSH Paris-Saclay, 2023.

Kott, Sandrine. *Organiser le monde: une autre histoire de la guerre froide*. Paris, France: Éditions du Seuil, 2021.

Lécole Solnychkine, Sophie, David Martens, et Jean-Pierre Montier. *Portraits de pays : textes, images, sons*. Rennes: Presses universitaires de Rennes, 2024.

Manfred Heiting (dir). *Czech and Slovak photo publications, 1918-1989*. Prague: Torst, 2018.

Martens, David. « Qu'est-ce que le portrait de pays ? » *Poétique* 184, n° 2 (12 novembre 2018): 247-68. <https://www Cairn-info.acces.bibliotheque-diderot.fr/revue-poetique-2018-2-page-247.htm>.

Martens, David, Anne Reverseau, et Xavier Canonne. *Pays de papier. Les livres de voyage*. Charleroi : Musée de la Photographie, 2019.

Martin, Laurent. « Point de vue sur les images du monde. Voyage, photographie, médias de 1839 à nos jours ». *Le Temps des médias* 8, n° 1 (2007): 142-58. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tm.008.0142>.

Martins, Susana S. « Between present and past: photographic Portugal of the 1950s ». *Image & Narrative : online magazine of the visual narrative* 23, n° 23 (2008). <http://www.imageandnarrative.be/inarchive/Timeandphotography/martins.html>.

- Moine, Caroline, Yves Bouvier, et Michael Palmer. « L'Europe au cœur de circulations et de transferts transnationaux ». *Le Temps des médias* 11, n° 2 (2008): 6-9. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tdm.011.0006>.
- Morin, Alice, et Jens Ruchatz. « Photography In/Between Media Formats: The Work of Format from Magazines to Books, from Horst. P. Horst to Henri Cartier-Bresson ». *Interfaces. Image Texte Language*, n° 45 (12 juillet 2021). <https://doi.org/10.4000/interfaces.2234>.
- Nachtergaele, Magali, et Anne Reverseau. *Un monde en cartes postales: cultures en circulation*. Marseille, France: Le mot et le reste, 2022.
- Neves, José, éd. « Photobooks as Propaganda A Platform for Power, Protest and Persuasion ». *PhotoResearcher*, n° 38 (2022).
- Pattieu, Sylvain. « Voyager en pays socialiste avec Tourisme et travail ». *Vingtième Siècle. Revue d'histoire* n° 102, n° 2 (6 avril 2009): 63-77. <https://www-cairn-info.acces.bibliotheque-diderot.fr/revue-vingtieme-siecle-revue-d-histoire-2009-2-page-63.htm>.
- Popa, Ioana. « La circulation transnationale du livre : un instrument de la guerre froide culturelle ». *Histoire@Politique* 15, n° 3 (2011): 25-41. <https://doi.org/10.3917/hp.015.0025>.
- Reverseau, Anne. *Portraits de pays illustrés Un genre phototextuel*. Lire et voir, n° 3 in *La Revue des lettres modernes*. Paris: Classiques Garnier, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.15122/isbn.978-2-406-05647-8>.
- Reverseau, Anne, et Galia Yanoshevsky (dir.). « Images d'un Pays. Circulation Iconographique et Identités Nationales ». *Image & Narrative* 22, n° 2 (2021). <https://www.imageandnarrative.be/index.php/imagenarrative/issue/view/156>.
- Sándor, Kálai. « Regards croisés sur la culture médiatique européenne ». *Belphegor. Littérature populaire et culture médiatique*, n° 18-1 (11 janvier 2020). <https://doi.org/10.4000/belphegor.2155>.
- Venayre, Sylvain. « Le voyage, le journal et les journalistes au XIXème siècle ». *Le Temps des médias* 8, n° 1 (1 décembre 2007): 46-56. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tdm.008.0046>.

The Transmedia Publicity of Swiss Banks: Public Relations Strategies and Mass Media Coverage (1960–1977)

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Although many stories keep with Swiss banking, the historical determinants and modalities of information publicly available on Swiss banks have remained out of historiography's interest.¹ This paper examines how transmedia might be used as a method to inquire into the publicity of Swiss banks. In the 1960s and 1970s, Swiss banks became increasingly present on the radio and the television (TV). This added to a long-standing press coverage and herewith amplified and diversified their publicity. Information, images and ideas about Swiss banks circulated across several media simultaneously. Meanwhile, modern public relations (PR) techniques were explored in Swiss industries, including banking. While Swiss banks had long kept 'low-key', they began experimenting with broader PR campaigns. With that in mind, how was public information about banks shaped in the 1960s and 1970s? To answer this question, this paper addresses the rise of Swiss banks' 'transmedia publicity' in the 1960s and up until the Chiasso scandal of 1977, through the PR strategies of the Swiss Bankers' Association (SBA) and the mass-media coverage of banking in Switzerland. It uses the SBA's physical archives, its digitised archives, SBA publicist Leo Schürmann's archives, as well as digitised mass-media archives, for which it draws from the databases of *Radio Television Suisse* (RTS), *Schweizer Radio und Fernsehen* (SRF), *Impresso*² and *e-newspaperarchives*.³ Scientific literature on this topic is virtually non-existent, except for two exploratory works that benefitted from limited first-hand and mass-media archives (Guex and Mazbouri 2013; Agthe 2016).

Throughout the twentieth century, the Swiss banking sector was characterised by extended joint communication. The industry's business association, the SBA, played a central role in publicising banks, their image and values (Guex and Mazbouri 2013). It engaged in what it called indistinctly "Propaganda", "Public Relations", "Öffentlichkeitsarbeit", and "Publizität", to arguably "make the public aware of the important role played by banks in the country's economic life and the advantages that their services can offer everyone".⁴ In fact, it promoted pro-bank and pro-business messages through media financing and content creation (Agthe 2016). Although banks preferred discretion over mass media exposure (Guex and Haver 2007), the association established a commission for permanent publicity efforts in 1948, the *Kommission für Publizitätsfragen* (KfP).⁵ Members were responsible for linking with newspapers in their areas.⁶ The KfP sent them instructions, while also

¹ This paper presents early results of an ongoing doctoral research carried out as part of the project "Impresso - Media Monitoring of the Past II. Beyond Borders: Connecting Historical Newspapers and Radio" (<https://impresso-project.ch/project/>), jointly funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF 213585) and the Luxembourg National Research Fund (17498891). The thesis' working title is "Swiss Banks on Display. A History of the Publicity of Swiss Banks in the 20th Century Through the Public Relations of the Swiss Bankers' Association and Mass-Media Coverage (1913-1991)". It is supervised by Raphaëlle Ruppen Coutaz (University of Lausanne).

² <https://impresso-project.ch/app/>

³ <https://www.e-newspaperarchives.ch/>

⁴ Schweizerische Wirtschaftsarchiv (SWA) (Basel), PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the secretariat (Oetterli) to Philippe de Thibault de Boesinghe, 'Publicité bancaire', 12 March 1964, p. 1; all quotes in German and in French are translated by the author.

⁵ Swiss Bankers Association's Archives (SBAA), VR184Prot_VGgescannt, 'Vorbericht zur 184. Sitzung des Verwaltungsrates der Schweizerischen Bankiervereinigung', 22 September 1947, p. 6.

⁶ SBAA, VRA101Prot_VGgescannt, 'Protokoll der 101. Sitzung des Ausschusses der Schweizerischen Bankiervereinigung', 25 February 1948, p. 10-11.

relying on their own initiatives.⁷ They maintained ties with editorial staffs, especially liberal-conservative press, which collaborated willingly and shared bankers' views.⁸ They published articles and were active in the local public sphere. Besides, the KfP, whose PR exceeded banking topics, operated within the "complex nebula" of corporate influence (Longchamp 2014, 247), aligning with anti-tax, anti-statist, and anti-socialist groups financed by big business since the 1930s (Eichenberger and Leimgruber 2024).

In the 1960s-1970s, the KfP started engaging with radio and television, viewed as means to reach "outsiders".⁹ It encouraged bankers to participate to economic chronicles and information programmes,¹⁰ while occasionally coordinating such efforts,¹¹ like on *Erwachsenen-Bildung* in 1965.¹² The SBA insisted on selecting interviewers and questions.¹³ Partners included NBC, BBC, and *Süddeutschen Rundfunk*, but it also produced a series for SRG's English-speaking international broadcasting titled, "Swiss Banks: Myths and Reality".¹⁴ Furthermore, following liberalisation of advertising on public broadcast in 1965 (Rostan 2017), banks chose joint advertising led by the KfP over individual advertising.¹⁵

Meanwhile, the KfP bolstered its presence in the press beyond liberal-conservative outlets, most notably to local newspapers, and youth and women's magazines. It also partnered with journals such as *Schweizertag* and *Wirtschaft und Recht* on special issues comprising bankers' articles. Some were mailed to Switzerland diplomatic representations for dispatch overseas, as exemplified by a 1967 article in Manila's *Sunday Times Variety* titled "The Truth About Swiss Banking".¹⁶ Initially hesitant about foreign media, the KfP selectively engaged with foreign press, publishing in outlets like *The Times* (UK), *Correio da Manhã* (Brazil), *Valeurs Actuelles* (France), *Southern Economist* (India) and *Svenska Dagbladet* (Sweden). Efforts remained limited and deliberate, avoiding mass coverage. In this regard, the SBA repeatedly rebuffed PR companies' offers. Be it in Switzerland or abroad, the KfP intervened when an article wasn't going banks' way.¹⁷

The KfP's content was remarkably homogeneous. It usually consisted of pro-bank messages draped in educative or technical narratives, as instanced by 1963 articles "L'argent et les banques" and "Que se passe-t-il à la Bourse?",¹⁸ or by the specialist press article "The Evolution of Swiss Banks".¹⁹ If no transmedia campaign was launched as such, the SBA sought a strategic presence in the media ecosystem. Material was framed according to a common standard, contributing to a coherent coverage. The SBA's PR can therefore be understood as an instance of "organised persuasive communication" (Bakir et al. 2019) or "practices of influence" (Cohen 2017). They used a kind of "transmedia advertising" (Mendiz and García Avis 2017), i.e. transmedia PR strategies.

⁷ Ibid., p. 11

⁸ See for example: SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from Michel Petitpierre (Journal de Genève) to A. Herminjard (Banque cantonale vaudoise), 13 February 1968; Swiss Federal Archives (SFA) (Bern), Nachlass (NL) Leo Schürmann, SFA J1.298#2003/36#2182*, letter from L. Schürmann to C. Mötteli (NZZ), 4 March 1958; SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#2174*, letter from D. Barth (Basler Nachrichten) to L. Schürmann, 30 June 1951.

⁹ SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#4023*, letter from Leo Schürmann to E. Roesle, 3 July 1951, p. 2.

¹⁰ Quoted in: SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the secretariat to KfP members, 15 November 1962, p. 5. To the best of my knowledge, no agenda or minutes of this meeting were preserved.

¹¹ SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#411*, 'Protokoll der Sitzung der Kommission für Publizitätsfragen', 22 November 1962, p. 12.

¹² SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, 'Protokoll der Sitzung des Arbeitsausschusses der Publizitätskommission', 26 February 1965, p. 4.

¹³ SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, letter from Schweizerische Volksbank (V. Krügler) to the KfP president (H. Bauer), 'Publizität der Banken am Radio "Die Börse ist nicht nur zum Spekulieren da"', 20 January 1967; SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, 'Protokoll der Sitzung des Arbeitsausschusses der Publizitätskommission', 26 February 1965, p. 2.

¹⁴ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the SBA (Oetterli) to Joël Curchod (SRG), 10 February 1967.

¹⁵ SWA PA 650, G-3-0-1160, letter from the secretariat to KfP members, 18 October 1965, p. 1.

¹⁶ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from the Federal Political Department to the SBA, 14 September 1967.

¹⁷ See for example: SFA, NL Leo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#2174*, letter from L. Schürmann to R. Deonna (carbon copy), 13 August 1951.

¹⁸ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from Wirtschaftsförderung (L. Simeon) to the SBA, 'unsere Bildreportage: "Das Geld und die Banken" und "Was geht an der Börse vor?"', 17 August 1964.

¹⁹ SWA PA 650, G 3-0-1160, letter from Oetterli (SBA) to Statist, 11 July 1966.

Figure 8: 'Bank' Mentions in French-speaking and German-speaking Newspapers in Switzerland (1913–91).²⁰

Figure 9: Frequency of 'Bank' in French-speaking Newspapers in Switzerland (1913–91). See Figure 1 for Impreso collection breakdown. Sources: <https://impresso-project.ch/app/>, consulted on 13 January 2025.

Were transmedia PR strategies correlated with transmedia publicity? In other words, did they succeed? From press perspective, figures 1 and 2 reveal that newspapers reported significantly and increasingly more on banks in the second half of the twentieth century. The coverage steadily increased between the 1950s–1990s, rising nearly fourfold and reflecting the economic growth of Swiss banks during this period (Mazbouri, Guex, and Lopez 2021; Michelet 2023). Peaks often

²⁰ The Impreso collection (orange) comprises all French-speaking newspapers in the Impreso database which are entirely available over the period 1913–91: Journal de Genève, Gazette de Lausanne, L'Express, La Liberté, L'Impartial, Le Confédéré. The e-newspaperarchives.ch collection (red) comprises all German-speaking newspapers in the e-newspaperarchives.ch database which are entirely available over the period 1913–91: der Bund, Berner Tagwacht, Bieler Tagblatt, Bote vom Untersee und Rhein, Burgdorfer Tagblatt, Engadiner Post, Freiburger Nachrichten, die Gewerkschaft, Neue Zürcher Nachrichten, Neue Zürcher Zeitung, Nidwaldner Volksblatt, SMUV-Zeitung, der Schweizer Arbeitnehmer, VHTL-Zeitung, Walliser Bote. Sources: <https://impresso-project.ch/app/> and <https://www.e-newspaperarchives.ch/>, consulted on 13 January 2025.

coincided with crises, such as in 1914, 1931, 1978, and the late 1980s, periods marked by bank failures or takeovers (Giddey and Mazbouri 2022, 256). The period 1955–85 established banking as a focus for newspapers, significantly boosting the publicity of Swiss banks with both positive and negative narratives. Regarding public broadcast, information expanded on both radio and television in the 1960s–1970s (Vallotton 2006), sparking debates about the politicisation of SRG on economic issues (Schneider 2006). Quantitative analysis of bank coverage remains difficult due to fragmented archives. Preserved sources featuring banks include newsflash, documentaries, interviews, debates, and one fiction. A key characteristic was the presence of experts. KfP members and major banks' CEOs participated in information programmes, discussing matters pertaining the economy or the industry in general, rather than their banks.

A striking example was Philippe de Weck, *Union Bank of Switzerland* CEO, who made 27 appearances between 1967 and 1979. He featured on six TV programmes and five radio shows, including six times on *Un jour une heure*. In *En direct avec...* (18 June 1975, one hour), he discussed banking secrecy, banks' financial might, and the Swiss franc. In *En question* (2 November 1976, one hour), he covered his career, banking laws, and Swiss banks' activities. Additionally, he joined a debate on banking regulation during *Table ouverte* (TV, 1977), following the Chiasso money laundering scandal. De Weck's presence contrasted with that of banks' critics: between those two interviews, Swiss-French radio cancelled an interview of socialist MP Jean Ziegler about a book of his, which critically assessed the activity of Swiss banks (Vallotton 2006, 71). De Weck, on the other hand, regularly gave in-depth interviews lasting twenty-plus minutes, ranging from European financial markets, Swiss monetary policies, and the 1970s economic crisis to Swiss democracy, Geneva's international relations school (HEI), and the *Neue Zürcher Zeitung*. He never directly discussed his bank, positioning himself as the go-to banking expert. There is no record of such extended media presence for any banker. De Weck, it appears, was one of the first of his kind to gain a media stature. In 1970, he received the second ever "prize of contact" awarded by Swiss-French economic journalists for his good relations with the press.²¹ Philippe de Weck fostered the transmedia publicity of Swiss banks as he propagated banks' views across several media simultaneously. His case not only shows that the SBA's PR succeeded to a certain extent but also that access to information on banks depended on bankers themselves, at least partly.

Sources

E-newspaperarchives.ch database, various newspapers.

Impresso database, various newspapers.

RTS ARCHIVES database, various programmes.

Schweizerische Wirtschaftsarchiv (Basel), PA 650, G 3-0-1160.

SRF FARO Mediendatenbank database, various programmes.

Swiss Bankers Association's Archives (Basel), various digitised documents.

Swiss Federal Archives (Bern), Nachlass Léo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#411*.

Swiss Federal Archives (Bern), Nachlass Léo Schürmann, J1.298#2003/36#4023*.

References

Agthe, Bonnie. 2016. 'Les Stratégies de Propagande de l'Association Suisse Des Banquiers (1920–1977)'. Master's thesis, Lausanne: University of Lausanne, unpublished.

²¹ Le nouvelliste, "Le prix Contact 1970 des journalistes économiques romands décerné à M. Philippe de Weck", 21 April 1970, p. 5. Available: <https://www.e-newspaperarchives.ch/?a=d&d=NVE19700421-01.2.20.1.3>, consulted on 21 January 2025.

- Bakir, Vian, Eric Herring, David Miller, and Piers Robinson. 2019. 'Organized Persuasive Communication: A New Conceptual Framework for Research on Public Relations, Propaganda and Promotional Culture'. *Critical Sociology* 45 (3): 311–28.
- Cohen, Yves. 2017. 'Une école de liberté historiographique'. *Critique* 843–844 (8–9): 700–711.
- Eichenberger, Pierre, and Matthieu Leimgruber. 2024. 'Monied Politics and Business Influence. The Swiss Wirtschaftsförderung, 1942-2000'. Conference paper. La Suisse, Espace Privilegié Du Néolibéralisme? Lausanne: Université de Lausanne.
- Giddey, Thibaud, and Malik Mazbouri. 2022. 'Banking Crises, Banking Mortality and the Structuring of the Banking Market in Switzerland, 1850–2000'. *Financial History Review* 29 (2): 247–70.
- Guex, Sébastien, and Gianni Haver. 2007. 'James Bond Contre - Ou Pour? - Les Gnomes de Zurich. L'image de La Place Financière Suisse Dans La Série 007'. In *James Bond (2)007. Anatomie d'un Mythe Populaire*, edited by Françoise Hache-Bissette, Fabien Bouilly, and Vincent Chenille, 330–38. Paris: Belin.
- Guex, Sébastien, and Malik Mazbouri. 2013. 'Une Grande Association Patronale Dans La Sphère Publique: L'exemple de l'Association Suisse Des Banquiers (de 1912 à Nos Jours)'. In *Les Organisations Patronales et La Sphère Publique. Europe XIXe et XXe Siècles*, edited by Danièle Fraboulet, Clothilde Druelle-Korn, and Pierre Vernus, 205–35. Rennes: Presses universitaires de Rennes.
- Longchamp, Olivier. 2014. *La Politique Financière Fédérale (1945–1958)*. Lausanne: Antipodes.
- Mazbouri, Malik, Sébastien Guex, and Rodrigo Lopez. 2021. 'La Place Financière Suisse 1890–2010'. In *Histoire Économique de La Suisse Au XXe Siècle*, edited by Patrick Halbeisen, Margrit Müller, and Béatrice Veyrassat, 495–550. Les Routes de l'Histoire. Neuchâtel: Livreo-Alphil.
- Mendiz, Alfonso, and Isadora García Avis. 2017. 'La Hibridación de Narrativas (Transmedia y Branded Content) En El Actual Storytelling Publicitario'. In *Nuevas Narrativas. Entre La Ficción y La Información: Desde La Desregulación a La Integración Transmedia*, edited by E. de la Cuadra. Barcelona: Ediciones de la UAB.
- Michelet, Arthur. 2023. 'Exile on Wall St. The Swiss Big Banks' Multinationalisation and Their Expansion to the United States (1966–1978)'. Master's thesis, Lausanne: University of Lausanne, unpublished.
- Rostan, Blaise. 2017. *La Publicité, Enjeu Du Financement Mixte de l'audiovisuel En Suisse*. Genève: Slatkine.
- Schneider, Thomas. 2006. 'Vom SRG-"Monopol" Zum Marktorientierten Rundfunk'. In *La Radio et La Télévision En Suisse. Histoire de La Société Suisse de Radiodiffusion et Télévision SSR 1958-1983*, edited by Theo Mäusli and Andreas Steigmeier, 83–138. Baden: hier+jetzt.
- Vallotton, François. 2006. 'Anastasia Ou Cassandre? Le Rôle de La Radio-Télévision Dans La Société Helvétique'. In *La Radio et La Télévision En Suisse. Histoire de La Société Suisse de Radiodiffusion et Télévision SSR 1958-1983*, edited by Theo Mäusli and Andreas Steigmeier, 37–82. Baden: hier+jetzt.

The Intellectual Life that Oil Fostered: Exploring the History of a 'Media Ecosystem' in Latin America (1950-1980)

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In the history of the media in Latin America, oil companies played a fundamental role. Established in the continent since the 1920s, but especially active since the 1950s, companies such as Standard Oil –with its subsidiaries Esso and Creole– and Royal Dutch Shell used the media as a key tool to position themselves locally and gain social and political sympathies. Connecting objectives with the geopolitical interests of the United States, Esso supported the transmission of international news in Argentina, Brazil and Uruguay across radio programs, such as *El Reporter Esso* (Klößner, 2008). Shell and Creole pushed up, in turn, the production of documentaries and audiovisual contents on the history and cultural life of Brazil and Venezuela.

However, the media work of these companies was more extensive and complex. In Brazil and Colombia, Esso also supported the emerging artistic field, sponsoring exhibitions and contests that would help renew the arts in both countries. Esso Colombia also sponsored the 1959 Book Festivals, and the main Novel Prize of the 1960s. Based on its New York magazine *The Lamp*, Standard Oil also maintained the magazines *El Farol* (Caracas, 1939-1975), and *Lámpara* (Bogotá, 1952-1972, 1979-1990), both noted for their material quality and vanguard content (Nesselrode, 2023). Shell also launched its own cultural magazines: *Revista Shell* (Caracas, 1952-1962) and *Vínculo Shell* (Bogotá, 1955-1965), which directed by local academics and intellectuals brought together studies on history, literature, and science.

The national and material specificity of each medium created or promoted by the oil companies has, however, prevented them from being analyzed in its entirety. Although a large part of the oil media did not interact with each other in terms of contents, they were all articulated within a larger strategy of acclimation in different and complex political and sociocultural contexts. Sometimes encouraged by the governments themselves, such as that of Venezuela, which promoted different investments by the oil companies in areas such as education or agriculture, but on other occasions by opening up a space of their own, due to the absence of the State in cultural policy, as in the case of Colombia or Brazil, the oil companies managed to institute a series of media operations of wide scope and influence.

Key to building the reputation of companies among different interest groups, such as politicians, businessmen and intellectuals, but also relevant for advertising purposes among the working and emergent middle classes, the set of media built by oil companies in Latin America demands a study approach that transcends the monomedia vision. Concepts such as 'media ecosystem' seem, in this sense, more appropriate to encompass the complexity and diversity of the media built by the oil companies. Despite the national, technological and production differences, and even the target audiences, literature magazines, films, radio and television programs, along with the cultural activities that the companies also encouraged, such as literary prizes or art exhibitions, coexisted and were dynamically interconnected.

A special case of interconnection and ubiquity is provided by the Filmoteca Shell, a repository of short films created by the company and which operated simultaneously in Caracas, Bogotá and São Paulo. Linked to the public relations offices present in each city, Filmotecas made its films catalogues available to universities, schools, other companies and institutions. Although initially composed of Shell's own films, this repository gradually incorporated films produced independently or those

winners of contest sponsored by the company. Publicized extensively in the different Shell magazines and other news and literary periodicals, the Filmotecas were fundamental places in the promotion of the company's audiovisual work but played in parallel as a kind of 'media libraries' for educational purposes in general publics.

Examples like this show that the oil media ecosystem affected the evolution of the media cultures of each country –complexing to this extent their role as agents of modernization (Colmenares, 2024). On the one hand, it determined new products and forms of audiovisual consumption, and on the other, it influenced groups and actors interested in using the media for academic purposes or artistic creation. The ability to affect professions associated with the media, precisely through the creation or stimulation of new media platforms, constitutes another particularity of the ecosystem. In Venezuela, television news such as *El Observador Creole* (Standard Oil, 1953-1972) were not only key in the transition and familiarization of modern forms of informative communication but also crucial in the expansion of journalists' labor field. Staffed by local journalists with large experience in radio news programs, such as *El Reporter Esso*, the new television program required, however, adaptations that led to early specializations in the profession.

The public relations offices of Esso and Shell were equally relevant in the transformation of intellectual figures into 'mediensarbeiters' (Wagner, 2019). In Shell Colombia, its first public relations director, the journalist Jorge Arenas Lemos, would be the director of the magazine *Vínculo Shell*, publication always admired by their materiality and newer reportages, as well as the producer of the company films. The experience gained would later make him a representative figure of private television production and advertising agencies in Colombia.

The recruitment of writers and poets for public relations positions was, in fact, a constant among oil companies. In Venezuela, *Revista Shell* was headed by young but valued figures from the literary medium, such as the poet Julián Pradón and the politician and publisher José Ramón Medina, while in Colombia Esso would hire writers such as Álvaro Mutis and journalists such as Hernando de Francisco as public relations directors, both of whom were key in sponsoring radio programs and supporting contests and magazines. This practice would even be replicated by national oil companies, such as the Peruvian Petroperú, which had the poet Pedro Roger Cateriano as its head of public relations for a long time, a position that allowed him to create the Copé Short Story Prize in 1979.

By stimulating and recruiting writers and journalist, promoting new practices in public relations, supporting galleries and artists, introducing radio news programs and producing audiovisual content, oil capital represented, in short, a decisive factor in the transformation of the Latin America cultural field. Part of a larger research project, this proposal aims to explore for the first time the 'media ecosystem' built by Oil Companies. Along with reconstructing their origins and multiply fronts, this study explores its impacts within intellectual sphere. Considering the entangled dimension of the case (Cronqvist & Hilgert, 2017), as well as its transnational condition (Lyons & Mollier, 2012), the proposal also reflects on the legacy of this media 'petroculture' in the region.

References

- Colmenares, M. (2024). Después de medio siglo (1966) y el ocaso de la Shell como agente modernizador en Venezuela. *Culturales*, 12(1), 1-41.
- Cronqvist, M., & Hilgert, C. (2017). Entangled Media Histories: The value of transnational and transmedial approaches in Media Historiography. *Media History*, 23(1), 130-141.
- Klöckner, Luciano (2008). *O Repórter Esso: a síntese radiofônica mundial que fez história*. Porto Alegre: Age.
- Nesselrode, Sean (2023). *Refined Material: Petroculture and Modernity in Venezuela*. Oakland: University of California Press.
- Lyons, M. & Mollier, J.-Y. (2012). L'histoire du livre dans une perspective transnationale. *Histoire et civilisation du livre* 8 (nov.), 9-20.
- Wagner, H.-U. (2019). Writers and Radio: How literary authors have made use of the medium over a century. *Journal for Media History*, 22(2), 8-23.

Research Data Infrastructures Before They Were Cool: Microfilms, Photocopies and Early Digital Storage Devices in Humanities Scholarship (1950-1990)

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Introduction and methodological framework: media-aware historiography of Humanities disciplines

Humanities disciplines, such as History and Philology, have historically developed methods, tools, and infrastructures for organizing, accessing, and referencing primary sources as research data. However, their historical narratives - often rooted in a print-based culture - frequently overlook the role of media and technology. However, over the past fifteen years, interest in older technological and communication media has surged, fueled by cultural "technostalgia" (van der Heijden, 2015) and a shift in Media History scholarship, flagged by the emergence of "media archaeology" (Huhtamo & Parikka, 2011; Parikka, 2012) and the contributions of media historians like Lisa Gitelman (2014) and Matthew Kirschenbaum (2016), who emphasize the material, cultural, and social dimensions of media technologies.

In that vein, concepts and practices related to research data infrastructures in historicophilological disciplines have been significantly shaped by various media technologies over the years. These technologies have, in turn, influenced and enhanced key research practices, standards, and processes, such as copying, storage, documentation, sharing, and access, that continue to be central - but not entirely new - to today's digital research agenda. However, many recent initiatives developing and establishing 'best practices' in research data infrastructures in Humanities (Gooch and Strange, 2023), especially when dealing with cultural heritage assets (Benardou et al., 2017), have overlooked the historical foundations and contributions of these infrastructures "before they were cool," failing to situate these research practices within a broader historical continuum.

This presentation summarizes preliminary findings from an interdisciplinary research on the (pre)history and use of research data infrastructures in the Humanities. This work forms part of a broader international research project currently under development for submission for international funding. The project seeks to connect and compare case studies from the UK, the Netherlands, France, and Greece, exploring the transnational and transmedia histories of media technologies like microfilming, photocopying, and early digital storage (e.g., floppy discs, CDs), within the historiographies of historical and philological disciplines. By examining these media technologies, the study highlights the overlooked material dimensions shaping historicophilological disciplines in post-war Europe while introducing a broader critical framework for examining the relationship between epistemological and methodological practices in the Humanities and their ties to historicity, materiality, media, and technology. By following Gerben Zaagma's recent work around the genealogy of Digital History through the role of technology in historical research (Zaagma 2024), this work also aims to enrich transnational historiographical accounts of the Humanities by integrating Media History and Media Archaeology. For this presentation, I will explore the case study of the introduction of microphotography in Greece, particularly in Modern Greek History and Philology after the 1950s.

A (brief) history of microphotography in Humanities research

Microphotography, a technique using microfilm to reproduce entire texts in miniature form, dates back to the mid-19th century. Introduced by the British optometrist John Benjamin Dancer, the "father of microphotography," who created the first microphotographs of texts in 1839 using a microscope and camera, the technique was further refined in 1859 by René Dagron who patented a method replacing the daguerreotype with the collodion wet plate technique, enabling clearer images and multiple reproductions (Luther 1959). Commercial interest surged in the late 1920s when Eastman Kodak released the first microphotographic plates. The development of microphotography in America advanced rapidly during the 1930s, driven by innovations like the portable camera from Recordak Corporation, which initially served banks and insurance companies before gaining adoption by libraries and research institutions, mainly for document preservation, particularly for newspapers printed on fragile wood-pulp paper and manuscripts (Binkley, 1929; Kuhlman, 1935). Key milestones included a 1936 Carnegie-funded study confirming the stability of microphotography (Binkley, 1936), the formation of the American Library Association (ALA)'s Committee on Photographic Reproduction of Library Materials (Raney, 1937), and the launch of *The Journal of Documentary Reproduction* in 1938. In subsequent years, libraries expanded the range of microphotographed materials to include newspapers, periodicals, rare books, manuscripts, and maps. Microfilm classification systems were also introduced, integrating microfilms into library collections under the principle of "treat microfilm like a book," with detailed classification information such as numbers, physical descriptions, content, and ownership/user details.

In Europe, microphotography saw extensive use during World War II for espionage and document preservation under the threat of destruction. In the post-war period, the widespread adoption of various microphotographic formats (microfilm, microfiche, aperture cards), along with advancements in photographic and reading devices, gradually expanded to England, France, and Germany (London Symposium 1949). By the 1960s, microphotography had become a widespread, cost-effective, compact and stable solution for storing the exponentially growing volume of archival and original research and archival documents. Advances in technology further cemented its role in providing efficient storage and fast and high-quality access for textual research data.

Microphotography and Modern Greek Historical Disciplines

Microphotography arrived in Greece in the early 1960s in the fields of archival and historical research, and coincided with the development of the Center for Modern Greek Research at the Royal Research Foundation under the direction and guidance of K. Dimaras. "Every time I returned from a trip abroad," noted Dimaras, "I would bring back, each time, bags full of microfilms of manuscripts or printed materials" (Dimaras 1977a), and indeed he was the one who brought microfilms in his suitcases while introducing the technique and the uses of microphotography to the historical and philological disciplines and to research processes.

Through and around this Center, and mainly through the development of newly funded Greek Enlightenment Study Group (OMED) in 1962, Dimaras promoted a series of methodological renewal attempts for Modern Greek Historicophilological disciplines by seeking "good tools for doing our job": "Organization of documentation, indexes, computerization, all media technologies are beginning to be employed to facilitate young researchers in accessing quicker their sources" (Dimaras 1969).

Since the 1960s Dimaras initiated more than hundred scientific missions for microphotography and cataloging documents, manuscripts and printed archival assets across Greek monasteries, libraries and special collections, establishing also the Microfilm Archive (Sklavenitis 1982). Microfilms from these missions as well as special orders from abroad were stored at the Archive, with on-site reading machines available for researchers. Microphotography quickly became an infrastructural technology for Greek researchers, granting them access to otherwise inaccessible historical resources, while introducing the concept of affordable, mechanical copy and (re)use of research data for multiple cases/uses. Researchers gained access to research data without the need to travel to the source institutions, transforming their research and working conditions long before the advent of the

digitization revolution. Microfilms were further enhanced with detailed documentation and finding aids, including reference numbers, which streamlined their search, retrieval, and referencing; they quickly became an integral part of the Center's library holdings, prioritizing access over the broader goal of preservation of archival and historical resources (fig.1-2).

These microfilm collections have been pivotal in enabling groundbreaking research outputs from dissertations, scholarly editions of rare material, editions of correspondence and large scale bibliographies and indexes of journals. These outputs, particularly in the fields of Modern Greek Enlightenment and Early Modern Greek Studies, have profoundly shaped the development of disciplines of History and Philology in Greece over the past 70 years. Microfilms also introduced innovative solutions for data management, such as compiling complete journal series by combining microfilms from multiple libraries ("composite journal bodies") (Dimaras 1967). Additionally, the introduction of new formats like microfiche in the 1970s revolutionized access, availability, and portability of research data (Dimaras 1977b).

Fig.1-2. Microfilms stored at the storage units of the Center for Modern Greek Research

The Historical and Paleographic Archive (IPA) of the Educational Foundation of the National Bank of Greece also started its microphotographic collection in 1975, with the stated goal of preserving and microfilming historical archives and manuscript codices in Greece (IPA 1978, 8). Since its inception, IPA employed microphotography both to preserve and to provide access to historical source materials through scientific missions across Greece, while systematically organizing expert research services centered around microfilms as accessible research data infrastructures. These services extended across media and technologies, including offering photocopies derived from microphotographs and providing microfilm copies, relying to expensive machines for this task (reel-

to-reel), as well as the option to borrow microfilms for a minimal fee, while providing formal ways to referencing the microfilms as sources, while encouraging national and international collaboration across institutions (fig.3-4). Finally, around the microfilm collection, IPA developed an informed, technologically-supported institutional expertise around Paleography and Textual Studies, with specialised publications, annual seminars and classes around paleography and preservation of primary documentary sources, following the example of the Center for the History of Texts of the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)” (Tselikas 1994).

Fig. 3. The HIRAKAWA camera for microphotography at IPA

Fig. 4. The MICROPRINT KODAK machine at IPA, for producing photocopies from microfilms.

Conclusion

The above brief overview of the adoption and use of microphotography by the historical and philological research community in post-war Greece allows us to discern the progressive change in working conditions as well as the epistemological and methodological development of the fields of Modern Greek History and Philology. Interestingly, while microfilms globally addressed the issue of storing growing volumes of newspapers and books, in Greece, microphotography initially served as a tool for accessing hard-to-reach archival documents. The Greek library sector massively adopted microphotography only in 1984, starting with the microfilms of the daily press collections at the

Library of the Parliament. Furthermore, microfilm introduces the concept and practice of the accessible copy into the workflow of Modern Greek historical and literary fields, thus inaugurating a series of practices around the relationship of researchers with the original source and its technically mediated reproductions, visible to this day in the digital environment, resulting to new protocols of research practices around possession, storage, sharing, access, and (re)use of research data. Not surprisingly, modern copyright legislation has been shaped around the concepts of reproduction and copying, with rights for use and distribution of copies first being formalized in relation to microfilms; in Greece, a systematic legal framework for copyright was established only in 1993. Finally, microfilm, which allowed limited interventions in copies, was quickly replaced by commercial photocopiers in research environments. These media technologies, easy to use and affordable, enabled a wide range of user interventions, fundamentally altering the way we process and use copies and research data.

Selective Bibliography

- Benardou, A., Champion, E., Dallas, C., & Hughes, L. (Eds.). (2017). *Cultural Heritage Infrastructures in Digital Humanities*, Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315575278>
- Robert Cedric Binkley (1936), *Manual on methods of reproducing research materials: a survey made for the Joint Committee on Materials for Research of the Social Science Research Council and the American Council of Learned Societies*. Ann Arbor, Mich.: Edwards
- Robert Cedric Binkley (1929), "Do the records of science face ruin?" *Scientific American*, 140, p. 28-30.
- K. Th. Dimaras (1977a), "Technical Tools", *To Vima*, 24 June 1977.
- K. Th. Dimaras (1977b), "The microfiche", *To Vima*, 15 July 1977.
- K. Th. Dimaras (1969), "Bibliography of Greek Symmeikta"(1888-1961)", *The Gleaner*,7, p.113-114.
- K. Th. Dimaras (1967), "Composite journal bodies", *The Gleaner*, 5, p.172-174.
- Tim van der Heijden (2015), "Technostalgia of the present: From technologies of memory to a memory of technologies", *European Journal of Media Studies*, (4), 2, p.103-121.
- Erkki Huhtamo and Jussi Parikka (2011), *Media Archaeology: Approaches, Applications, and Implications*. Berkeley, CA: University of California Press
- Lisa Gilteman (2014), *Paper Knowledge: Toward a Media History of Documents*, Duke University Press.
- Megan Gooch and Damon Strange (2023). Consolidating Research Data Management Infrastructure: Towards Sustainable Digital Scholarship. *J. Comput. Cult. Herit.* 16, 4, Article 82 (December 2023), 16 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3627169>
- IPA (1978), "Development and Institutions", *Microphotography of manuscripts and Archives* Athens, Historical and Paleographic Archive (IPA), p .7-9.
- Matthew Kirschenbaum (2016), *Track Changes: A Literary History of Word Processing*, Harvard University Press
- A. F. Kuhlman (1935), "Are we ready to preserve newspapers on film?", *Library Quarterly*, 5, p. 189-214
- London Symposium (1949), «Symposium on Microphotography from the user's point of view», London meeting, 16 February 1949.
- Luther, F. (1959). *Microfilm: a history, 1839-1900*. Annapolis, Md.: National Microfilm Association.
- Jussi Parikka (2012), *What Is Media Archaeology?* Polity.
- M. Llewellyn Raney (ed.) (1937), *Microphotography for Libraries. Papers Presented to the Microphotography Symposium at the 1936 Conference of the American Library Association*.
- T.E. Sklavenitis (1982), "Catalogue of Microfilm Archive. Microphotographies of documents, manuscripts, printed assets and lists", 1960-1980", *Working papers*, 1.

A. Tselikas (1994), “The Historical and Paleographic Archive (IPA) of the Educational Foundation of the National Bank of Greece”, *Technology*, IPOP, 4, p. 10-11.

Gerben Zaagsma (2024), “Facing the History Machine: Toward Histories of Digital History”, *History of Humanities* 9:2, p.451-491, <https://doi.org/10.1086/731827>

Just to Be Safe. The Transnational History of the Nuclear Energy Debate Across Media, Science, Activism and Parliamentary Debate (1950-2025)

Work in Progress Report

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Introduction

The “Just to be Safe” project seeks to study the history of the nuclear energy debate as it unfolded over time and across media, political and scientific discourses and across national boundaries. Methodologically, it is situated at the intersection between social sciences, history and digital humanities. Building on corpora of mass digitised documents, we focus on the flow of ideas between media (newspapers and radio), science (journals), politics (parliamentary proceedings), activists (popular science books, memes). Using a longitudinal and transnational approach, we analyse the evolution of anticipated futures, interpretative frames, and reference points analogue to the concepts included in book indices.

In this paper, we document our efforts to augment and scale up the traditionally manual work on frame analysis using Large Language Models (LLMs). Frame analysis describes a heterogeneous field of research practices in the social sciences and media/communication studies which “examines the selection and salience of certain aspects of an issue by exploring images, stereotypes, metaphors, actors, and messages”¹. At its core, it serves scholars to study how human interpretation and reasoning gives meaning and coherence to historical events.

For this study we revisit earlier work by Gamson and Modigliani who conducted a frame analysis of the coverage of nuclear power in US-American media based on samples of TV news, magazines, cartoons and columns in the period 1950 until the 1980s. Their study centers around the accident at Three Mile Island nuclear power plant: On March 28th 1979, the TMI-2 reactor released radioactive gas and iodine into the environment as a direct consequence of badly executed maintenance on the day before. The accident has gained notoriety due to competing alarms which contributed to misdirected efforts to remedy its consequences². To-date considered the worst nuclear accident in US history, the incident has garnered worldwide attention and led to a reevaluation of security systems for nuclear power plants. Moreover, the accident occurred in a period in which much of the initial unconditional excitement over nuclear power technologies had given way to an increasingly heated and critical debate over safety, economic viability, impacts on human health and environmental risks.

Growing resistance against nuclear power manifested itself in Switzerland as it did elsewhere in the form of organised protest against individual prospected projects (first and foremost: Kaiseraugst³) by heterogeneous groups of activists. Especially noteworthy is a popular vote from 20.5.1979: The Swiss

¹ Jörg Matthes, “What’s in a Frame? A Content Analysis of Media Framing Studies in the World’s Leading Communication Journals, 1990-2005,” *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly* 86, no. 2 (June 1, 2009): 349, <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769900908600206>.

² J. Samuel Walker, *Containing the Atom: Nuclear Regulation in a Changing Environment, 1963–1971* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1992), 211.

³ Patrick Kupper, *Atomenergie und gesplante Gesellschaft. Die Geschichte des gescheiterten Projektes Kernkraftwerk Kaiseraugst*, 1st ed. (Chronos Verlag, 2003), <https://doi.org/10.33057/chronos.0595>.

public validated a revision of the preceding legislation which now coupled new nuclear power plant projects to actual energy needs and placed the responsibility for waste management on plant owners⁴. The Three Mile Island accident took place in the midst of campaigning by state-backed proponents and activist-backed opponents.

Gamson and Modigliani's study builds on a theoretical model developed by Gamson and Lasch⁵. The model identifies a frame as a "central organising idea for understanding events related to the issue in question". According to the authors, frames are ambivalent, evolve, overlap, may capture modestly contradictory viewpoints and exist above simple for-against dichotomies. Frames are shaped by framing devices such as metaphors and reasoning devices such as asserted roots, consequences and principles. Frames and framing devices together are conceptualised as "interpretive packages". Gamson and Modigliani identified such packages, traced their trajectories over time and related them to survey results as proxies for shifts in public opinion. Two of them, titled "runaway" and "devil's bargain" are closely related and emerge as increasingly important after the accident. They interpret "nuclear power as an inevitable, uncontrollable fact of life combined with anxiety about the unknowable disasters that may spring from it"⁶. The authors conclude that in the time after the accident "the dominant package in media discourse is fatalistic"⁷.

We hypothesize that a similar dynamic unfolded in the Swiss press, especially in light of the ongoing debate prior to the popular vote. If this was indeed the case, we expect that the "runaway" and "devil's bargain" frames dominate the press coverage.⁸

From a linguistic point of view, frames appear as subtle rhetorical devices. Their power derives from the fact that even though we can recognize frames, their presence is not made explicitly. Readers consume and oftentimes accept the frames precisely because they remain 'hidden in plain sight'. Frames provide coherence to otherwise inchoate chains of events (and sentences) thereby influencing perception of such complex issues as nuclear power.

Until now, frame analysis is a method predominantly rooted in qualitative data analysis practices which revolve around rule-based human interpretation of text. Machine learning, on the other hand, tends to rely heavily on surface structure of a text, i.e. the sequence and frequency of tokens. Detecting semantic nuances therefore posed difficulties. But with the advent of neural networks and especially the language modelling, the field has made a substantial leap forward in the automated semantic analysis of language.

In this abstract we experiment with Large Language Models as tools for 'qualitative frame analysis' at scale. The main methodological question we tackle is: to what extent can LLMs reliably detect the runaway frame (and of course others) in newspaper articles and other sources? To this end, we test different prompting and validation strategies using different ChatGPT models. Our analysis is based on a set of 9890 Swiss newspaper articles running until 2017 which were derived from the Impresso corpus.⁹

Methods

Our experiments focussed on three elements: prompting strategies, document selection, and evaluation. Prompting—often somewhat bombastically referred to as 'prompt engineering'—is the technique of writing task-specific instruction in natural language, which the model will then aim to "complete", by predicting probable continuations. We experimented with various prompts of increasing complexity, from binary to automatic 'chain-of-thought' prompting.

⁴ <https://www.bk.admin.ch/ch/d/pore/va/19790218/index.html>.

⁵ William A. Gamson and Kathryn Eilene Lasch, "The Political Culture of Social Welfare Policy," Working Paper, December 1980, <http://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/handle/2027.42/50995>.

⁶ William A. Gamson and Andre Modigliani, "Media Discourse and Public Opinion on Nuclear Power: A Constructionist Approach," *American Journal of Sociology* 95, no. 1 (1989): 27.

⁷ Gamson and Modigliani, 30.

⁸ Gamson and Modigliani, 33.

⁹ <https://impresso-project.ch/app/>.

Prompting consists of two layers or messages. The 'system' message outlines how you want to model to behave, and the contours of the task you want to implement. The 'user' message then provides the content you want to model to operate on. Our base template was the following: we provided as a system prompt the message: “You are a helpful AI that will help with detecting frames in Swiss newspaper articles.” Our user message consisted of three demarcated inputs:

We prompted ChatGPT with bullet points that correspond to the framing and reasoning devices proposed by Gamson & Modigliani. We deconstructed the “runaway” frame into the following elements:

- The "runaway" argument on nuclear power contains the following elements:
- Nuclear power is a technology that has spiraled out of human control.
- We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power.
- We are committed to nuclear power but will eventually have to pay an unknown and potentially severe price.
- Nuclear power is a powerful force that we've unleashed but can no longer control - like a genie that can't be put back in the bottle.
- Nuclear power is like Frankenstein's monster: a force turning on its creator, or a time bomb waiting to explode.
- There are invisible and delayed radiation effects and harm may not be known until years later.
- Nuclear power shows that humans have dared to play God by tampering with fundamental forces of nature.

Each prompt furthermore contained

- **A newspaper article** about nuclear energy from a Swiss newspaper written in German or French.
- **Task instructions:** the steps the model needs to follow when generating a response to the prompt.

All the prompts pose the same question— “Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article? Yes or no?”—but contain different, and increasingly complex instructions.

- **Binary:** we simply ask the model to give a yes/no answer.
- **Automatic chain-of-thought:** in this case, we close the prompt with the instruction ‘let’s think step-by-step’ which invites the language models to spend more tokens on reasoning before producing the final yes/no answer. We refer to this prompt type as Auto-CoT.
- **Automatic chain-of-thought and Quoting:** this prompting strategy closely follows Auto-CoT, with the added instruction to “support your reasoning by providing quotations from the article” (Auto-CoT+Quote).

The table below, shows examples of the completions for each prompting technique. The prompts themselves can be found in the Appendix.

binary	Auto-CoT	Auto-CoT+Quote
No.	<p>To determine if the "runaway" frame appears in the article, let's examine the elements of the frame against the article's content.</p> <p>1. Nuclear power is a technology that has spiraled out of human control. - The article discusses potential dangers and risks of the Goesgen nuclear power plant, indicating concerns about control, but it does not explicitly state that nuclear power has spiraled out of control.</p> <p>2. We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power. - The article does not explicitly mention a lack of understanding about nuclear power. It focuses on</p>	<p>To determine whether the "runaway" frame appears in the article, let's examine each element of the frame and see if it is reflected in the article.</p> <p>1. Nuclear power is a technology that has spiraled out of human control. - The article discusses the potential danger of a nuclear core meltdown and the inability to guarantee the safety of the population. This suggests that nuclear power could potentially spiral out of control. - Relevant quotation: <QUOTE>lors d'une éventuelle fusion du noyau entraînant une explosion, des éléments radio-actifs pourraient se propager à l'extérieur, dans un périmètre de plusieurs kilomètres</QUOTE>.</p> <p>2. We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power. - The article highlights concerns about the safety measures and the lack of comprehensive planning for potential disasters, indicating a lack of full understanding of the risks involved.</p>

<p>current safety concerns and the need for improvements rather than past misunderstandings.</p> <p>[...]</p> <p>Therefore, the overall presence of the "runaway" frame in the article is limited. The frame is not clearly or fully articulated in the article.</p> <p>Answer: no</p>	<p>- Relevant quotation: <QUOTE>aucun plan d'évacuation concret n'existe</QUOTE>.</p> <p>[...]</p> <p>Considering these points, the "runaway" frame is indeed present in the article. The article articulates the various elements of the frame through concerns about safety, uncontrollable risks, and the potentially severe consequences of nuclear power. Therefore, the answer is yes.</p>
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Table 1: Example of completions for different prompting strategies

To evaluate (and better understand) these prompting techniques, we pursued following strategies:

- **Manual validation:** We compare our manual annotations to the classification produced by the LLM.
- **Consistency across prompting strategies:** We inspect to what extent applying different prompts results in the same answers. Are the LLMs confident in their classification, even when applying slightly varying prompting strategies? Which articles emerge as hard to classify and are potentially ambiguous?
- **Prompt-brittleness and self-consistency:** We repeatedly apply the same prompt to the same inputs and monitor to what extent the produced answers are consistent across runs. If the prompt produces different outcomes for the same inputs, we can refer to it as brittle. In the literature, this approach is also referred to as “self-consistency”¹⁰.

For our initial experiments we used the *gpt-4o* and *gpt-4o-mini* models. We used the standard text generation parameters, except the temperature which was set to 0.7.¹¹ This allows for more diversity and randomness in the generation process. Temperature regulates the ‘creativity’ of the model, or put differently, instead of deterministically generating the same output each time, it allows the model to follow diverging paths. When predicting the next word in a sequence, increasing temperature will put more probability mass on less obvious tokens, thereby giving the model a wider variety of options to formulate an answer.

Preliminary results

Because frames are such intricate linguistic phenomena, studying them with computational instruments poses multiple challenges. To summarize the methodological aims pursued in this abstract: we investigate to what extent Large Language Models offer a valuable instrument for frame analysis at scale. In this abstract, we test the feasibility of the approach and aim to understand the extent to which these models accomplish this complex task, before applying a chosen method at a larger scale, which is the aim of future work.

We sampled articles from a keyword-based collection of more than 9890 articles mentioning nuclear power-related concepts from the Impresso corpus (as of 2024). For our initial experiments, we narrowed our focus to articles published between 1979 and 1983 that mentioned the location “Harrisburg” (TMI sample). The latter toponym serves as a proxy to find articles that mention the Three Mile Island incident. To assess historical trends we also created a set of randomly selected articles between 1975 and 1983 (random sample).

In what follows, we first explore how LLMs handle this task by looking more closely at LLM responses to articles about the TMI incident, and then ask the question about “ground truth”, i.e. assess to what extent they provide the “correct” answers (annotated sample), and lastly provide a preliminary longitudinal analysis of the runaway frame in the Swiss news reporting on nuclear energy based on the random sample.

¹⁰ Xuezhi Wang et al., “Self-Consistency Improves Chain of Thought Reasoning in Language Models” (arXiv, March 7, 2023), <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.11171>.

¹¹ Wang et al.

Dataset name	Content	Explanation
Nuclear energy dataset	9890 articles	Keyword search against Impresso corpus
Three Mile Island (TMI) sample	TMI: 27 articles published in 1979 Post TMI: 41 articles published between 1980-83	Nuclear energy articles mentioning “Harrisburg”
Random sample	Pre-TMI: 200 articles between 1975-1978, TMI: 200 articles from 1979 Post-TMI: 200 article between 1980-1983	Random sample from nuclear energy dataset restricting to specific timeframes
Annotation sample	18 articles from the TMI subsample	Articles where selected based on the (dis)agreement between responses using the binary and Auto-CoT+Quote prompting strategies

Table 2: Overview of datasets used in this abstract

Given the subtlety and intricacy of the task, we initially questioned how different types of models respond. We compared the answer of *gpt-4o* (OpenAI’s “flagship” model at the time of writing) and *gpt-4o-mini* (a smaller model for more “focused” tasks), our intuition is that the models behave differently because of the difficulty and complexity of both the input data as well as the task. Our results partly confirmed this intuition. The results below are based on the TMI sample.

Figure 1: Distribution of yes(1) and no (0) answers for different prompts and models for articles in the TMI sample

What immediately captures the eye in Figure 1, is the volatility of the smaller model (*gpt-4o-mini*): it seems especially sensitive to the inclusion of quotations in the response. Just following the chain-of-thought results in largely negative answers, but after being asked to cite the original source during reasoning, the model largely switches its decision and replies “yes” in the vast majority of the cases. We observe more robust behaviour in responses of the *gpt-4o* model, while the distribution changes a bit depending on how we formulate the question, the overall direction of answers remains stable as the vast majority consist of negative answers.

Interestingly models behave similarly for simplest, binary prompts. When we don’t give the model “space” (or tokens) to reason, the distribution of the answers seems similar. Even though we turn

later to a manual evaluation, both high incidence rates of the positive cases combined with sensitivity to prompting suggest that the smaller model provides a less reliable tool for frame analysis.

Another signal in this respect is the model’s self-consistency plotted in Figure 2. Self-consistency captures the extent to which a model gives the same answers to the same question. High scores indicate high consistency, while lower scores suggest less stability, meaning the model might change its opinion when confronted with the same question.

These results indicate that the larger model tends to be more consistent, especially when we allow more space to reason. It won’t change its “mind” under the pressure of repeated questioning. What is interesting, moreover is that Figure 2 also suggests that including direct quotations tends to lower the self-consistency, i.e. that quotes can influence a model's response to go the other way. Overall, these divergences require us to rely on the unfortunately more expensive (both financially as well environmentally) *gpt-4o* for parts of our analysis.

Figure 2: self-consistency for different prompts and models for articles in the TMI sample

Of course, even when the distribution of the responses is the same, this doesn’t necessarily imply that the models agree. To what extent is there inter-annotator agreement between these models? We address this question in more detail below.

Figure 3 Heatmap comparing model output at the document level for articles in the TMI subsample

To assess to what extent these prompting strategies converge, not just on the global level but looking at the distribution of the responses, but also at the individual, document level, we consider each pair

of prompt type and model (e.g. a binary prompt processed by *gpt-4o*) as an annotator, and then compute inter annotator-agreement using Cohen’s Kappa.¹² When near zero, the Kappa scores indicate that agreement is no better than chance. Scores very close or equal to indicate near perfect agreement. The scores reported in Figure 3 suggest low to moderate agreement between most of the prompting strategies.

The preceding analysis suggests that measuring the presence of the runaway frame depends on the model and prompting technique used. Unfortunately, there is no easy way to select which strategy works best. The comparison of algorithmic responses does not tell us to what extent any of these answers are correct. For this purpose, a large part of our research consists of a manual evaluation of these ChatGPT outputs. We are only at the early stages, but we can explain how we approach the evaluation and comparison of different approaches.

For our first annotation experiment, we sampled 18 articles for manual labelling, focussing on both positive and negative examples of the runaway frame. We were especially interested in gauging whether a simple binary prompt is as reliable as the more complex chain-of-thought style prompting. For this reason, we selected cases in which both prompting strategies (dis)agreed. For example, for the cases where Auto-CoT+Quote answered ‘yes’, we selected three articles for which the binary prompt repeatedly and consistently gave positive or negative answers and cases where it was uncertain (it answered yes, one or two times out of three). We’d repeat the same sampling method for the negative Auto-CoT predictions.

Figure 5: accuracy for different prompting strategies based on the annotated sample

Figure 5 clearly indicates that in case of disagreement, the more complex prompting strategies deliver the best responses. In more than 90% of the cases, the annotator agreed with the LLM judgement based on chain-of-thought reasoning. Zooming in on the disagreement can help us establish which route leads to better answers and where things might go wrong.

However, there is a tricky problem with this evaluation, because the more elaborate completion (and thereby the LLM) has the power to convince us of its assessment. For example, looking more closely at the following argument made by *gpt-4o*, when arguing the extent to which the article reflects the claim “We did not fully understand what we were getting into with nuclear power”:

The article touches upon the argument that theoretical calculations cannot replace practical experience: <QUOTE>...les calculs théoriques ne peuvent pas complètement remplacer l’expérience pratique.</QUOTE> This implies that the full extent of nuclear power’s risks may not have been understood before its adoption.

To what extent the quote supports the claim is a qualitative, rather subjective judgment. When annotating, we experienced that the response of the LLM itself might influence our reading of the article and, therefore, the annotation. Sometimes, the response would flag passages that went unnoticed or interpreted those fragments in ways we initially understood in a different way. Rather

¹² https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.metrics.cohen_kappa_score.html

than simple hallucinations, these diverging interpretations appear to be valid, complementary interpretations in their own right and justified with the spectrum of subjectivity.

Figure 6: Probability of article containing the “runaway” frame by year based on the random sample. Figure on the left shows the results for the binary prompt, the one on the right those for the Auto-CoT+Quote prompt.

Lastly, we turn to a longitudinal analysis. We applied the binary and Auto-CoT prompt to a random sample of 600 newspaper articles between 1975 and 1983¹³ to assess changes in the presence of the runaway theme over time. Figure 6 shows the annual probability that an article on nuclear power contains the runaway frame. We applied the simple binary and the chain-of-thought prompt with quotations.

While applying these different prompts to a random set of articles on nuclear does change the timeline, somewhat, the results nonetheless point in the same direction. Most importantly, the runaway frame is not a product of the disastrous events in Harrisburg as observed by Gamson and Modigliani for their US-based analysis, but was already “in the air” in the preceding years. While these preliminary results need to go further, they do contradict the findings of Gamson and Lasch, especially because the negative frame of losing control over nuclear power, actually declines after the incidents.

	Random sample	TMI sample
pre-TMI	0.18	
TMI	0.17	0.26
post-TMI	0.07	0.31

Table 3 Probability that article contain the runaway frame based on the random and the TMI sample

However, other findings do align partly with the existing literature. We computed the presence of the runaway frame in the TMI and a random sample. We find that articles about the Three Miles Island incident are more likely to contain the runaway frame when compared to a random selection of articles on nuclear energy. Focusing on the binary prompt as an example—but the same applies to the Auto-CoT prompt—we found that the runaway frame has an incidence rate of less than 20%. Articles that report about the looming nuclear disaster in Pennsylvania, the likelihood is substantially

¹³ We divided the data into three periods: pre-Three Mile Island (1975-1978), the year of the incident (1979) and the aftermath (1980 till 1983). For each period we randomly sampled 200 articles and annotated them with gpt-4o using the binary and Auto-Cot with quote prompt.

higher, hovering between 25% and 31%. In this sense, these two phenomena do seem entangled, but our evidence suggests that existing negative frames of nuclear energy influenced the perception of the Three Mile Island incident instead of the reverse (i.e. the event changed the framing).

Conclusion and Future Work

In this presentation, we discussed a methodological experiment on automatic frame detection with Large Language Models. We focussed on evaluating how a language model responds to prompts with instructions to identify the runaway frame in Swiss newspaper articles. We showed that its responses might be substantially different and developed a few automated and manual approaches to assess the performance and behaviours of LLMs. Lastly, we demonstrated how such a frame analysis at scale might contribute to the wider historical discussion on the perception of nuclear energy, more specifically related to the influence high-profile, often disastrous, events have on the way this technology is framed.

In the future, we expand the analysis not just to more and more diverse data (e.g. books, scientific articles), but will also include other frames. More importantly, we will refine our prompting strategies as well as the automated and manual evaluation of LLMs outputs. Also, we will experiment with building smaller, more specialized language models, based on *gpt-4o* response and synthetic data. This will be crucial to apply these techniques to a large corpus of more than 160.000 articles.

Bibliography

- Gamson, William A., and Kathryn Eilene Lasch. "The Political Culture of Social Welfare Policy." Working Paper, December 1980. <http://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/handle/2027.42/50995>.
- Gamson, William A., and Andre Modigliani. "Media Discourse and Public Opinion on Nuclear Power: A Constructionist Approach." *American Journal of Sociology* 95, no. 1 (1989): 1–37.
- Kupper, Patrick. *Atomenergie und gespaltene Gesellschaft. Die Geschichte des gescheiterten Projektes Kernkraftwerk Kaiseraugst*. 1st ed. Chronos Verlag, 2003. <https://doi.org/10.33057/chronos.0595>.
- Matthes, Jörg. "What's in a Frame? A Content Analysis of Media Framing Studies in the World's Leading Communication Journals, 1990-2005." *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly* 86, no. 2 (June 1, 2009): 349–67. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769900908600206>.
- Walker, J. Samuel. *Containing the Atom: Nuclear Regulation in a Changing Environment, 1963–1971*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1992.
- Wang, Xuezhi, Jason Wei, Dale Schuurmans, Quoc Le, Ed Chi, Sharan Narang, Aakanksha Chowdhery, and Denny Zhou. "Self-Consistency Improves Chain of Thought Reasoning in Language Models." arXiv, March 7, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.11171>.
- Wei, Jason, Xuezhi Wang, Dale Schuurmans, Maarten Bosma, Brian Ichter, Fei Xia, Ed H Chi, Quoc V Le, and Denny Zhou. "Chain-of-Thought Prompting Elicits Reasoning in Large Language Models," n.d.
- Zhang, Zhuosheng, Aston Zhang, Mu Li, and Alex Smola. "Automatic Chain of Thought Prompting in Large Language Models." arXiv, October 7, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2210.03493>.

Appendix: Prompts

Below we detail the prompts used in the article. {FRAME CONTENT} contains the bullet claims of the runaway prompt as specified by Gamson and Modigliani. {ARTICLE CONTENT} refers to a newspaper article drawn from the nuclear energy data or other sample

Binary prompt

System message

You are a helpful AI that will help with detecting frames in Swiss newspaper articles.

User message

We provide you with:

(A) FRAME: a frame consisting of different claims listed as bullet points.

(B) NEWSPAPER ARTICLE: a newspaper article about nuclear energy from a Swiss newspaper written in German or French.

(C) TASK: question and description of the task you need to perform.

(A) THE FRAME: {FRAME CONTENT}

(B) NEWSPAPER ARTICLE: {ARTICLE CONTENT}

(C) TASK:

Question: Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article?

Simply answer with *****yes***** or *****no*****.

Auto-CoT prompt

Same as the binary prompt except for point (C) in the user message.

(C) TASK:

Question: Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article? Let's think step by step.

At the end, decide if the frame is present in the article by answering *****yes***** or *****no*****.

Auto-CoT+Quote prompt

Same as the binary prompt except for point (C) in the user message.

(C) TASK:

Question: Does the "runaway" frame appear in the article?

Instructions:

- Let's think step by step.
- Support your reasoning by providing quotations from the article and explain how they articulate the runaway frame.
- Quotations should follow the original language of the article and surrounded by <QUOTE> tags
- At the end, decide if the frame is present in the article by answering *****yes***** or *****no*****.

A Transmedia History Approach to Studying the Cultural Politics of Software Interfaces, 1977-1995

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In my paper, I explore how a transmedia approach can play a crucial role in developing a conceptual framework for historical research on software interfaces. I am currently designing such a framework for my upcoming research project, *INTERFACE POLITICS: Evolution of Software Interfaces and the Politics of the Imagined Computer User, 1977–1995*. This project aims to analyze how software interfaces from 1977 to 1995—including operating systems, productivity software, utilities, edutainment, and games—embedded computer users within power/knowledge dynamics and either reinforced or challenged cultural norms associated with the "imagined user."

The UI functions as a screen-based, aesthetic representation of a computer's functionality (Andersen, Pold, 2011). Additionally, the UI enables the computer to simulate itself (Krapp, 2024) by providing users with an intelligible set of abstractions (such as files and folders) and presenting possible actions in a comprehensible manner. My project adopts a historical approach, critically analyzing the evolution of personal computing from 1977 to 1995, with a focus on the changing politics of design language in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). I conceptualize UIs as integrated systems that merge discourse, visual representation, and technical functionality, exploring the interplay between these domains. My research is primarily grounded in critical software studies (Fuller, 2008; Mackenzie, 2006), a field that emerged within the broader framework of media archaeology. To enhance this framework, I incorporate selected concepts from Science and Technology Studies (STS), media history, and design studies.

I aim to outline how a transmedia approach can be used to build a research toolset that connects theory development with empirical research. First, I argue that a software interface is a form of media in itself. As a result, the history of interfaces should receive more attention and theoretical consideration, similar to other "media histories." While there is a body of studies on the contemporary digital environment in terms of "interface culture" (e.g., Paulsen, 2017; Hookway, 2014; Callahan, 2004; Jørgensen, 2014), scholars paid very little attention to critically examining the historical development of UIs. Moreover, these aforementioned works can often be interpreted as examples of research focused on monomedia units.

I explain how I adopt a transmedia approach in designing an exploratory project that develops theory through extensive empirical research involving diverse media objects. My project goes beyond analyzing the program itself to investigate the functionalities and cultural significance of software interfaces. In doing so, I address the issue of screen essentialism—a "monomedia perspective" often seen in works on software history, including game studies research. Much of the existing scholarship and popular discourse focuses on the aesthetics and internal organization of the screen, which is central to the interface. However, studies that address the historical trajectory of software interfaces often pay little attention to concepts like 'transcending monomedia units,' as mentioned in the CFP, or to the various forms of circulation that occur between media.

Surprisingly, there is very little empirically based theoretical consideration of computers as a medium. While there is a substantial body of literature discussing computers as tools for accessing digital media such as movies and music, these discussions often focus on the interfaces of programs used to access such media. However, relatively little scholarly attention has been devoted to studying the histories of interaction with computers as a medium in their own right. This research gap is evident in the relative lack of studies that bridge the fields of the history of computing and media history.

Historically, computer interfaces functioned as transmedia objects, visually representing programs on the screen. This visualization extensively used references to the design conventions in other media, but also extensively used conventions from office work. To ensure these interfaces were fully functional and widely adopted, they relied on various supporting materials. These included user manuals, keyboard overlays, reference cards, and favorable reviews in computer magazines. Visual elements such as box art, advertisements, and TV commercials also played a critical role. Furthermore, third-party books and magazine guides often offered additional support, occasionally revealing undocumented interface features.

I argue that software interfaces should be investigated as mediums interconnected with various objects. These objects should not be seen merely as historical sources for studying the history of software but as integral elements of the software itself. My application of the transmedia approach is informed by several corresponding and complementary frameworks, including John Law's study (2002) on decentering objects in STS scholarship, selected works on transmedia by Kinder and McPherson (2014), and recent calls for theoretically informed research in the history of computing by Abbate and Dick (2022).

In my paper, I present the key ideas that form the theoretical framework and design of the empirical research for my project. My research agenda aligns with the remark included in the CFP, which emphasizes moving away from "accumulating histories of different media" and instead focusing on "the elements that bridge them" [Transmedia CFP]. My research involves the emulation of a sample of legacy programs to better understand their functionalities. However, the insights into design language and human-computer interaction systems derived from emulation-based research are closely connected to four key areas. These include the use of historical sources beyond the program itself to explore how the interface existed within the broader media landscape of its era.

Here, I outline the key research areas of my project that correspond to the field of transmedia research

1. Decentering interfaces.

Here, I demonstrate the extent to which the software user interface was embedded within print culture. Contemporary interfaces are, so to say, largely self-sustained, incorporating tutorials, tooltips, and other user aids directly within the interface itself. However, historically, software was accompanied by extensive collections of printed materials. The most obvious of these artefacts was the user manual. Beyond that, users were often provided with other materials, such as reference cards and technical documentation. In addition to official documents, there was—and still is—a robust industry of third-party books providing users with additional knowledge. For example, at this moment, I have collected more than fifty third-party books that teach users how to operate or design programs for various iterations of the Mac OS and Windows 95.

I also design an analysis of how software interfaces and their claimed innovativeness are portrayed in other media. Specifically, I aim to conduct a critical discourse analysis of the language used in software reviews in the computer press to highlight positive or negative impressions of user interfaces. 'Software critics,' as magazine editors referred to themselves, developed a specific vocabulary and set of conventions in their reviews to emphasize the strengths or weaknesses of an interface.

2. Connecting interfaces to broader ideas of how users should interact with computer as a medium.

This research area focuses on selecting and deconstructing several broad ideas and more specific design principles of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). These concepts have played a pivotal role in shaping and negotiating the role of the user interface as a central element in computer-based media ecosystems. For example, I can reference a seminal work that deconstructs the politics surrounding the concept of "user-friendliness" (Black, 2022). Similarly, Rachel Plotnick, in her study *Pushing the Button Across the Twentieth Century*, argues that not only the button itself but also the designed pleasures, experiences of control, and agency associated with pushing a button across various media and infrastructures played a pivotal role in shaping modernity in the twentieth century. Of course,

interacting with a user interface often involves similar pleasures of control of clicking buttons on-screen or pressing the ENTER key. Drawing from professional literature on HCI and software criticism, my research deconstructs the role of these interactions in computer as a medium.

3. How interfaces represent office ecosystems?

This focal point of my research deconstructs the key influence of office-related ideas and objects on how interfaces are designed to integrate into the everyday lives of users. Office culture is not a medium itself, but as Haigh (2012) noted, it was a key ecosystem for information processing and retrieval. This culture played a pivotal role in shaping twentieth-century modernity. In this context, I analyze a range of programs that provide an on-screen simulacrum of a literal desktop, such as *Magic Desk* (Commodore, 1983). More broadly, I also explore ideas about how users should organize information processing on a computer, drawing inspiration from traditional office culture.

4. How user interfaces are represented in other media?

This focal point deconstructs the conventions and cultural logic behind the presentation of UIs in audiovisual media. Television programs from the 1980s, such as BBC's *The Mighty Micro* and *Micro Live*, often portrayed computers as the future, extensively showcasing actions on a computer screen to support their overarching theses on how computers would transform society. The highly influential program *Computer Chronicles* frequently employed the convention of inviting software designers into the studio, where they demonstrated program functionalities and discussed their qualities while navigating the interface on-screen. Rather than simply using such materials as supplementary sources for studying interfaces, I am more interested in exploring the cultural logic of speaking about and showcasing interfaces in other media.

This focal point also includes an investigation into the world of FUIs—fictional, or fantasy user interfaces. These are elaborate interfaces designed for audiovisual media to depict how users interact with computer technology in fictional settings.

References

- Abbate, J. and Dick, S. (eds.). *Abstractions And Embodiments. New Histories of Computing and Society*. Johns Hopkins University Press, 2022.
- Andersen, C. U., Pold, S. B., eds. *Interface Criticism: Aesthetics Beyond the Buttons*. Aarhus: Aarhus University Press, 2011.
- Black, M. *Transparent Designs: Personal Computing and the Politics of User-Friendliness*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press, 2022.
- Callahan, E. "Interface Design and Culture." *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology* 39 (2004): 257–310.
- Fuller, M., ed. *Software Studies: A Lexicon*. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2008.
- Haigh, G. *The Office: A Hardworking History*. Melbourne: The Miegunyah Press, 2012.
- Hookway, B. *Interface*. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2014.
- Jørgensen, K. 2014. *Gameworld Interfaces*. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2014.
- Kinder, M. and McPherson, T., eds. *Transmedia Frictions. The Digital, the Arts, and the Humanities*. Oakland: University of California Press, 2014.
- Krapp, P. *Computing Legacies. Digital Cultures of Simulation*. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2004.
- Law, J. *Aircraft Stories. Decentering the Object in Technoscience*. Durham and London, Duke University Press, 2002.
- Mackenzie, A. *Cutting Code: Software and Sociality*. New York: Peter Lang, 2006.

Paulsen, K. *Here/There: Telepresence, Touch, and Art at the Interface*. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2017.

Plotnick, R. *Power Button: A History of Pleasure, Panic, and the Politics of Pushing*. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2018.

From Oral History to Metadata? Report from the Oral History of Radio Archivists (OHRA) Pilot Project

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About Impresso

The ‘Impresso – Media Monitoring of the Past II: Beyond Borders’ project (2023-2027)¹ aims to pioneer new approaches for exploration of Western European newspaper and radio sources in five languages and to advance innovative practices in historical research with transnational and transmedia perspectives. As such, it promises to allow the joint exploration of historical media content across time, languages, and national borders. Building on the first Impresso project (2017-2020) that created a research infrastructure for Swiss and Luxembourgish newspaper sources, the current project represents an expansion in geographical and linguistic scope, as well as media type. Accordingly, it promises to not only generate innovative interfaces for the exploration and computational processing of enriched historical print collections, but also those of radio, which span, for example, audio recordings, transcribed speech, typescripts and accompanying archival metadata.

Challenges of newspaper and radio sources

The addition of radio collections as part of the second Impresso project introduces a new level of complexity. While many historical newspaper collections may also have gaps, in most European contexts they generally tend to be well-preserved by national libraries and archives, and included in mass digitization projects since the 2000s (Ehrmann, Bunout, and Clavert 2022, 1–5). By contrast, the emergence of European broadcast collections in the 1930s were generally characterised by the creation of radio programme recordings for internal needs, predominantly for the purposes of re-use in programming (Birdsall and Harrison 2022). Early radio collections in Europe often comprise pre-recordings or partial recordings, rather than the systematic recording and documentation of broadcast transmissions, a practice that was only introduced at some national broadcasters with the transition to digital archiving methods from around 2000 onwards. In addition, institutional radio collections may include recordings over multiple formats (e.g. wire, disc, analog/digital tape), recordings donated by amateur collectors, and gaps/inconsistencies in descriptive and technical metadata.

Neither newspapers nor radio sources allow for complete and representative reconstruction of past media landscapes and present distinct challenges for historians: Newspapers are overwhelming through their sheer abundance of preserved materials. In contrast, radio research faces the scarcity of preserved recordings and the variety of different sources.

¹ <https://impresso-project.ch/>

The OHRA project

Overall, Impresso is committed to the idea of providing transparency regarding the composition of the historical media corpus, the process of semantic enrichment and its implications and the representation of enriched media sources in its interfaces. In this context, the “Oral History of Radio Archivists” (OHRA) project strives to help users understand the intricacies of radio collections, inform their reasoning and point them to relevant resources beyond the Impresso platform. Impresso II’s future users will be able to search and compare radio and newspaper sources, but may be less familiar with the institutional, technical and/or archival conditions influencing the available corpus of digitized recordings and enriched metadata. For this reason, and in line with the principle of transparency, OHRA has the intention of exploring possibilities to collect and represent in a comparable manner contextual information between available collections within the Impresso II research infrastructure: What information about radio archives is relevant for researchers and missing from the existing metadata? Which of this information could be added by an archivist? As such, we recognise that there is often crucial knowledge preserved in current radio archivists’ memories that cannot be inferred from institutional records. In line with recent archivist knowledge transfer initiatives (van Dalen and Šičarov 2021), we identify oral history interviews as a productive method for eliciting key insights about radio collections, the conditions of their creation, stewardship and (digital) preservation.

We identified three main information needs for which an oral history approach appears promising: First, researchers need to understand the composition and content of a given archival collection. This includes evolving archival policies, source prioritisation during digitisation, variabilities in audio/data quality over time and unexpected data in the collection. Second, researchers need to identify additional, relevant resources. These resources may, for example, be created by other institutions or amateur historians, previous research projects. Third, researchers need to gain insights into forthcoming projects (e.g. collection digitisation) or other relevant information not yet announced publicly. OHRA’s goal is to collect such information and to make it available to Impresso users to allow critical usage of the data we provide and to help guide their further research.

Related work: Oral history in Media History and Metadata quality assessment

Oral history, as a methodology for data collection and analysis, has long been a key approach within humanities research. More recently, there has been an increased interest in using oral history research data within digital humanities research, and the growth of a field of digital oral history (Boyd and Larson 2014; Flinn et al. 2024; Dalen and Šičarov 2021). The value of oral history for histories of broadcasting has gained more traction in recent years, yet it is only more recently that projects like ‘Connective Histories of the BBC’ have explored the possibilities for embedding oral histories of media institutions within web interfaces that allow for full-text searches of interview data (Sichani and Hendy 2021). Previous research infrastructures that allowed exploration of print, radio and television archival collections, such as CLARIAH Media Suite, made a concerted effort to provide information on the datasets (“Sound and Vision Radio Archive (up to 2018, iMMix Version, Deprecated) - CLARIAH Labs Dataset Registry” 2018; “Radio Collection DAAN’, CLARIAH Media Suite” 2024). However, there has not been a rigorous attempt to extract, compare and contextualise the metadata that accompany historical radio collections, either through oral history interviews or exploring possible means of visually representing such information.

Completeness	The element, property, and/or attribute is present.
Accuracy	Information is correct both semantically and syntactically.
Accessibility	Metadata can be read by both humans and machines.
Conformance to expectations	Values adhere to the expectations of your defined user communities (both internal and external).
Consistency	Semantic and structural values and elements are represented in a consistent manner across records. Values are consistent within your domain.
Timeliness	When the resource changes, the metadata is updated accordingly. When additional metadata becomes available or when metadata standards change, the metadata associated with the resource changes.
Provenance	You have information about the source of the metadata, and you can track metadata transformations back to the original form of the metadata record.

Table 1: Non-exhaustive overview of metadata quality criteria developed by the DLF Metadata Assessment Working Group.

Metadata quality assessment is a well recognised challenge for data providers in the cultural heritage sector and beyond. As an example, Table 1 offers a non-exhaustive overview of common metadata quality criteria developed by the DLF Metadata Assessment Working Group (Gavrilis et al. 2015). These criteria reflect common problems and information needs for researchers. Inspired by these categories, OHRA strives to collect expert knowledge for metadata quality assessment albeit choosing a qualitative approach which seeks to complement existing metadata rather than analysing it.

Oral History Interview Setup and Analysis

We selected interview partners based on two principles: They represent one of Impresso’s project partners and have a seniority level which corresponds to deep knowledge about the histories of the collections they provide. OHRA interviews take place in two rounds: A first (partially completed at the time of writing) focuses on the institutional history of radio archives. This includes reflections on the implications of institutional mergers, changing missions and archival strategies as well as the adoption of digitisation techniques. A second round will focus specifically on the intricacies of the collections the archive provides to the Impresso project and will be conducted in partnership with Impresso’s EPFL-based team, responsible for the ingestion and modeling of historical media collections. All interviews are semi-structured and based on a list of questions made available to the interview partner beforehand (see Table 2). Interviews are recorded using Cisco Webex and rely on their automated transcription service together with manual note keeping. Despite the inherent imperfections in automated transcription, Anthropic’s Claude AI turned out to be helpful to retrieve relevant interview quotes based on these notes, however always subject to manual validation.

History of the collection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How did preservation activities start in your archive? What were the priorities? What was there before systematic archival-work and documentation? 2. Are there any unexpected “gems” in your collections? E.g. artefacts/objects/recordings/catalogues/lists/index cards - any form of document, documentation or object one would not at first expect to find in there? 3. What is the best way to explore your collections beyond what will be in Impresso? 4. Can you think of a research project which used your data which was particularly successful in your view? 5. Are you aware of other institutions which contain documents related to your collections? For example, radio magazines, programming indices provided by amateur groups?
Digitisation history	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How did digitisation start? How have titles been selected for digitisation? 2. Is there an even distribution of OCR and/or speech to text quality in your collections? Is there a way to know what will likely be hidden due to poor quality?
Data shared with Impresso (tbd if applicable at the time of interview)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On which grounds were you able to share the data with us? 2. To which extent is it (not) representative of your collection? 3. In the Impresso team we have historians working on colonialism, feminism, history of format evolution in newspapers and radios and other topics. Imagine a historian sees your data in Impresso and wants to work with it. What should this person be aware of? 4. Which advice would you give for non-expert historians who want to work with radio data?

Table 2: *Questions for the semi-structured interviews provided to interview partners beforehand.*

First results

The OHRA project is still in its early and formative stages but, nevertheless, has already yielded promising insights into two radio collections: DeutschlandRadio via an interview with Jörg Wehling, head of documentation and archival services and Bas Agterberg, curator at the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV). The interviews revealed hitherto unknown aspects about both institutions’ collections, for example the existence of interview collections dating back to the 1930s in the case or the challenges to integrate data from different institutions in the case of the NISV.

Both interviews have shown that they can support the main user needs we identified above. To illustrate this, we have developed first drafts of researcher-facing information based on the interview with Bas Agterberg on the history of NISV’s collections. Figure 1 presents a timeline which reflects the periodization introduced by Agterberg and includes collection-specific information such as references to the Netherland’s colonial broadcasts and private recordings of Radio Oranje during World War II.

During the interviews we also discussed the intricacies inherent in any cultural heritage collection. Table 3 gives an overview of caveats to consider when working with NISV's collections together with general advice on how to approach the collections. Future work will focus on separating generally applicable caveats (early radio recordings being rare and fragmentary) from collection-specific ones (e.g. searches in Media Suite and DAAN will produce different results). Complementary to this, Table 4 gives an overview of collection-specific opportunities identified by our interview partner. This includes an overview of forthcoming data which will become available in the near future, another important source of information for researchers. References to existing resources generated by the institutions (e.g. the NISV Wiki²) and the public (e.g. Wikipedia) will be integrated as well wherever they provide meaningful additional information.

Figure 1: First draft of a timeline of NISV's collections targeting researcher needs.

² <https://wiki.beeldengeluid.nl/index.php/Hoofdpagina>.

Early Radio Recordings (1920s-1940s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recordings are rare and often fragmentary • Many recordings were accidental or made for specific purposes rather than preservation • Often only contains partial content rather than full programs
World War II Period (1940-1945)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radio Oranje (London) collection includes recordings provided by individual citizens as well as created by the broadcaster • Selection bias based on what was chosen for recording
Historical Preservation Bias (1950s-1980s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on journalistic reuse value rather than historical preservation • Materials often taped over or discarded
Conservation Tapes Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple unrelated recordings on single tapes • Complicated to work with specific collections • Poor documentation practices • Duplicates exist
Database and Search Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different search results between systems (Media Suite vs. DAAN), advice to use both in parallel • Date search issues may yield false positive results • Beware of incomplete metadata transfer between systems
Data integration after Institutional Merger	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital database doesn't maintain collection relationships • Difficult to identify sub-collections or related materials
Documentation and Context Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Much institutional knowledge was kept in archivists' heads rather than documented • Handwritten notes not systematically archived • Complicated provenance trails
Access Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some collections require direct archive contact • Different systems have different levels of accessibility • Language barriers with audio content
General advice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Always check multiple systems (DAAN, Media Suite, and direct archive contact) • Consider the broader historical context of preservation • Be aware that absence of material doesn't mean events didn't happen • Contact the archive directly for comprehensive research

Table 3: Overview of caveats to consider when working with NISV collections.

Complementary Sources for Missing Broadcasts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program guides • Broadcast logs with detailed information • Photographs (especially for television)
Recent Digital Collections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete 24/7 broadcasts since 2012
Biannual Complete Recording Weeks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two weeks per year of all Dutch channels including commercial ones
International Comparative Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International News Exchange materials • Opportunities to study how different countries use same footage • Extensive collection awaiting full integration
Phillips PHOHI Collection (1930s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colonial radio broadcasts to Indonesia • Unique preservation due to time difference needs
Academic Audio Collection (from 1930s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early academic use of audio recordings • Interview collections
Podcasts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full podcast archives recently acquired

Table 4: Overview of opportunities for researchers working with NISV collections.

Conclusion

This abstract gave an introduction to the OHRA project. Whilst still in an early stage, we can report that interviews with long-serving radio archivists have proven to be a viable means to obtain research-relevant information which is not readily available via public sources or can be extracted from metadata provided by the respective institution. Using the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision as an example, we have showcased how information extracted from interviews can help to address the user needs identified beforehand. This includes information about research opportunities, caveats, forthcoming data as well as a timeline of the collection history tailored to the needs of researchers.

These first interviews also pointed to the heterogeneity and complexity of radio archive collections. The organisation of radio archival sources is inherently linked to individual archivists, their visions, strategies and practical operational decision-making. Researchers and archivists need to become aware of this in order to make sense of the collections. This last point highlights the urgency to invest in a systematic approach to preserve the rich but also ephemeral institutional knowledge of archivists that is often lost as a consequence of retirement or career change.

References

- Birdsall, Carolyn, and Erica Harrison. 2022. "Researching Archival Histories of Radio." *TMG Journal for Media History* 25 (2): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.18146/tmg.841>.
- Boyd, Douglas A., and Mary A. Larson, eds. 2014. *Oral History and Digital Humanities: Voice, Access, and Engagement*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan US. <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137322029>.
- Dalen, Janneke van, and Nadja Šičarov. 2021. "How-To: Sharing Knowledge Among Generations of Archivists." *Journal of Film Preservation* 105:13–22.
- Ehrmann, Maud, Estelle Bunout, and Frédéric Clavert. 2022. "Digitised Historical Newspapers: A Changing Research Landscape (Introduction Chapter)." In *Digitised Historical Newspapers: A Changing Research Landscape*, 1–22. De Gruyter Oldenbourg. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110729214-001>.
- Flinn, Andrew, Doug Boyd, Charlie Morgan, and Julianne Nyhan. 2024. "Democratising Access? The Interface of New Technologies and Archived Life Stories." *Oral History Journal: The Life Story in Oral History Practice* 52 (3): 102–9.
- Gavrilis, Dimitris, Dimitra-Nefeli Makri, Leonidas Papachristopoulos, Stavros Angelis, Konstantinos Kravvaritis, Christos Papatheodorou, and Panos Constantopoulos. 2015. "Measuring Quality in Metadata Repositories." In *Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries*, edited by Sarantos Kapidakis, Cezary Mazurek, and Marcin Werla, 9316:56–67. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24592-8_5.
- "Radio Collection DAAN", CLARIAH Media Suite." 2024. 2024. <https://mediasuitedata.clariah.nl/dataset/radio-collection-daan>.
- Sichani, Anna-Maria, and David Hendy. 2021. "Connected Histories of the BBC: Opening up the BBC Oral History Archive to the Digital Domain." *J. Comput. Cult. Herit.* 15 (1): 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3480954>.
- "Sound and Vision Radio Archive (up to 2018, iMMix Version, Deprecated) - CLARIAH Labs Dataset Registry." 2018. 2018. <https://mediasuitedata.clariah.nl/dataset/nisv-catalogue-radio>.

Archiving Multiplatform Conspiracy Social Spaces: A Case Study of the QAnon Counter-Public

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Recent political events, including the COVID-19 pandemic, the invasion of Ukraine, as well as the 2020 and 2024 American elections, have underscored the growing prevalence of conspiracy narratives in public discourse (Enders et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2021; Ellison, 2024). Although such narratives are far from unprecedented (Barkun, 2003; Butter, 2020), their contemporary ubiquity is closely tied to QAnon's emergence on social networking sites (SNS). In this study, we argue that QAnon functions as a mobilizing phenomenon, fostering transmedia conspiracy content within a dispersed network of social spaces. Its foundation lies in an asymmetrical relationship between Q—an enigmatic figure who posted cryptic “drops” from 2017 to 2022 on platforms such as 4chan, 8chan, and 8kun (Zuckerman, 2019; Rothschild, 2020)—and the Anons, a decentralized group tasked with interpreting and disseminating these drops. Q's narratives revolve around a covert battle between allegedly corrupt Democratic elites in a “deep state” and patriotic forces led by Donald Trump, challenging American institutions, media, and electoral processes (Papasavva et al., 2021). While many of these narratives initially emerged in fringe online communities, they were rapidly amplified into mainstream arenas such as Reddit, YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter (O'Connor et al., 2020; Bloom and Moskalenko, 2020; Miller, 2021; Hannah, 2021; Engel, 2022). This amplification culminated in the “normification” (De Zeeuw et al., 2020) of QAnon's ideas, whereby fringe content infiltrated broader public discourse and became part of mainstream debates.

In this respect, Q and the Anons align with Fraser's (1990) notion of a counter-public—“parallel discursive arenas” in which marginalized groups “develop alternative interpretations of their identities, interests, and needs” (p. 81). Yet QAnon's digital orientation modernizes this concept, reflecting what Jackson and Foucault Welles (2015) describe as a “networked counter-public.” This conspiratorial network crystallizes through deliberate, though seemingly organic, efforts to integrate fringe narratives into mainstream discourse (Dilley et al., 2022; Rossetti & Zaman, 2023). Additionally, the fragmentation of authority in digital contexts has enabled ad hoc elites to establish communities beyond traditional power structures in media and politics.

Despite extensive research on QAnon's anglophone origins, significant gaps endure. First, QAnon's counter-public has shifted to alt-tech social spaces—Telegram, Odysee, and Truth Social—after its bans on mainstream platforms. These environments, often characterized by minimal moderation, decentralized hosting, and a tolerance for controversial or extremist content under “free speech” principles (Dowling, 2023; Siapera, 2023), remain underexplored, complicating any large-scale or systematic analysis of their content. Second, although QAnon's transnational presence has been documented (Labbe et al., 2020; Hoseini et al., 2021; Paschetto et al., 2022; Murru, 2022; Zehring & Domahidi, 2023), the adaptation of these narratives for French-, Italian-, and German-speaking audiences is poorly understood. We know little about the sociocultural processes that enable local adaptations or about the key figures who extend QAnon's ideological reach across linguistic and national boundaries.

This study addresses these gaps by examining the transmedia content produced by central actors within QAnon's networked counter-public across alternative platforms. Emphasizing data extraction, analysis, and archiving, we investigate how device-driven content, research practices, and platform infrastructures converge to construct, circulate, and preserve QAnon narratives in a mutable digital ecosystem. Employing a “mixed-method approach” (Crossley & Edwards, 2016; Snelson, 2016; Aguilera & Chevalier, 2021) that integrates computational tools with digital ethnography, our

methodology reveals the social and cultural practices that shape QAnon’s networked counter-public. This framework aligns with the “computational turn” (Hase et al., 2023), wherein researchers devise ways to systematically capture and analyze transmedia productions on SNS.

Earlier work centered on accessible Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for platforms such as Facebook, YouTube, and Twitter to map interactions, identify influential actors, and visualize information flows (Kosinski et al., 2015 ;Firdaniza et al., 2021; Antonakaki et al., 2021; Coromina & Padilla, 2022). Despite stricter limitations introduced after the Cambridge Analytica Scandal, API availability facilitated the development of replicable tools for examining socio-technical structures and negative behaviors such as bots, echo chambers, and disinformation (Marres & Gerlitz, 2015; Colleoni et al., 2014; Bessi & Ferrara, 2016; Airoldi et al., 2016; Gray et al., 2020). However, alt-tech platforms like Telegram, Odysee and Truth Social lack robust documentation for API usage, prompting us to devise adaptive strategies for data collection. We created custom codes to enable an efficient snowball sampling process (Chan, 2019; Buehling & Heft, 2023), starting with a small set of initial channels that expanded as shared material was traced to newly discovered channels. Ultimately, this yielded millions of messages and shared content (see annex 1).

We then analyzed the resulting dataset using graphical representations (e.g., monthly posting by language) and Social Network Analysis (SNA) with Gephi (Bastian et al., 2009), which highlights influential nodes, clusters, and interaction patterns in conspiracy networks (Logan et al., 2023). Yet SNA alone offers only a macro-level viewpoint, leaving the sociocultural nuances of central conspiracy actors unexamined. To address this, we conducted an in-depth study of Les DéQodeurs—three prominent figures in the francophone conspiracy community, who operated multiple accounts on platforms lacking APIs. Data collection combined crawling to locate interlinked web pages (Kausar et al., 2013) with static scraping of simple HTML sites and dynamic scraping, which simulates user actions to uncover hidden content on platforms without official APIs (Lotfi et al., 2021)—including Rumble, CrowdBunker, and X (see annex 2). This approach allowed us to build a transplatform posting graph, revealing cross-platform strategies and activity patterns underpinning QAnon’s counter-public.

Subsequent qualitative observations of high-profile channels and accounts drew on digital ethnography (Kozinets, 1997; Jeanne-Perrier, 2010; Jouët & Le Caroff, 2013; Caliandro, 2018), illuminating the social, cultural, and discursive foundations of conspiracy networks. We also invoked the concept of digital affordances, derived from Gibson’s (1979) original ecological approach to perception and Norman’s (1988) emphasis on perceived affordances in design. As updated by Ronzhyn et al. (2022), digital affordances in social media research refer to “the perceived, actual, or imagined properties of social media that emerge through the interplay of technological, social, and contextual factors.” This theoretical lineage clarifies how both conspiracy influencers and researchers adapt platform usage to their distinct objectives and constraints, illustrating the reciprocal relationship between user behaviors and platform features.

Our first key finding introduces “conspiracy influencers,” central figures who leverage Q’s drops to gain social and economic capital. Operating across transnational conspiracy communities located linguistically (see annex 3), these individuals fall into three categories: Interfacers, Transmedia influencers, and Unimedia influencers. Interfacers imitate Q’s persona, bridging global QAnon content with localized communities; Transmedia influencers combine video productions, articles, and livestreams to interpret current events; and Unimedia influencers concentrate on a single content format, forging deep ties with audiences while maintaining influence in broader ecosystems. Despite varied strategies, all prioritize visibility—expanding reach—and persistence—ensuring content remains accessible over time (Boyd, 2010). By constructing complex infrastructures of follower networks, accounts, and targeted content, they cater to audience preferences, circumvent moderation, and reinforce QAnon’s message.

Platform choice deeply shapes these practices. Odysee is often employed as a video repository that allows limited interactivity, while Telegram and Truth Social foster audience engagement and reciprocal content exchange. Yet each platform’s affordances also hinge on user perceptions. For instance, European conspiracy communities have made minimal inroads into Truth Social, which remains largely American in user base, implying that visibility aligns with entrenched audience habits. The prominence of English-speaking influencers underscores how adopting an anglophone-driven

approach bolsters broader impact, even though a considerable volume of Telegram content is produced in German.

Among francophone multimedia influencers, Les DéCodeurs demonstrates how platform affordances guide content production. Active on eleven platforms, they strive to maximize visibility by aligning their narratives with national and global events (see annex 4). They recontextualize material from French and global media alongside Q's drops, presenting and debating excerpts live, thereby weaving a continuous transmedia narrative. Technical refinements, such as green screens and polished visual design, lend a veneer of professionalism, while lively Telegram-based discussions nurture parasocial bonds. They also archive videos on Odysee to preserve content, guarding against "deplatforming." Ultimately, Les DéCodeurs illustrates how content production practices respond to audience demands for easy, up-to-date materials, simultaneously exporting conspiracy agendas across national boundaries.

A second key finding shows that these influencers' practices align with what Weltevrede (2016) terms "research affordances." The same visibility and persistence valued by influencers also prove pivotal for scholarship: archived material supports in-depth analysis of how conspiracy narratives evolve, tracks cross-linguistic adaptations, and elucidates sociotechnical factors influencing their spread. By storing content across multiple repositories, conspiracy influencers inadvertently build structured data that researchers can use to document shifting discourse over time. This mirrors a "follow the natives" approach (Caliandro, 2018), integrating user-driven behaviors into technical inquiry. However, platforms perpetually evolve through API updates, policy changes, and new Terms of Service (ToS)—thus research affordances remain inherently unstable. As Marres and Gerlitz (2015) suggest, refining existing methods, rather than designing entirely new ones, may be most effective, acknowledging the triangular interplay among research objectives, mediums, and methods. Indeed, some alt-tech platforms that offer "secluded" spaces for extremist communities can also provide ample data-collection opportunities, as illustrated by our extensive datasets.

Nonetheless, navigating these research affordances brings obstacles. Telegram's large-group calls, for example, remain inaccessible, while new Truth Social firewalls have rendered certain datasets unreplicable. Although Telegram and Odysee appear less restrictive than mainstream SNS, they still present legal and ethical dilemmas. Odysee's ToS explicitly prohibit unauthorized scraping, despite its public-facing content. Researchers must also address privacy obligations, especially with massive multimedia datasets (Fiesler et al., 2016). Although cloud-based solutions (i.e., Google Drive and Google Collab) can mitigate storage and data processing issues, they introduce additional costs and data stewardship concerns.

Ethical considerations arise when disseminating findings as well. Our Odysee and Telegram datasets can be hosted, for instance on Humanum, yet legal constraints deter public release of parallel datasets from Truth Social. These restrictions underscore the need for interdisciplinary cooperation among legal, technical, and social-science specialists to refine data-collection tactics and comply with ever-shifting regulations. Some scholars advocate a "data activist" stance (Venturini & Rogers, 2019; Caliandro, 2021), maintaining that platforms integral to public dialogue must not lock down data without accountability. Bruns (2019) similarly highlights the ethical and legal imperative for independent research, asserting that platforms profiting from user data have a responsibility to facilitate analyses of their societal influence. Still, occupying these activist or pioneering positions can be fraught with risks if platforms impose legal hurdles. Researchers must therefore navigate a delicate balance between seeking robust, large-scale data and preserving ethical and legal standards in the realm of alternative digital environments.

Annexes

Annex 1. Overview of Collected Corpora by Platform and Depth				
Platform	Depth	Channels	Content	Shared Content
Telegram	Depth 0	15	1,075,351	408,835
	Depth 1	5,709	93,428,687	31,149,497
	Depth 2	134,221	532,430,305	467,242,455
Odysee	Depth 0	80	38,906	3,083
	Depth 1	328	301,721	37,169
	Depth 2	1,748	1,273,486	229,479
	Depth 3	9,498	3,873,357	466,872
	Depth 4	13,432	4,962,595	516,803
Truth Social	Depth 0	8	4,630	3,336
	Depth 1	410	5,050,880	2,896,326
	Depth 2	61,427	239,234,822	177,184,754

Annex 2. Overview of Collected Corpora Related to Les Décodeurs	
Websites	3,036
Telegram	7,125
Odysee	483
Rumble	307
VK	13
Crowd Bunker	74
X	1,958

Annex 3: Graphical Renderings of Conspiracy Communities with Gephi

From left to right: Telegram, Odyssey, and Truth Social. Each Gephi-generated graph displays the distinct communities identified using the Louvain method, with the most influential actors labeled within each cluster.

Annex 4: Graphical Rendering of Monthly Publications by Les DéQodeurs

This visualization depicts how Les DéQodeurs distribute their content over time across various social media platforms, illustrating the cadence and reach of their posting activity.

References

- Aguilera, Thomas, and Tom Chevalier. 2021. "Les méthodes mixtes: vers une méthodologie3.0?" *Revue française de science politique* 71 (3): 361–63. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rfsp.713.0361>.
- Airoidi, Massimo, Davide Beraldo, and Alessandro Gandini. 2016. "Follow the Algorithm: An Exploratory Investigation of Music on YouTube." *Poetics* 57: 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.poetic.2016.05.001>.
- Antonakaki, Despoina, Paraskevi Fragopoulou, and Sotiris Ioannidis. 2021. "A Survey of Twitter Research: Data Model, Graph Structure, Sentiment Analysis and Attacks." *Expert Systems with Applications* 164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.114006>.
- Barkun, Michael. 2003. *A Culture of Conspiracy: Apocalyptic Visions in Contemporary America*. 1st ed. Berkeley: University of California Press. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1525/j.ctt1pnjvz>.

- Bastian, Mathieu, Sebastien Heymann, and Mathieu Jacomy. 2009. "Gephi: An Open Source Software for Exploring and Manipulating Networks." *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media* 3 (1): 361–62. <https://doi.org/10.1609/icwsm.v3i1.13937>.
- Bessi, Alessandro, and Emilio Ferrara. 2016. "Social Bots Distort the 2016 US Presidential Election Online Discussion." *First Monday* 21 (11/7). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v21i11.7090>.
- Bloom, Mia, and Sophia Moskalenko. 2021. *Pastels and Pedophiles: Inside the Mind of QAnon*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Boyd, Danah. 2010. "Social Network Sites as Networked Publics: Affordances, Dynamics, and Implications." In *A Networked Self: Identity, Community, and Culture on Social Network Sites*, edited by Zizi Papacharissi, 39–58. New York: Routledge.
- Buehling, Kilian, and Annett Heft. 2023. "Pandemic Protesters on Telegram: How Platform Affordances and Information Ecosystems Shape Digital Counterpublics." *Social Media + Society* 9 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231199430>.
- Butter, Michael. 2020. *The Nature of Conspiracy Theories*. Translated by Sharon Howe. Cambridge, UK / Medford, MA: Polity.
- Bruns, Axel. 2019. "After the 'APIcalypse': Social Media Platforms and Their Fight against Critical Scholarly Research." *Information, Communication & Society* 22 (11): 1544–66. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2019.1637447>.
- Caliandro, Alessandro. 2018. "Digital Methods for Ethnography: Analytical Concepts for Ethnographers Exploring Social Media Environments." *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography* 47 (5): 551–78. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891241617702960>.
- Caliandro, Alessandro. 2021. "Repurposing Digital Methods in a Post-API Research Environment: Methodological and Ethical Implications." *Italian Sociological Review* 11 (4S): 225–42. <https://doi.org/10.13136/isr.v11i4S.433>.
- Chen, Emily, Herbert Chang, Ashwin Rao, Kristina Lerman, Geoffrey Cowan, and Emilio Ferrara. 2021. "COVID-19 Misinformation and the 2020 U.S. Presidential Election." *Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*. <https://doi.org/10.37016/mr-2020-57>.
- Colleoni, Elanor, Alessandro Rozza, and Adam Arvidsson. 2014. "Echo Chamber or Public Sphere? Predicting Political Orientation and Measuring Political Homophily in Twitter Using Big Data." *Journal of Communication* 64 (2): 317–32. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12084>.
- Coromina, Òscar, and Adrián Padilla. *How to Study YouTube With API-Based Methods*. Edited by Kate M. Miltner. *Sage Research Methods: Doing Research Online*. SAGE Publications, Ltd., 2022. How-to Guide. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781529609417>.
- Crossley, Nick, and Gemma Edwards. 2016. "Cases, Mechanisms and the Real: The Theory and Methodology of Mixed-Method Social Network Analysis." *Sociological Research Online* 21 (2): 217–85. <https://doi.org/10.5153/sro.3920>.
- De Zeeuw, Daniël, Sal Hagen, Stijn Peeters, and Emilija Jokubauskaite. 2020. "Tracing Normification: A Cross-Platform Analysis of the QAnon Conspiracy Theory." *First Monday* 25 (11). <https://doi.org/10.5210/fm.v25i11.10643>.
- Dilley, L., W. Welna, and F. Foster. 2022. "QAnon Propaganda on Twitter as Information Warfare: Influencers, Networks, and Narratives." *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2207.05118>.
- Dowling, Melissa-Ellen. 2023. "Far-Right Populism in Alt-Tech: A Challenge for Democracy?" *New Media & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448231205889>.
- Ellison, Sarah. 2024. "Conspiracy Theories Shaped the 2024 Election." *Washington Post*, November 4. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/politics/2024/11/04/election-2024-conspiracy-theories/>.
- Enders, Adam M., Joseph E. Uscinski, Casey Klofstad, and Justin Stoler. 2020. "The Different Forms of COVID-19 Misinformation and Their Consequences." *Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*. <https://doi.org/10.37016/mr-2020-48>.

- Engel, Kristen, Yiqing Hua, Taixiang Zeng, and Mor Naaman. 2022. "Characterizing Reddit Participation of Users Who Engage in the QAnon Conspiracy Theories." *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.07433>.
- Fiesler, Casey, Cliff Lampe, and Amy S. Bruckman. 2016. "Reality and Perception of Copyright Terms of Service for Online Content Creation." In *Proceedings of the 19th ACM Conference on Computer-Supported Cooperative Work & Social Computing (CSCW '16)*, 1450–61. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2818048.2819931>.
- Fraser, Nancy. 1990. "Rethinking the Public Sphere: A Contribution to the Critique of Actually Existing Democracy." *Social Text*, no. 25/26: 56–80. <https://doi.org/10.2307/466240>.
- Gibson, James J. 1979. *The Ecological Approach to Visual Perception*. New York: Houghton Mifflin.
- Gray, Jonathan, Liliana Bounegru, and Tommaso Venturini. 2020. "'Fake News' as Infrastructural Uncanny." *New Media & Society* 22 (2): 317–41. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444819856912>.
- Hannah, Matthew N. 2021. "A Conspiracy of Data: QAnon, Social Media, and Information Visualization." *Social Media + Society* 7 (3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051211036064>.
- Hase, Valerie, Daniela Mahl, and Mike S. Schäfer. 2023. "The 'Computational Turn': An 'Interdisciplinary Turn'? A Systematic Review of Text as Data Approaches in Journalism Studies." *Online Media and Global Communication* 2 (1): 122–43. <https://doi.org/10.1515/omgc-2023-0003>.
- Hoseini, Mohamad, Philippe Melo, Fabricio Benevenuto, Anja Feldmann, and Savvas Zannettou. 2021. "On the Globalization of the QAnon Conspiracy Theory Through Telegram." *arXiv*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2105.13020>.
- Jeanne-Perrier, Valérie. 2010. "Parler de la télévision sur Twitter: une 'réception' oblique à partir d'une 'conversation' médiatique?" *Communication & langages* 166 (4): 127–47. <https://doi.org/10.4074/S0336150010014079>.
- Labbe, Charlotte, Valentina Padovese, Mario Richter, and Anna-Sophie Harling. 2020. "Rapport: QAnon en Europe." Juillet. *NewsGuard*, Paris. <https://www.newsguardtech.com/special-reports/special-report-qanon/>.
- Kosinski, Michal, Sandra C. Matz, Samuel D. Gosling, Vess Popov, and David Stillwell. 2015. "Facebook as a Research Tool for the Social Sciences: Opportunities, Challenges, Ethical Considerations, and Practical Guidelines." *American Psychologist* 70 (6): 543–56. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0039210>.
- Lotfi, Chaimaa, Swetha Srinivasan, Myriam Ertz, and Imen Latrous. 2021. "Web Scraping Techniques and Applications: A Literature Review." In *Proceedings of the SCRS Conference on Intelligent Systems*, 381–94.
- Marres, Noortje, and Carolin Gerlitz. 2015. "Interface Methods: Renegotiating Relations Between Digital Social Research, STS, and Sociology." *The Sociological Review* 64 (1): 21–46. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-954X.12314>.
- Murru, Maria Francesca. 2022. "QAnon and Its Conspiracy Milieu: The Italian Case." In *Populism and Science in Europe*, edited by Hande Eslen-Ziya and Alberta Giorgi, 163–84. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-97535-7_8.
- Norman, Donald A. 1988. *The Psychology of Everyday Things*. New York: Basic Books.
- Pasquetto, Irene, Alberto Pasquetto, Luca Tacchetti, Alessandra Spada, and Gianni Riotta. 2022. "Disinformation as Infrastructure: Making and Maintaining the QAnon Conspiracy on Italian Digital Media." *OSF Preprints*. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/btjuf>.
- Rossetti, Michael, and Tauhid Zaman. 2023. "Bots, Disinformation, and the First Impeachment of U.S. President Donald Trump." *PLOS ONE* 18 (5). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0283971>.

Ronzhyn, Alexander, Ana Sofia Cardenal, and Albert Batlle Rubio. 2022. "Defining Affordances in Social Media Research: A Literature Review." *New Media & Society* 25 (11): 3165–88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14614448221135187>.

Siapera, Eugenia. 2023. "Alt Tech and the Public Sphere: Exploring Bitchute as a Political Media Infrastructure." *European Journal of Communication* 38 (5): 446–65. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02673231231189041>.

Snelson, Chareen L. 2016. "Qualitative and Mixed Methods Social Media Research: A Review of the Literature." *International Journal of Qualitative Methods* 15 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406915624574>.

Weltevrede, Esther, and Erik Borra. 2016. "Platform Affordances and Data Practices: The Value of Dispute on Wikipedia." *Big Data & Society* 3 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951716653418>.

Zehring, Maximilian, and Emese Domahidi. 2023. "German Corona Protest Mobilizers on Telegram and Their Relations to the Far Right: A Network and Topic Analysis." *Social Media + Society* 9 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231155106>.

Zuckerman, Ethan. 2019. "QAnon and the Emergence of the Unreal." *Journal of Design and Science*, no. 6. <https://doi.org/10.21428/7808da6b.6b8a82b9>.